

School of Business & Creative Industries

**AN EFFORT TO ESTABLISH EFFECTIVE CORPORATE GOVERNANCE PRACTICE,
IMPACTS ON CORRUPTION, AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN DEVELOPING
COUNTRIES: A CASE OF MONGOLIA**

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ABSTRACT

Mongolia has been experiencing evolving socio-economic challenges since its economic reform in the 1990s due to a lack of transparency and insufficient accountability. The spread of corruption and its effects directly depends on transparency and accountability. Grand, optimum and public sector corruption are endemic in Mongolia. Thus, this research aims to define alternative ways for improving and strengthening transparency and accountability as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia.

Qualitative archival research alongside observation were conducted based in Mongolia to determine these practical approaches. Data were collected through archival research and analysed through a weighted scoring model, whereas the observed information was analysed through grounded theory analysis. Findings of the weighted scoring model were compared with those of the grounded theory analysis. Results introduced an integrity restoration framework consisting of five fundamental processes: the practice of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power, enhancement of inclusiveness, accomplishments and sustainable development. Each process involves further practical approaches.

These findings imply that a successful implementation of practical approaches likely improves and strengthens the overall transparency and accountability practices. As a result, a normative layout of isomorphic institutional pressure is formed to combat corruption, thus further contributing to sustainable development.

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CHAPTER 1: RESEARCH INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of the Chapter

This chapter introduces the research, provides background information, defines the scope and presents structures. Section 1.2 presents the topic and context of the study. Section 1.3 explains the researcher's personal motivation for selecting the topic. Section 1.4 discusses the scope and focus of this study, which determines particular aspects of the research topic. Section 1.5 explains the importance of the study, Section 1.6 presents the study's aims, research questions and objectives, emphasising what the researcher aims to find out and how the researcher approaches it. Lastly, Section 1.7 illustrates the structure of subsequent chapters.

1.2. Topic and Context

Over the last decade, governance disputes have been the interest of development studies (Leftwich, 1994), socio-economics (Campbell et al., 1991; Hollingsworth et al., 1994; Hollingsworth & Boyer, 1997; Crouch, 2006), international relations and globalisation studies (Senarclens, 1998), organisational studies (Starkey, 1995; Jones et al., 1997), public administration (Rhodes, 2000), policy implementation and social policy studies (Daly, 2003) and political science (Christopher, 2010).

Diverse literature has documented an immense alteration in governance, depending on its position in a diverse field of study. Nevertheless, control, cooperation and inclusiveness are the essential premises in modern governance theory. Excessive controlling power and government influence have been condemned for corruption, poverty, political instability, economic stagnation, muddled priorities, abuse of human rights and chaos. These social issues have been at the centre of the establishment of good governance, sustainable development debate and development programs of international donor organisations and developing countries. Good governance and institution can be perceived as people-oriented, responsive, cooperative, accountable and efficient systems and mechanisms (Huque, 2001).

For instance, the contemporary world has two effective governance mechanisms: market control mechanisms (also called the Anglo-Saxon mechanisms) in the United Kingdom and the United States and the large-shareholder control mechanisms (also called the Continental European mechanisms) in Japan, Germany, France and Spain (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). The legal system of effective governance mechanisms is classified into civil and common law. The legal system signifies the norms that legalise company behaviour, protect minority shareholders' rights through diverse protective laws and prompt ways to develop a capital market (La Porta et al., 1997) and economy (Levine, 1999). The code of effective corporate governance comprises recommended best practices regarding the structure and behaviour of the board of directors (BOD) (Dalton et al., 1998) and alternatives for potential deficiencies in the minority shareholders' protection in the regulatory system (Aguilera & Cuervo-Cazurra, 2009). In contrast, this normative governance mechanism is absent in the developing country of Mongolia. Grand corruption is widespread, which further extends to its public and private sectors, regulatory system and institutional

environment. As a result, the country has been facing issues in poverty, inequality, transparency, accountability, society, cultural control, development and economic growth.

World-leading aid organisations, such as the World Bank (World Bank, 1994; 1977), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 1995), the United Kingdom's Overseas Development Administration (ODA), the G8 countries (the United States, France, the United Kingdom, Italy, Germany, Canada, Japan and Russia) (Council on Foreign Relations, 2014), the Committee of the European Communities, the New Millennium Challenge Account and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 1997; 2002) have been great supporters and frequent advocates of good governance concepts, particularly for aid-receiving nations. They aim to encourage democracy, the rule of law, decentralisation, transparency, accountability and public participation in the decision-making process of development agenda. For example, the World Bank has emphasised that good governance is the foundation of establishing and sustaining a condition that cultivates equitable and robust development and associated essential counterparts to vibrant economic arrangements; this concept is based on its considerable superior experience in several developing nations (World Bank, 1997).

The institutional environment also plays a primary role in the constitution of governance mechanisms because dynamic institutional norms are distinctive across nations. This distinction is due to differences in myth, tradition, culture and religion. Transparency, accountability, responsibility and fairness are the four central principles that underpin effective governance mechanisms. These principles are equally important mechanisms and structures (Husted & Folger, 2004). Corruption could happen when public officials and civil servants lack accountability and prudence over public services (Alt & Lassen, 2006). Accordingly, a great practice of transparency and accountability recruits civil society against corrupt conduct.

In the case of Mongolia, the country faces various governance challenges that impact the development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), economic growth and sustainable development. Mongolia has gained its democracy 30 years ago. However, the state has several problems that pressure governance, including market concentration, the scope of corruption, poverty and inequality, insufficient accountability and the absence of transparency. Authorities have been striving to strengthen the anti-corruption regulatory framework for the past two decades. However, the 2019 Monitoring Report has emphasised corruption in the country as substantial; the report was published by the Anti-corruption Network of the OECD for Central Asia and Eastern Europe (IMF, 2019). Moreover, the implementation of action plans has been highlighted as uneven and limited. Furthermore, the enforcement of the anti-corruption framework and development of governance in other national functions limit the exposure to corruption through improved transparency and accountability. These government functions include the regulatory environment, the rule of law, and the financial sector management.

In contrast, although the regulatory framework has evolved since the economic reform in the 1990s, extensive loopholes remain, resulting in unintentional consequences. Although an appropriate institutional and legal framework is being improved, the penalty measures and effectiveness of enforcement mechanisms remain weak, thus requiring change. In addition, Mongolia currently faces another governance challenge regarding the inclusiveness and growth in employment. During its economic boom, Mongolia's overall economic performance

was between 6% and 7% on average. Nonetheless, the rate of poverty and inequality has hardly dropped over the years and remained at a rate of over 28% in 2018 (IMF, 2019). By contrast, the unemployment rate has jumped in the last 2 years. Thus, despite economic growth, poverty, inequality and unemployment rates have remained big issues that question Mongolia's governance mechanisms.

Governance mechanisms are categorised into normative structures and organisational behavioural processes (Suzanne et al., 2014). The normative mechanism refers to the social setting in which the organisation operates, for instance, the regulatory environment, financial market and human rights protection. In contrast, the organisational behavioural processes involve day-to-day activities, such as board meetings, strategic decision-making, operational performance and efficiency and the consideration of shareholders and other stakeholders. Organisational behaviour is habitual and reflects normative mechanisms; thus, focusing on normative governance mechanisms has greater importance than focusing on corporate governance practice in a fragile state. Accordingly, this study will further focus on normative governance mechanisms to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia.

1.3. Researcher's Motivation

Firstly, the researcher has Mongolian background and, throughout her teenage years, had witnessed the rich getting richer, the poor getting poorer and an increasing number of people living in poverty and suffering from afflictions. People have become more vulnerable, though Mongolia has been recognised by the International Monetary Fund (2012) as one of the 29 rich developing countries in terms of resources. The country hosts 10% of the world's coal reserves, amounting to approximately 162 billion tonnes in 2011, with 17 active coal mines (Sawe, 2019). According to the latest data from the United Nations (UN), Mongolia's population is only over 3.3 million as of March 2021 (Worldometer, 2021). Comparing the given figures in natural resources and the total population, Mongolians are expected to have abundant export of those natural resources. The 2016 report of the International Trade Administration (2017) presented that Mongolia's mining industry accounted for more than 30% of the state budget income, 85% of exports, more than 70% of the national foreign direct investment and approximately 20% of the GDP. Despite the extensive export of natural resources, the Asian Development Bank (2018) reported that over 28% of Mongolian citizens live in poverty in 2018. This national poverty line has been stable with uneven improvement in poverty reduction among rural and urban areas. Hagenars (1991) and MacPherson and Silburn (1998) defined poverty as a shortage of income to obtain minimum nutrition and minimum consumption of goods and services required for individual well-being.

This phenomenon has raised several questions: Why do many people still live in poverty given the number of natural resources? Why do wealthy people get wealthier, whereas the poor get poorer? Why is the number of socio-economic challenges increasing, such as deteriorated public services, unemployment, corrupt activities and distrust in society? These questions have led to the examination of corporate governance practices, corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia. Accordingly, the researcher seeks alternative ways for establishing good governance to enforce the right behaviour and prosper economic development as opposed to pervasive corruption

and contribution toward sustainable development. Additionally, reports on the disappointing nature of governance and institutional establishment were also considered additional concerns.

Secondly, after many years of social science study in the United Kingdom, the researcher has been aiming to make a positive difference in a complex society to a certain extent. After extensive brainstorming for research topics, the researcher had recognised that governance is more relevant to the existing situation in Mongolia. Because the researcher had wanted to make a positive difference in society, she had chosen the topic of an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia.

1.4. Scope and Focus of Study

The philosophy of governance deals with conflicts of interests between different stakeholders, particularly agency problems, separation of ownership and finance. Accordingly, a paramount discussion of governance ensures return on investment, enabling a complex and interrelated scope. Therefore, an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia designates such assurance and a trustful and confidential environment through different structures, diverse mechanisms and systems. However, it does not mean that effective governance can be conducted in the same manner in all places. Effective governance is developed through the reflection and alteration of an institutional environment, culture, social belief, economic situation and financial sources, political background and legal system.

People perceive governance as comprised of corporate governance, shareholders, the BOD and other stakeholders. In a developing country such as Mongolia, the corporate governance issue is bigger than the principle–agent relationship. The reason is that corporate governance in emerging economies is confronted with peculiar problems that differ from those of developed economies. Issues faced in developed economies include establishing the rule-based corporate governance mechanism as opposed to the existing relationship-based mechanism, confronting layered interests, promoting an acceptable culture, improving minority shareholders' protection and encouraging a good corporate governance practice.

Contrarily, ineffective corporate governance practice indicates insufficient transparency and an absence of accountability. This condition further creates a convenient environment for corrupt individuals to perform their misconduct. Corruption can be defined as prioritising self-interest before the public interest or seeking benefits at the cost of others. This condition underpins the majority of socio-economic problems. For instance, modern governance theory holds that corruption causes a concentration of controlling power in few individuals prone to asymmetric information, constraints on the cooperation between social structures and limitation on inclusiveness driven inequality and poverty levels while practising insufficient transparency and lack of accountability. This condition becomes a threat to sustainable development due to resource misallocation, restraining opportunities for individuals and businesses. This situation is the case of Mongolia, one of the developing countries and rich in natural resources. The country has been working together with international organisations and signed many anti-corruption conventions. However, corruption in the country has been rapidly spreading. Therefore, the scope of this study covers corporate governance, corruption and sustainable development.

1.5. Importance of the Study

Most corporate governance studies were built on firm performance based on agency theory, stakeholder theory, protection of ownership, and shareholder wealth. However, the term corporate governance refers beyond those theories. Compared with developed economies, developing economies, such as Mongolia, have family-owned businesses, a government-controlled economy, non-product markets, influences from external factors and low living standards. In the case of Mongolia, corruption is widespread, involving the top level of the state, government organisations, public and private sectors, institutional entities, the judiciary system, banking systems and the media. Mongolia has been working closely with the World Bank to develop good governance for nearly three decades (World Bank, 2021). Furthermore, the country launched an anti-corruption legal framework in 1996; joined the Istanbul Anti-corruption Action Plan in 2003; signed the UN Convention in 2006; and established the Independent Authority Against Corruption (IAAC) in 2007 to supervise the implementation of anti-corruption rules and regulations (IMF, 2019). However, corruption has been rapidly spreading over time. Non-transparent, non-accountable, irresponsible and unfair public official activities, government officials' self-defence of their influential connections, failure of the judiciary system to tackle such misconduct and majority of the residents' vulnerability to public services have been increasing. These conditions lead to questioning the governance mechanisms in Mongolia.

In comparison between population and its natural resources, Mongolia has a high chance of creating a middle-class level in its society, such as Qatar with effective resource-based management if accountability, transparency, responsibility and fairness are enforced and practiced (World Atlas, 2018). However, it is worrying that the nation is heading to become another Nigeria, where oil discovery in the 1970s brought conflicts and environmental debris and where national wealth was wasted by corruption, leaving half of the population in poverty (World Bank, 2006). Singer (1950) and Prebisch (1950) claimed that resource-based industries have limited innovative opportunities, and their trade tends to decline in the long run. Therefore, exploring alternative transparency and accountability approaches as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia are necessary.

1.6. Research Aim and Questions

This research aims to strengthen practice of transparency and accountability in developing countries as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Particularly, the research aim focuses on three essential premises: controlling power, cooperation and inclusiveness. Accordingly, this study aims to address the following research questions:

1. What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be used to enhance structural cooperation among different social participants to establish effective corporate governance practice, combat corruption and support sustainable development?

2. What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be applied to decentralise the controlling power of blockholders to establish effective corporate governance practice, combat corruption and support sustainable development?
3. What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be used to promote public participation to establish effective corporate governance practice, combat corruption and support sustainable development?

1.7. Structure of Chapters

This study on an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in developing countries: a case of Mongolia involves six chapters as follows:

1. **Research Introduction.** This chapter presents the topic and context of the study, researcher's motivation, scope and focus of the study, importance of the study; study aims and objectives, and structure of each chapter.
2. **Literature Review.** This chapter focuses on a review of various articles, books and reports on corporate governance, corruption and sustainable development. The chapter enables familiarisation with the contemporary condition of knowledge to determine unresolved issues, construct a conceptual framework and define research gaps.
3. **Research Methodology.** This chapter discusses the rationale and available research methodologies for this study. It also describes the steps done to perform this research. These steps include describing the type of data collected, data collection and analysis procedures, duration of the study, management of ethical principles and the validity and reliability of the study.
4. **Data Collection and Analysis.** This chapter focuses on data analysis through the selected research methodology. Methods and reports of these analyses are performed with the selected analytical techniques, which have been addressed in the Research Methodology chapter.
5. **Discussion of Findings.** This chapter focuses on the meaning, significance and relevance of study findings by interpreting and assessing the results, discussing how the findings address the research questions and relate to the study's conceptual framework. The chapter is divided into four main sections: interpretation of the study findings, discussion of implications, study limitations and recommendations.
6. **Conclusion.** This last chapter summarises the entire study on an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Most importantly, it ensures whether the research aims and objectives are met, followed by a discussion of a new knowledge contribution of this study and suggestions for further research.

The content of each chapter has been described in the respective Introduction section.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2. 1. Purpose of the Chapter

This chapter provides essential knowledge about the research topic to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in developing countries: a case of Mongolia. The researcher has reviewed numerous studies from journal articles, dissertations, books and research reports. Then, this section is structured as follows.

Section 2.2 presents an argument about corporate governance in developed countries versus that in developing countries. Section 2.3 discusses improvements and cessation of sustainable development based on three corporate governance models, namely the shareholder protection model, stakeholder model and corporate social responsibility (CSR) model to corporate governance. Section 2.4 explains the constitution of, institutional impacts on and significance of accountability and disclosure in corporate governance in the context of corporate governance dealings in Mongolia as a developing country. Section 2.5 presents corruption induced by the constitution of corporate governance. This type of corruption indicates tax fraud, socio-economic instability (i.e. a deficient social interconnection and a lack of capability for state reform), economic maladministration and statistical control. Section 2.6 presents anti-corruption actions and actions taken to improve the regulatory environment. Section 2.7 discusses sustainable development considering cooperation, controlling power and participation. Section 2.8 summarises the chapter. Finally, Sections 2.9 and 2.10 define the study's conceptual framework and gaps, respectively, based on the literature review.

2. 2. Corporate Governance: Developed versus Developing Countries

The beginning of the 21st century of Europe and the United States witnessed the corporate outrages of WorldCom, Pharmalat and Enron due to poor governance and mismanagement. Thereafter, many authors have emphasised the term corporate governance in various contexts. Sir Adrian Cadbury, corporate governance committee director in the United Kingdom (Cadbury, 1992) defined corporate governance consists of various different systems and mechanisms of processes, rules, and practices by which corporations governed and controlled. Accordingly, the effective governance designates: meaningfulness, not just structure form; practices, not just rules; and implementation, not just compliance with.

The definition of corporate governance can be categorised into two general groups: the narrow and wide perceptions of corporate governance. Larcker et al. (2005) explained the narrow perception of corporate governance as an associated set of systems that impacts the decisions of managers (agents) considering a separation of control and ownership. This perception is also known as the organisational behaviour process (Dunphy et al., 2003). Several studies highlighted that this perception is extensively constructed from agency theory that deals with issues emerging from agency costs and shareholders assigning the responsibility of directing the organisation to managers (Jensen & Mecklings, 1976; Hills & Jones, 1992; Kulik, 2007). Neyroud (2011) stated that

Anglo-Saxon countries are the leading representatives of the narrow perception of corporate governance practice. These countries include English-speaking states, such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, though the United States and the United Kingdom are excluded.

The narrow perception of corporate governance is unsuitable for developing economies, particularly in the case of Mongolia, which previously had a communist regime. Several scholars have asserted that the definition of narrow corporate governance fails to tackle systematic challenges at the core of corporate governance (Oman et al., 2003). These challenges involve the underdevelopment of institutional infrastructure, which is essential for corporate governance to prosper, whereas it is resilient in developed economies (Adegbite & Nakajima, 2012; Isukul & Chizea, 2015). In contrast, the majority of developing countries have weak judicial institutions and inadequately outlined property rights (Okike, 2007; Adegbite, 2012). Thus, the wide perception of corporate governance is required, where corporate governance outside the internal determinants including managers and shareholders; the purpose is to include political practice, governing institutions and the rule of law in institutional infrastructure (Ahunwan, 2002; Tsamenyi & Uddin, 2008; Wanyama et al., 2013). Moreover, Oman et al. (2003) highlighted that corporate governance is associated with public and non-state-owned institutions, recognised and unrecognised, which collectively shape the relationship between managers and investors. Similarly, Ahunwan (2002) and Okike (2007) added that these institutions enforce state laws, rules, regulations, policies and practices and set appropriate corporate norms. Therefore, this definition of corporate governance reveals that emerging economies have wide influences and themes of corporate governance.

Siddiqui (2010) and Agyei-Mensah (2017) emphasised the misleading perception that corporate governance does not exist in emerging economies due to their poorly outlined property rights, insubstantial financial institutions, weak minority shareholder protection, few publicly listed companies and widespread corruption in the private and public sectors. Contrarily, numerous scholars specified that most corporate governance literature is built on the principal–agency conflict that reflects the narrow perception of corporate governance in developed economies (Adegbite & Nakajima, 2012; Isukul & Chizea, 2015).

Consequently, although the discussion addresses corporate governance issues in developed economies, the description fails to capture such challenges in developing economies (Wanyama et al., 2009; Adegbite & Nakajima, 2012; Nakpodia et al., 2016). Analysts stated that the underlying factors of this phenomenon are the peculiar corporate governance problems in emerging economies, which are distinctive from those of developed economies (Ahunwan, 2002; Oman et al., 2003; Tsamenyi & Uddin, 2008). Corporate governance dealings significantly differ between developed and developing economies. The main corporate governance problem of developed economies can be defined as the principal–agency conflict (Gillian, 2006; Brennan & Solomon, 2008). In contrast, that of developing economies can be described as the installation of rule-based corporate governance mechanism as opposed to the existing relationship-based mechanism. This rule-based mechanism confronts layered interests, promotes acceptable cultures, improves minority investor protection and encourages good corporate governance practice (Wanyama et al., 2009; Adegbite, 2015).

In addition, studies on corporate governance in emerging economies, such as Mongolia, are limited. Nevertheless, researchers in the field of corporate governance in developing countries are increasing (Wanyama et al., 2009; Chanda et al., 2017). This present study is built on the need to examine existing corporate governance systems and practices in Mongolia, identifying the barriers to the successful implementation of corporate governance and proposing alternative approaches to creating effective corporate governance practices in Mongolia. This study will provide insightful information not only for researchers in the field of corporate governance in developing economies but also for policymakers who are responsible for establishing policy frameworks that shape corporate governance practices and policies. This study also has implications for international aid organisations that manage development projects of good corporate governance agenda in developing economies.

Table 1: *Differences in Corporate Governance Challenges between Developed and Developing Countries*

<i>Dealings</i>	<i>Developed Countries</i>	<i>Developing Countries</i>
Corporate governance perception	Narrow perception is defined as an associated set of systems that impacts the decision of managers (agents) considering the separation of control and ownership	Wide perception is defined as the systematic challenges at the core of corporate governance, such as underdeveloped institutional infrastructure, which narrow perception fails to tackle
Institutional infrastructure	Resilient with a strong regulatory and judiciary system and extensively outlined property rights	Fragile with a weak regulatory and judiciary system, inadequately outlined property rights, insubstantial financial institution, weak minority shareholder protection, few publicly listed companies and widespread corruption in private and public sectors
Determinants	Managers and shareholders	Political practice, governing institutions and the rule of law practice
Areas of concern	Principal–agency conflict	Establishing a rule-based mechanism as opposed to the existing relationship-based mechanism, confronting layered interests, promoting acceptable cultures, improving minority investor protection and encouraging a good corporate governance practice

2. 3. Corporate Governance Models: Improvements and Cessation of Sustainable Development

In corporate governance literature, methods focusing on wealth interest are more prevalent than inclusive methods that consider various stakeholders (Aguilera & Jackson, 2010; Claessens & Yurtoglu, 2012; Hamrick et al., 2008). Three extensive viewpoints contribute to the argument on corporate governance and its impacts on corporate obligations: the shareholder value, stakeholder and political CRS methods. The corporate governance literature has documented numerous other methods, such as approaches based on economic, institutional and behavioural perspectives. These approaches focus on different concentrations of analysis and deal with either internal aspects of behavioural and structural conditions or external aspects of institutional conditions (Hamrick et al., 2008).

Here, the comparative method investigates the differences between wealthy institutions and corporate governance impacts (Hall & Soskice, 2001; Whitley, 1999). The behavioural corporate governance method identifies the impact of confirmed or unconfirmed power structures and incentives on individual action (Wiseman & Gomez-Mejia, 1998). The actor-centric corporate governance method links the different concentrations of analysis (Aguilera & Jackson, 2010; Westphal & Zajac, 2013). These three methods will discuss in detail below the inclusion and exclusion of different stakeholders, the balance of conflicts of interest between different stakeholders and decision-making influences on social well-being.

2.3.1. Shareholder Protection Model of Corporate Governance

As defined by many scholars, the shareholder protection model emphasises the protection of shareholders' investment as the real business owners (Bebchuk & Weisbach, 2010; Jensen & Meckling, 1976) and ensures a return on investment (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). In contrast, Sundaram and Inkpen (2004) stated that the remaining stakeholders are protected by regulations and contracts, the ownership of the company is treated to be the dwelling claimants. Besley and Ghatak (2007) proposed that corporate behaviour emphasises rent-seeking in an economic condition where a resilient government defines and enforces regulations that constrain corporate behaviour while serving public interest that contributes to sustainable development. The shareholder protection model holds that sustainable development contribution is not a corporate responsibility, instead businesses should focus only on profit-making, and contribution toward sustainable development will depend on their profit level.

This view also suggests that environmental and social issues are not significant and depend on financial performance only (Crane et al., 2014). As stated previously, the shareholder protection approach was based on assumptions that companies should only concentrate on generating profit as institutions can effectively regulate corporate behaviours to ensure the collective interests of all other stakeholders (Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004). However, in practice, although corporations comply with and operate within a regulatory framework, their legitimacy is not guaranteed. Many studies have shown that such condition is due to corporations' frequent catastrophic operations (Benabou & Tirole, 2010; Scherer & Palazzo, 2007; Stone, 1975) or weak institutions (Kolk & Lenfant, 2015; Scherer & Palazzo, 2011). In both situations, institutions are unwilling or cannot outline and enforce governing rules of corporations' profit-generating strategies for the public good and sustainable development. Accordingly, Scherer et al. (2013) asserted that businesses must either adjust their activities to the expectations of state critics or cooperate with the immoral activities of self-centric individuals to demonstrate their legitimacy.

The effectiveness of the shareholder protection governance approach is questionable when considering sustainable development. As stated by Ramo (2002), if the effectiveness of the approach does not impose harm or damage, then it implies contributing to public well-being. This perception of effectiveness addresses two issues of the shareholder protection approach. First, the influence of a national regulatory framework on global business platforms restricts corporations' motivations for international operations to pursue growth that supports sustainability. Additionally, the impediments to the condition of sanctions against companies whose operations destruct society are also restricted. Second, corporate decisions focus significantly on owners' interests, suggesting

that other stakeholders' interests are excluded from business decision-making processes. Consequently, corporate growth will predominantly meet investors' capital interests over the public interests, though this phenomenon depends on financial performance (Porter & Kramer, 2011; Siegel, 2009).

2.3.2. Stakeholder Model of Corporate Governance

The stakeholder model denies the narrow perception of the shareholder model (Blair, 1995; Driver & Thompson, 2002; Lazonik & O'Sullivan, 2000; Letza et al., 2004). The stakeholder model recognises the interests of different stakeholders who are influenced by or can influence the development of company practices (Freeman, 1984). Rather than exclusively focusing on generating profits, the stakeholder model of corporate governance facilitates the management to balance the interests and concerns of various external and internal stakeholders. Thus, the stakeholder model defines a choice of action that serves the interests of different stakeholders (Blair & Stout, 2001; Cadbury, 2003). This model significantly contributes to the development of an alternative approach to shareholder protection.

The stakeholder model significantly strongly impacts sustainable development because stakeholders whose interests include social well-being are incorporated in business decision-making processes. However, their participation often depends on stakeholder powers. Regarding legitimacy, Phillips (2003) declared that the stakeholder model considers legitimacy the central determining factor of businesses' strategic decisions. However, decisions must be grounded on the normative layout that various stakeholders should be involved (Donaldson & Preston, 1995) or contemplated from an instrumental or strategic outlook. In strategic outlook, corporations consider various stakeholders' expectations based on their legitimacy, influence and priority of their needs (Mitchell et al., 1997). However, this approach tends to prioritise the needs of the most influential stakeholders and ignore those of less influential stakeholders (Agle et al., 1999).

Countries possess distinctive regulations and legal mechanisms for product safety, employee rights, environmental issues and taxation (Micheals, 2009; Young, 2012). Numerous scholars revealed that firms tend to operate in unstable countries where the rule of law and legal institutions are weak (Kolk & Lenfant, 2015; Scherer & Palazzo, 2011). Furthermore, the considerable heterogeneity of social values, lifestyles and norms in distinctive cultures indicates that corporations are motivated by the good expectations of diverse stakeholders (Scherer, 2015). In contrast, Bres et al. (2018) asserted that the stakeholder model has yet to offer systems that will enable businesses' broad cooperation in moral and institutional concerns to safeguard the legitimacy of sustainable development.

Regarding effectiveness, the strategic stakeholder model contrarily suggests that corporations consider sustainability objectives only when such goals are proposed by highly influential stakeholders. Spar and La Mure (2003) added that in such a circumstance, research and development (R&D) strategies contribute to sustainable development. This contribution is realised either when various stakeholders openly enforce businesses to support social welfare or when the most influential stakeholders uphold sustainable development objectives. Hence, the effectiveness of the stakeholder model on sustainable development depends on whether stakeholders possess compatible objectives and sufficient power to impact business decisions. Contrarily, many studies have asserted

that normative stakeholder theory must comprehensively outline how to manage complex challenges that hinder Stakeholders' insights and sustainable development objectives (Ferraro et al., 2015; George et al., 2016).

The strategic and normative stakeholder models hold that the effectiveness of and support for sustainable development objectives depends on stakeholders' competence and knowledge, eagerness to invest their possessions and the ease of transforming all these confrontations into social welfare and sustainable development through corporate governance structures.

2.3.3. Corporate Social Responsibility Model of Corporate Governance

The CSR model considers businesses as social actors that promote public well-being in states where it is unwillingly or cannot be managed (Matten & Crane, 2005; Scherer & Palazzo, 2011; Scherer et al., 2016). Research disciplines investigating the CSR model argue about firms' public governance contribution. These studies primarily emphasise macro-level national governance. In contrast, many studies focus on in-house structures and practices that corporations apply to close differences in national governance (Baumann-Pauly & Scherer, 2013; Scherer et al., 2016). The study addressing these issues emphasised two issues: the challenges of legitimacy that imply firm intervention in social issues (Parker, 2002) and the contribution of reflection on multi-stakeholder networks and corporate governance liberalisation to institutional underdevelopment in a business environment (Baumann-Pauly & Scherer, 2013).

Studies examining the CSR model argue that businesses cannot solely rely on following the right expectations and normative layout because an international legal framework is disintegrated (Teubner & Korth, 2012), and normative layouts are distinctive (Palazzo & Scherer, 2006). This view suggests that corporations can select from the three corporate governance approaches (Scherer et al., 2013). Firstly, corporations can adopt a controlling strategy that facilitates the construction of the legitimacy approach to meet the expectations of the most influential stakeholders. Secondly, corporations can develop an adjustment strategy that requires corporations to selectively adjust their general strategy to the expectations of important stakeholders. Third, corporations can employ an ethical debate strategy that demands corporations to actively participate in debates on the social approval of their general corporate behaviours and strategies to uphold or restore their legitimacy. These three strategies can be employed proactively or reactively (Oliver, 1991).

Regarding effectiveness, the CSR model denies shareholder protection theory and emphasises fiscal performance (Scherer & Palazzo, 2007). This model offers a balanced strategy that integrates environmental, social and economic concerns in various decision-making measures, such as justice, efficiency and stability (Marti & Scherer, 2016). Effectiveness implies that corporations should cause social welfare destruction and should openly support the public good. Hence, corporate growth should not be primarily affected by capital drivers to manage social issues and serve society. In contrast to the stakeholder model, the CSR approach enables a system built on consideration and recommends practices that assist in prioritising objectives.

Each of the corporate governance models has unique characteristics. The shareholder protection model focuses on generating profit for its shareholders, contrary, the stakeholder model emphasises the interests of different

stakeholders who are influenced by or can influence corporate decision-making processes, whereas the CSR model considers businesses as social participants that contribute to social well-being. The choice of an appropriate model depends on the context of the study. Accordingly, this study emphasises the wide perception of corporate governance. Employment of all three models is preferred because of the complexity of corporate governance practices underpinned by underdeveloped institutional infrastructure. Therefore, this study would focus on balancing the three models as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development.

2.4. Corporate Governance Dealings in Mongolia as a Developing Country

Mongolia has been increasing socio-economic issues since its economic reform in the 1990s. A review of the research reports and publications on corporate governance in Mongolia revealed three major concerns on corporate governance: corporate governance constitution, institutional impact on corporate governance and corporate governance accountability and disclosure. These themes are based on dominant issues addressed in studies rather than theoretical frameworks. Numerous studies focused on examining the constitution of Mongolia's corporate governance (ADB, 2018; Asia Foundation, 2017; BTI Transformation Index, 2018; CFA Institute Research Foundation, 2021; Global Integrity, 2011; IMF, 2019; International Trade Administration, 2017; Nixon & Walters, 2006; Nixon et al., 2000; OECD, 2013; USAID, 2005; World Bank, 2016). They investigated the constitution based on historical events of the breakdown of the Former Soviet Union (FSU) and the needs and influence of judicial and regulatory institutions. They revealed that the influence of judicial and regulatory institutions has been failing to shape effective corporate governance practice. Moreover, such internal constitution of corporate governance practices continues to hinder the establishment of good corporate governance practices and appropriate corporate norms.

2.4.1. Corporate Governance Constitution

Corporate governance constitution can be formed via country-level, market, institutional and firm-level transitions. These transitions aim to create capitalist, liberal, pluralist and market economies by abandoning state-owned productive assets to the private sector and improving transparency, accountability, authority management, market performance and market efficiency.

In contrast, in the modern corporate world, the United Kingdom, the United States, Germany and Japan possess some of the most effective corporate governance practices in the world. These practices can be categorised into two dominant mechanisms (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997): the market control mechanism (in the United Kingdom and the United States) and the large shareholder control mechanism (in Japan, Germany, France and Spain). These mechanisms are well-known as the Anglo-Saxon mechanism and Continental European mechanism, respectively. Neither mechanism has represented the most effective corporate governance mechanism. However, empirical studies suggested that the Continental European mechanism is less effective on corporate governance codes for achieving the goal of maximising business value, whereas the Anglo-Saxon mechanism is much more flexible. Therefore, the Anglo-Saxon mechanism is desirable.

When investigating the development of corporate governance in developed economies, particularly the market-controlling Anglo-Saxon countries, the fundamental concept of corporation must be traced back to the distant past. For example, the notion of a corporation was introduced in the United Kingdom in the 1600s when the British Monarchy started allocating monopolies to numerous investors who are eager to participate in particular ventures. Such monopolies began to establish joint-stock firms, which supported the combination of capital and labour to charges that would be excessively large for an individual. The East India Company is a classic example where a group of investors merge capital into a particular joint-stock corporation from which earnings would be shared based on their investment amount. Only the associates of the East India Company were permitted to conduct deals with India. Eventually, the company established a government at the centre of India and preserved a standing aggregation. Thus, companies can be governed to perform missions that are burdensome for an individual, including the government (Charles River Editors, 2016).

In contrast, the United States was established by corporations that began to evolve through the colonial era and the Industrial Revolution (Maier, 1993). Despite the Great Depression and World War II, the country managed to drive economic growth, promote cultural strength, expand opportunities, escalate living standards and develop new U.S. cultures assured of prosperity and position in the world. At the time, the majority believed that the United States would face an acute depression after World War II. In 1943, a future Nobel Prize winner Paul Samuelson stated that termination of demobilisation and hostilities will result in over ten million guys will be released in the labour market that would cause the economy to face the greatest period of industrial dislocation and unemployment (Bohanon, 2012). However, after the war, the command economy was demolished, government-controlled price and rationing systems were removed, and tax rates were reduced. Thus, the economy was subjected to greater market control than government intervention. The eradication of wartime command controls led to one of the biggest periods of lucrative growth in U.S. history.

The discussion above reveals the constitution of corporate governance in developing economies compared with that in developed economies, particularly market-controlling Anglo-Saxon countries. Developing countries' economic reform efforts were not uniformly held by the public but by the market transition in a non-transparent and unaccountable manner. Another major difference was government intervention. Economic reforms in developing countries have increased government interventions as privatisation has shifted state-owned productive assets to a few agile and corrupted unknown individuals. whereas economic reforms in developed economies were equally reinforced by the public underpinned by transparent and accountable practices. Contrarily, their governments were progressively reducing their interventions in corporate activities by decreasing expenditures, eradicating numerous government schemes, reducing tax rates and supporting private investors. Therefore, the constitution of corporate governance in developing economies is opposite to that in developed economies.

In Mongolia, the constitution of corporate governance has been formed since the 1990s when the country was required to undergo economic reforms to abolish the old institution and establish new institutions immediately. These economic reforms were implemented together with the maintenance and structural modification of policies, deregulations and liberalisation resulted from the closure of the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance and

breakdown of the Former Soviet Union (Nixson & Walters, 2006). Numerous scholars emphasised that the corporate governance transition was anticipated to reduce government interventions in corporate activities via policies, rules and regulations designed to liberalise, privatise and deregulate state-owned productive assets (Oyejide & Soyibo, 2001; Reed, 2004; Ahunwan, 2002). The reduction in government interventions aimed to progressively eliminate government involvements in business activities while welcoming market demands and shaping market mechanisms that determine economic transactions. Similarly, the Mongolian government sold its state-owned productive assets to the private sector.

However, Nixson et al. (2000) revealed that the Mongolian economic reform process did not favour the public; The reforms were in the interest of coalition power constituted at the time, which was close to asymmetric information (Birdsall & Nellis, 2003). According to Akerlof (1970), the term asymmetric information arises from the inadequate distribution of information between supply and demand; asymmetric information is motivated by uncertainties and dishonest behavioural motives, triggering moral jeopardy, principal–agent conflict and various adverse problems. A review of the privatisation conducted during the transition from a communist economic system to a capitalist market economy shows that the privatisation was conducted in a non-transparent and unaccountable manner and distributed the majority of the assets to few agile and corrupt individuals. Moreover, the behavioural motives driven by asymmetric information has become the normative layout in society. For example, during the parliamentary election in 2004, nearly 70% of total members of parliament (MPs) account for business interest (McMenamin, 2004). This example also demonstrates that the corporate governance reform failed to phase out government interventions in corporate activities. Privatisation, deregulation and liberalisation have increased government intervention in corporate activities, providing opportunities for those who are close to asymmetric information to utilise it for their self-interests while exercising non-transparent and unaccountable practices.

Table 2: *Formation of Corporations in Anglo-Saxon Countries versus Developing Countries*

Measures	Developed Countries	Developing Countries
Corporates formed as	Joint-stock and corporation	Formulate only as a replicate term from Anglo-Saxon countries
When the concept formed	1600–1800	1990s
Manner of conduct	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniformly held by the public • Transparent and accountable • Progressive reduction in government intervention by eradicating several government schemes, such as state-controlled price and rationing systems, and decreasing tax rates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the interest of constituted coalition power • Non-transparent and unaccountable • Increased government intervention driven by corrupt individuals
Corporate governance’s areas of concern	Corporate-level principal–agent relationship	National, institutional and company levels

2.4.2. Institutional Impacts on Corporate Governance

Whether an organisational or a national mechanism is more imperative in determining the effectiveness of corporate governance is a fiercely queried discussion in corporate governance studies. The literature continues to emphasise that both dynamics significantly shape the adoption of effective corporate governance practices (La Porta et al., 2000). Organisational governance mechanisms can be defined as those systems that operate within the organisation, such as stock exchange policies, shareholders, the BOD, bankers, employees, competitors and customers (Siegel, 2005; Agarwal et al., 2009). In contrast, national governance mechanisms deal with a country's regulations, laws, institutions, norms and culture (Adegbite, 2015). However, the study found that the impacts of both governance mechanisms were contingent upon the countries. For developed economies, organisational governance mechanisms tended to be more effective on corporate governance than national governance mechanisms. On the contrary, developing economies showed opposite results, where national governance mechanisms were likely to be more effective than organisational governance mechanisms.

Doidge et al. (2007) findings revealed that internal and external factors substantially impact corporate governance practices. Regarding the internal factors, the distinctive institutional arrangements are such that systemic deficits continue to prevent important enhancements in corporate governance practices. Internal deficits refer to the vast infrastructural insufficiencies that continuously increase businesses' operating costs as new entrants need to set up their facilities to conduct their businesses. Unstable all-encompassing socio-political and economic environments increase bills of goods and services due to impaired economic policies. The failure of governments to restraint corrupt activities in private and public institutions is addressed by compensating complicated end-to-end services than essentially combating and resolving them. Nevertheless, Adegbite (2015) directly responded to the argument that corruption is a worldwide curse that has serious outcomes not only on emerging economies but also on global unions. Although the issue of corruption continues to be relevant, other concerns are uniformly imperative, such as the defenceless regulatory environment that suggests slight or no safety for investors. Unwelcoming regulatory frameworks not only prevent investors from investing in the market but also hold that investors who neglect the defenceless regulatory framework invest in the market with threats. Accordingly, investments and investors are not assured.

Weber (2013) stated that compared with other nations, Western Europe has a rational regulatory framework that determines effective governance practice and capitalism development. This view considers regulatory practices as a benefaction that governs state development; if not, it is a matter to change (Deakin et al., 2017). North (North, 1990) demonstrated a similar perspective in his argument. He claimed that developed countries are those which have formed strong institutions that create an environment that protects property rights and administration of contracts; in contrast, such institutions in developing countries are vulnerable. As a developing country, Mongolia is one of the examples of such institutions. For instance, after the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1990, the country was required to undertake privatisation as a strategic approach to shifting immediately from a communist economy to a market economy (World Bank, 2016). However, the shift resulted in the transfer of state-owned productive assets to a few agile corrupt individuals. Oyejide and Soyibo (2001) asserted that privatisation causes several issues,

one of which is the absence of a regulatory framework for executing privatisation in developing countries. United States Agency for International Development (USAID, 2005) stated that although the main law revision occurred in 2002, extensive legal gaps remain in the regulatory framework. The survey data collected by the International Republican Institute in May 2017 indicated that over 60% of the participants reported that the country is turning to a wrong route. This result was due to the increase in bureaucracy and corruption (previously under 15%) by 6% from February 2017 to May 2017, failed state policies under 25% and income-inequality over 35%. Overall, more than 80% of the participants rated economic situations as very bad or bad (International Republican Institute, 2017). Thus, Mongolia is a prototypical example that demonstrates a significance of internal institutional arrangements to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development.

Regarding the external factors, demands from multinational organisations, such as the IMF, the OECD and the World Bank, and globalisation significantly impact corporate governance practices in emerging economies, such as Mongolia. These international financial agencies imposed broad structural modifications that have drastically transformed corporate governance practices in emerging economies as conditions for renewing loans in the late 1980s. These actions aimed to shift developing countries to adopt an Anglo-Saxon corporate governance mechanism focusing on certain measures, such as fiscal strictness.

This measure pressures states in developing countries to phase out radically their interference with industrial dogmas and the drastic setback of their intervention in the development of production. As a result, the privatisation and trade of state-owned productive assets were enhanced. Moreover, multinational financial organisations emphasised the importance of equity funding and encouraged emerging economies to deregulate exchange rates and interest rates and liberalise capital markets. Furthermore, these multinational organisations engaged in cross-border monitoring and supervision strategies for detecting compliance to the rules of best practices in financial reporting, accounting and corporate governance. The purpose is to encourage compliance, enforcement, standardisation and integration of domestic market economies.

Whether internal or external aspects are more effective on corporate governance in Mongolia is difficult to determine due to the complexity of their dealings. Both factors significantly impact to a great magnitude, continue to employ the factors in corporate governance, and Internal factors continue to constrain, repress and influence the adoption of effective corporate governance practices. In contrast, external factors may bring development by introducing the standard of codes of good corporate governance practices. However, the majority of the codes are not derived from corporate governance narration in Mongolia. Nevertheless, they can be viewed as Western resolutions and, therefore, may not appropriately solve the problems of corporate governance practices in Mongolia.

2.4.3. Significance of Accountability and Disclosure in Corporate Governance

The call for reinforcing accountability and disclosure in corporate governance is a rising trend in emerging economies (Ntim et al., 2013; Agyei-Mensah B. K., 2017). Brennan and Solomon (2008) claimed that an improved accountability and disclosure philosophy are essential to a market-based analysis of corporate behaviour. Such a philosophy is also the primary requirement facilitating shareholders to apply their rights properly. Accountability

and disclosure can be employed as an effective approach to influencing organisational behaviours and assuring prospective investors and shareholders (Guttentag, 2004; Dembo & Rasaratnam, 2014). Maingot and Zeghal (2008) explained that the objective of corporate governance accountability and disclosure is to disseminate and communicate information regarding the company's performance and governance to external investors. However, the information is used not only by shareholders and investors, to evaluate asset performance, but also by other stakeholders, who are concerned about environmental and social policies. Consequently, accountability and disclosure are key to maintaining and boosting the dynamic relationship between various participants with distinctive backgrounds (Husted & Folger, 2004).

By contrast, several scholars also claimed that accountability and transparency are crucial to access government information (Cuillier & Piotrowski, 2009; Bertot et al., 2010) in addition to various actions to fight against corruption. They have been emphasised as the key strategies towards anti-corruption. According to Iyoha and Oyerinde (2010), accountability suggests that delegated public funds must account for how resources have been distributed, consumed and created value. Hopper et al. (2009) argued that the public must have access to relevant information for performance evaluation; thus, transparency and accountability are linked. Furthermore, scholars have emphasised that accountability and transparency primarily form social recruitment that prevents corrupt comportment (Smulovitz & Peruzzotti, 2000). Principal-agent theory implies that corruption can happen when public officials and civil servants lack accountability and prudence over public services (Alt & Lassen, 2006). Civil servants should be accountable to public officials, and public officials should be accountable to citizens. Thus, the accountability principle plays a significant role in solving asymmetric information between citizens (principal) and public officials (agent) and potentially reinforces challenges that citizens can levy on public officials (Shleifer & Vishny, 1993). Hopper et al. (2009) asserted that the auditing approach plays a significant role in the practice of transparency and accountability by revealing evidence of corrupt activities, permitting public assessment and developing the right culture of liberty. Eabrasu (2012) stated that the auditing approach has two advantages: Firstly, morally unacceptable behaviours are scrutinised constantly and criticised publicly. Secondly, pressures are applied to these morally unacceptable activities to motivate responsible institutional behaviours.

Another significant role of accountability and disclosure in effective corporate governance practice is safeguarding fairness and justice. Khoury (2015) asserted this role addresses inequality and poverty by ensuring unbiased access to opportunities and rights and fair distribution of economic and social resources. Other researchers expressed a similar view that information must be equally accessible to various groups of stakeholders, such as shareholders and managers (Giannetti & Simonov, 2006; Williams & Ryan, 2007). The reason is that asymmetric information allows prosperous investors to take advantage of the price of others, drastically destabilising the integrity of institutional environments (Easterbrook & Fischel, 1996; Kelly & Ljungqvist, 2012). Moreover, Bosse et al. (2009) disputed that the notion of fairness involves the reflection of procedural justice (i.e. the justice and processes governing the allocation of resources), distributive justice (i.e. the distribution of material assets) and interactional justice (i.e. respectful, equal treatment throughout the interaction and exchange of information). It can be argued that stakeholders have different perceptions and interests of fairness. However, balancing actions and satisfying

the main stakeholders appropriately is still necessary to support access to resources required for civil society and thus maintain economic activities and growth (Frooman, 1999). Crouch (2014) added that the principle of fairness is not only about public well-being that can be evaluated by political actions but also about the interest, values and preconceptions that can be expressed and recognised through time and institutional development.

Broad transparency and accountability practices are exercised in developed countries through mandatory corporate social and environmental reporting. Voluntary CSR reporting is widely used at least within international corporations, whereas it is required by government conventions, particularly in Europe. Although measuring environmental and social impacts is not specified, providing necessary reports not only ensures transparency and accountability practices but also determines the extent to which businesses contribute to sustainable development. Numerous studies in developing countries revealed that accountability and transparency is poorly practiced in corporate governance (Akhtaruddin, 2005; Barako, 2007; Samaha & Dahawy, 2011; Agyei-Mensah, 2015). The subsequent sections will further discuss this finding relative to the corruption perceptions index (CPI).

Thus, the insufficient practice of transparency and accountability has resulted in reduced income distribution, increased poverty, the unethical behaviour of new owners of privatised firms, the connection of public officials with business interests, the crowd in resource-based markets and weakened institutional environments characterised by an increase in corrupt activities over the years.

Table 3: Practice of Transparency and Accountability in Developed versus Developing Countries

Dealings	Developed Countries	Developing Countries
	Similarities	
Role of transparency and accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key to maintaining and boosting the dynamic relationship between various social participants • Form social recruitment that prevents corrupt compoment • Solve asymmetric information between citizens and public officials • Safeguard fairness and justice • Allow equal access to information to various groups of stakeholders, such as shareholders and managers 	
	Differences	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence organisational behaviour • Assure prospective investors and shareholders • Mandate corporate social and environmental reporting. • Show the extent to which corporations contribute to sustainable development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demand widespread practice of transparency and accountability to conduct market-based analysis of corporate behaviour and facilitate shareholders' proper application of their rights • Used by other stakeholders concerned about environmental and social policies • Government information access • Anti-corruption approach • Addresses inequality and poverty to ensure unbiased access to opportunities and rights and a fair distribution of economic and social resources • Challenge reduction in income distribution, poverty and inequality, unethical behaviour of new private owners, connection of public officials with business interests, crowd in resource-based markets and institutional environment

2.5. Corruption Induced by Corporate Governance Constitution

According to Irdam et al. (2015), the privatisation process can be performed in many ways, though all methods generate rents by creating large sums of profit from the sale of public assets requested by individual players. Cross-country scholars highlight that government intervention is extensively connected to corruption as the central government controls economic resources (Faccio et al., 2006; Dong-Hua et al., 2007; Parsley, 2009). Several studies added that corruption prospects are evident throughout the privatisation process, from the commencement to the sale and tender of state-owned assets; these corruption prospects tend to be bigger when governors of the old system administer the privatisation arrangement (Rose-Ackerman, 2002; Sandholtz & Taagepera, 2005; Martimort & Straub, 2009). In the case of Mongolia, governors of the old system manage the privatisation arrangements. As mentioned previously, the Mongolian market reform prioritised the interest of the power of coalition constituted at the time rather than the interest of the majority of Mongolians. Asymmetric information facilitates rent-seeking opportunities and allows plenty rooms for corruption. Alternatively, Reinsberg et al. (2019) stated that outsiders have limited information access compared with insiders, including public officials and managers who have the opportunity to take advantage of this information for personal gain during the process. In contrast, Rose-Ackerman (2002) argued that buyers offer excess payments to decision-makers to enhance their likelihood of attaining or preserving dominant rents in previous nationalised enterprises. Moreover, Hamm et al. (2012) asserted that business insiders, for example managers, with entrusted interests execute conscious attempts to falsify reports and undervaluing enterprises to acquire them at reduced prices.

Martimort and Straub (2009) claimed that when these individuals have acquired assets during the privatisation process, they search for ways to protect their newly owned assets. They perform this action without any punishment from the state because, as rent-takers, they potentially bribe bureaucrats in exchange for complimentary treatment. Reinsberg et al. (2019) reasoned that short-term privatisation can lessen corruption control as individuals with personal interests will likely lessen the possibility of detecting corruption and preventing punishment, particularly in developing countries with fragile institutions. In contrast, this immediate effect is minor in developed countries with resilient institutions. Corrupt individuals fail institutions through inadequate information which leads to fragile institutions and major corruption. Thus, corrupt individuals can become empowered in fragile institutional environments because weak institutions fail to incorporate the outcome of their economic decisions in the institutional setting (Hoff & Stiglitz, 2005). Many scholars have proven that many countries experienced corruption through privatisation, such as Soviet Union nations (Kaufmann & Siegelbaum, 1997; Stone, 2002; Hoff & Stiglitz, 2005), Uganda, Kenya, Vietnam, Mexico, Venezuela, Brazil and Argentina. Privatisation has varying consequences depending on its conduct, though all forms of privatisation induce corruption. Therefore, corruption caused by privatisation may be prevalent or have certain limits.

The 2020 CPI produced by Transparency International (2021) has been used to compare the extent of corruption between developing and developed countries. The CPI is used to evaluate 180 nations and regions using their corruption levels in the public sector as recognised by entrepreneurs and experts. The scale ranges between 0–100, where 0 indicates vastly corrupt, whereas 100 indicates highly transparent. The data demonstrate that New Zealand

and Denmark ranked first and second, both scoring 88, whereas the United Kingdom shared the rank 11th with Canada, Australia and Hong Kong, with score of 77. The United States of ranked 25th with a score of 67. Mongolia ranked 111th, scoring at of 35. Transparency International (2021) stated that compared with the previous years, over 120 nations score below 50, with a common score of not more than 43 on the 2020 CPI. The collected data present that most nations remain unsuccessful in combating corruption progressively despite certain improvements.

Ufere et al. (2010) argued that corruption is also caused by the institutional and economic conditions of a state and mirrors the nation’s political, cultural, economic and legal institutions. Figure 1 below presents the outcomes of corruption on the government, society, legal system and economy.

Figure 1: Corruption

Source: Vargas and Sommer (2014)

The above figure demonstrates that corruption negatively influences four main pillars of effective corporate governance practice and sustainable development. For instance, the figure shows that corruption can potentially encounter social conflicts due to corrupt elites. They weaken the legal system by undermining legal certainty, drastically deteriorate desired economic outcomes by creating an environment that lacks oversight and exhibits risk of balance sheet manipulation and diminish government legitimacy by constraining transparency. These factors lead to mismanagement and risk of data manipulation.

Furthermore, Vargas and Sommer (2014) formulated four hypotheses below based on the effects of corruption on government, society, the legal mechanism and the economy as presented in Figure 1 above.

1. Corruption signals tax fraud and the shadow economy.
2. Corruption warns socio-economic instability, deficient social interconnection and a lack of capability for state reform.
3. Corruption marks economic maladministration.

4. Corruption warns statistical control.

Subsequently, they examined whether the hypotheses above are applicable in practice. The empirical evidence has proven hypotheses 1, 2 and 4. In contrast, the study revealed that corruption has a detectable impact only on inflation. Their argument on their proposed hypotheses will be discussed below relative to the case of Mongolia since the country’s corruption concerns emerge.

The current corruption level in Mongolia prevails, particularly in areas of rules and regulatory environment, financial environment and the public and private sectors. According to the 2019 CPI disclosed by Transparency International (2020), the Mongolian corruption level scored 35 out of 100, ranking 106th out of 180 countries as illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: *Mongolia’s Corruption Index in the Past 25 Years*

Actual	Previous	Highest	Lowest	Dates	Unit	Frequency
35.00	37.00	43.00	27.00	1999 - 2019	Points	Yearly

Source: *(Transparency International, 2020)*

Compared with the previous year of 2018, Mongolia’s CPI in 2019 is lower by only 2 points. However, this range of scores has been fairly steady since 2012. The spread of corruption in Mongolia will be discussed in relation to the above four hypotheses in Figure 1.

2.5.1. Corruption as a signal of tax fraud and the shadow economy

A state’s creditworthiness or wealth depends on its ability to produce tax revenues. However, if the collection of public payments and taxes is undermined by tax avoidance and illegal work, the capacity for economic activities is significantly limited. Thus, the magnitude of such a shadow economy plays a crucial role in the evaluation of creditworthiness. Vargas and Sommer (2014) have primarily assumed that corruption is the underlying factor for the expansion of the shadow economy; thus, corruption indicators can be employed as a substitute measure. From their point of view, this hypothesis is built on two motives. Firstly, the fine for breaching authoritative payment

duties is minor if inspectors, i.e. tax administrators, are willing to take bribes. In Mongolia, the survey reports on knowledge and perception of corruption presents that the participants' families had provided bribes in the last 3 months. Furthermore, 40% of the participants who have taken the survey in the education sector stressed that they had provided services without pay, gifts or cash to teachers and school staff and claimed that they pay bribes to avail simple services (Asia Foundation, 2017).

Secondly, corrupt individuals in the public sector can make businesses transactions demanding and pressuring entrepreneurs toward the shadow economy. From this perspective, the shadow economy is an outcome of corruption. In the case of Mongolia, the following has been revealed:

The **public sector** is one of the deeply corrupted areas in Mongolia. Survey data gathered by the Asian Foundation (2018) present that approximately 49% of businesses asserted that corruption is extensive in the public sector. The specialised inspection agency is emphasised as the most corrupted state agency highlighting over 25%, followed by the customs at 23%, whereas the social welfare immigration agency and authority for consumer protection and fair competition scored approximately 3.5%, 2.0% and 1.0%, respectively.

Regarding the **private sector**, the Asia Foundation survey (2016) publicised that the increasing concerns for entrepreneurs indicating approximately 40% in 2016, which increased by more than 19% in 2012. The concern among business owners has been doubled. Moreover, the survey also shows increasing mis-governance or pressure in the private sector which involves SMEs. The current regulatory system is ineffective in fighting corruption. The same survey was conducted in 2017 (Asia Foundation, 2018) and revealed that over 35% of the participants declared that corruption in the private business sector has increased compared with the last 3 years. Additionally, over 62% of the respondents claimed that the government could not enforce an effective economic policy. The information provided by GAN Integrity (2020) showed that businesses face expansive corruption when acquiring utilities, permits and licences. The 2017 survey of the Asia Foundation on private CPI (2018) disclosed that more than 72% of the participants said that the present transparency policy associated with business environments is ineffective, and more than 71% responded that government efforts towards anti-corruption are insufficient.

2.5.2. Corruption as a warning of socio-economic instability, deficient social interconnection and a lack of capability for state reform

Vargas and Sommer (2014) formulated the hypothesis that corruption warns of socio-economic instability, deficient social interconnection and a lack of capability for state reform. This hypothesis is built on the assumption that when faced with catastrophes, a broad-spectrum society necessarily expects its political and economic elites to conduct reform processes successfully. However, numerous dealings proposed to overcome economic crisis are strongly built on whether the civil society supports transformations. Therefore, the catastrophe faced in Mongolia today is rooted in the economic and institutional reforms in the 1990s. The Mongolian citizens have been experiencing acts of corruption for over three decades in the form of increasing poverty and inequality, inflation and mistreatment from the public sectors. Over the years, the situations have worsened, and residents are becoming frustrated. This observation can be further argued that the residents are uniting to prepare for economic reform, illustrating civil society's support for transformations. However, people have a lack of knowledge and guidance driven by

insufficient foundation of professional and non-government organisations (NGOs) in the field of corporate governance, anti-corruption and sustainable development.

Moreover, the residents' perception is formed by the degree of visible contributions to society of complex changes. Corruption indexes are used as a measure to determine whether the dealings truly aim to lessen the catastrophe or whether the proposed changes are based on the self-centric mentality of the nation's elites who aim for personal gains at the expense of the public. Although the proposed dealings have sociological relevance, they also have tangible economic significance to the nation's budget constraints, the capacity of institutional disposition and the tolerance of economic policy modifications. However, this context has a negative influence as corruption allows personal interests in the collective framework. For example, different businesses can practice bribery to guarantee personal benefits, gain extra market power and avoid fair competition.

2.5.3. Corruption marks economic maladministration

According to Vargas and Sommer (2014), this hypothesis was formulated based on the notion that institutions responsible for fiscal management are impaired by corruption. For example, a central bank could be established as autonomous and achieve a particular inflation pledge though individuals pursue personal interests because of corruption. A similar phenomenon happens to the nation's budget constraint. In the case of Mongolia, the public has confirmed widespread grand corruption (or high-level) corruption in the country. According to the data of the Global Corruption Barometer, 46% of the participants asserted that all or majority of the representatives in legislative are corrupt, whereas 39% of them emphasised that all or majority of the public officials are corrupt (Transparency International, 2017). In contrast, the survey conducted by Asian Foundation (2017) reported that 55% of the participants reported a substantial increase in grand corruption in Mongolia; this reported response shows an increase from 38% in 2014. The citizens addressed that the underlying factors of the pervasive grand corruption combined with business and political interests and the absence of capacity in the regulatory environment to confront these problems and government transparency (Asia Foundation, 2017).

Transparency International (2018) has reported that political parties significantly influence grand corruption. They were ranked fifth as the most corrupt government organisation in 2010 and ranked up to the second place in 2017, whereas the parliament ranked fourth and the government ranked fifth in 2017 (Asia Foundation, 2017). BTI transformation index (2018) asserted that extensive cronyism and corruption in the government and among political parties not only significantly jeopardise trust in state institutions but also threatens the rule of law considering the existing democratic growth. Similarly, Transparency International (2018) revealed that the close connection between politics and business are remain overlooked due to the lack of lobbying rules; such rules allow various arrangements of legal corruption, such as trade circulation with the corresponding influence between public and private entities under an unregulated and non-transparent setting. As a result, corruption spreads to the public and private sectors.

In addition, the judiciary is also one of the severely corrupt sectors and one of the cornerstones to forming good corporate governance mechanisms effectively. BTI transformation index (2018) stated that autonomous judges are appointed by the Judicial General Council. However, the U.S. Department of State (2017) reasoned that more than

34% cut to their salaries during the economic recession due to insufficient resources and guidance, limiting their financial independence, particularly regarding large amounts of capital. Similarly, the World Bank (2015) asserted that the examination of the customs department also involved a high possibility of corruption due to irregular export and import incomes. The failure of the judiciary system indicates the failure of the rule of law to operate. Countries with such a significant degree of corruption are likely to allocate a small budget to health and education sectors, whereas fancy infrastructure developments, though not supporting the civil society, are provided with a larger budget. Such corrupt domestic institutions and an insufficient legal assurance worsen competition between businesses, consequently restraining investments. On the contrary, from the householders' perception, corruption also shrinks equality in opportunities, thus enlarging disparities between household incomes.

2.5.4. Corruption as a warning of statistical control

Extensive fiscal fundamentals are employed when evaluating a state's economic condition. These instruments are commonly used to understand global competitiveness, growth, inflation and borrowings. However, the information generated by these measures is often compiled by domestic institutions and authorities. Therefore, the provided data could be controlled. Control exercised in this manner is essentially critical in situations where the fiscal condition deteriorates.

For example, a review of previous studies on corporate governance accountability and transparency in Mongolia revealed that government transparency is not sufficiently practiced. As reported by USAID (2005), the publication date of the state budget reveals numerous figures though asset disclosure rules are not enforced to public officials. As a result, politics have been described as a structure that defines who takes what within society (Brinkerhoff & Goldsmith, 2004). In 2004, over a decade after its economic reform in the market, the income per capita of Mongolia was only above \$460, ranking the nation with the poorest economies in the world. The economy was featured by substantial concentration on a limited range of products and export of commodities such as gold, cashmere and copper (Nixson & Walters, 2006). Therefore, the data and information compiled by authorities and domestic institutions have a high probability of being controlled as well as implications on economic growth and sustainable development.

On the one hand, the pressure on domestic sources to mitigate the condition is especially common in such circumstances. On the other hand, investors are willing to receive detailed and correct reports regarding the development in this condition. Statistical control is naturally difficult to verify due to the lack of systematic registers of controlled information, which could be associated with the extent of corruption (Vargas & Sommer, 2014). Therefore, corruption threatens the development of competent institutions due to informal network structures impeding the implementation of institutional transformations. Transformation processes significantly depend on civil society's livelihood. In contrast, corruption supports clientele relationships in society and politics, favouring democratic policy development. However, this condition deteriorates the institutional environment. Thus, corruption operates as a measure of a nation's socio-economic and political maturity, and the expansive practice of transparency and accountability monitors the process by allowing scrutiny from various stakeholders.

2.6. Actions to Fight against Corruption and Improve the Regulatory Environment

For nearly three decades, Mongolia and the World Bank has been cooperated to establish effective corporate governance framework and sustainable economic development by reducing corruption and the poverty level (Transparency International, 2018; World Bank, 2021). Accordingly, Mongolia has been actively participating in international initiatives and conventions and has been undertaking institutional arrangements.

In 2006, Mongolia signed the UN Convention for Anti-corruption as of its participation in international initiatives and conventions (Transparency International, 2018). In 2011, the UN (2011) reported that although the country has progressed towards anti-corruption, deficiencies in the enforcement system, judicial bribery and protection of witnesses among others have remained. The Financial Action Task Force (FATF, 2015) claimed that great risks in tax avoidance, corruption, ecological crimes and fraud continue to remain although Mongolia has primarily indicated anti-corruption laws in its anti-corruption regulations and criminal code. The law primarily states that any form of bribery and misconduct of mechanism is prohibited (GAN Integrity, 2020). Transparency International (2018) stated that the Mongolian government only approved the state's anti-corruption strategy at the start of 2017, whereas the Independent Authority Against Corruption (IAAC) is requested to oversee the strategy implementation. Positive progress towards sustainable development was evident through the National Action Plan introduced in 2016 under the Open Government Cooperation (Transparency International, 2018). However, the absence of enforcement mechanisms for the existing regulatory environment resulted in the difficulty to develop action plans to convert engraved commitments into essential actions and implementation of the proposed strategy. According to the U.S. Department of State (2017), Mongolia included in its 2006 anti-corruption law a range of penalties for various corrupt activities but insufficiently enforced in practice. A similar situation has been observed in auditing. The Mongolian auditing regulations consist of company laws and auditing regulations, insurance and national audit regulations and banking laws. Publicly listed companies whose equity is not less than 50 million in MNT (Mongolian Tugrug) and non-bank financial associations, insurance companies, banks, public entities, foreign investment companies are legally required to have an external audit for their financial reports (U.S. Department of State, 2017). However, such a requirement is not practiced adequately in Mongolia's corporate world.

Nevertheless, following institutional arrangements, the Mongolian government established the IAAC in 2007 as a central state institution that combats corruption (OECD, 2013). The IAAC aims to request wealth declarations, investigate corruption incidents and provide courses on corruption awareness. The scope of its operations involves abuse of position and power by public officials, the practice of excessive authority by public officials, exploitation of authority by private entities and NGO officials, all forms of bribery and overseeing the budget expenditure compared with its designed purpose (OECD, 2013). However, the establishment has been suggested to be ineffective in these areas due to its broad range of responsibilities with limited resources (OECD, 2015). Alternatively, the information provided by Transparency International (2018) disclosed that the IAAC head is contracted for six years, and nobody has completed such total years of service thus far. Several reports indicate that the IAAC has targeted politically inclined individuals (BTI Transformation Index, 2018). Correspondingly, the establishment of the IAAC has also been influenced by widespread corruption. BTI transformation index (2018)

provided evidence for this claim showing that the IAAC investigated over 184 incidents in 2005 but only 7% of them were convicted.

Another government institution established for the anti-corruption movement was the Office of the Prosecutor. Article 56 of the Mongolian Constitution states that the Office of the Prosecutor is responsible for executing criminal regulations, investigating criminal incidents, supervising probes, attending court trials to representing the state and giving punishments (Constitution, 2020). Global Integrity (2011) disputed that although the department of investigation in the office can track incidents involving policy enforcement officials in response to resident complaints, the operation of the office regarding the matter is null in the public. The U.S. Department of State (2017) asserted that the prosecutors in Mongolia can influence courts and set charges for the objection against prosecutions that are hardly dismissed. The Office of the Prosecutor is another central institution established to combat the spread of corruption but turned out to be influenced by corruption as well.

In addition to numerous international initiatives and conventions and institutional arrangements to combat corruption and strengthen the regulatory environment, other stakeholders also play a significant role in the formation of effective corporate governance practices, such as the media and civil society. As reported by Transparency International (2018), over 400 media firms operate in the country despite its small population. On the contrary, BTI transformation index (2018) stressed that the majority of media organisations are connected to business cartels and politicians in pursuit of particular programs. However, the Asian Foundation (2018) suggested a recent dramatic growth in the Internet and social media platforms, though TV has remained the main source of information. In addition, as one of the main stakeholders in national governance reform, civil society has a crucial role in fighting against corruption and strengthening the regulatory environment. The Mongolian residents are free to form assemblies and associations specified in law and have the right whether to cooperate with NGOs. BTI transformation index (2018) stated that Mongolia has a vibrant civil society that is established to combat corruption, specifically in urban regions. However, it lacks the power to fight against extensive corruption and change the conventional kin relationships.

Mongolia has considered various efforts to combat corruption and strengthen its regulatory environment. However, the spread of corruption has remained the central issue rather than setting appropriate norms, culture and effective corporate governance practices. The underlying factor for the pervasive corruption is not only the absence of capacity in the regulatory and institutional environments and the civil society but also the absence of transparency and accountability across all institutional structures. In this research, the great practice of transparency and accountability is recognised as the way to establish effective corporate governance practices in Mongolia to combat widespread corruption, strengthen enforcement mechanisms, enforce the rule of law and promote sustainable development.

2.7. Sustainable Development

A governance framework mainly aims to respect shareholders' rights within a regulatory environment and support positive cooperation between businesses and shareholders to create economies of scale, including jobs, wealth and the development of financially stable businesses (Handley-Schachler et al., 2007). In this study, sustainable

development can be described as development which encounters the existing needs without conceding the capacity of forthcoming generations to encounter their self needs (UN, 1987). The prevailing notions of sustainable development imply three assumptions: environmental cooperation and integrity, shared equity and lucrative prosperity (Scherer et al., 2013). How these assumptions can be encountered requires discussion in which the projected solutions range from minor adjustments to major social reforms of the existing economic and institutional conditions (Hopwood et al., 2005). Many scholars added that society is confronted with lofty challenges threatening future sustainable development (Ferraro et al., 2015; George & et al., 2016). Here, the term lofty challenges is defined as major environmental and social challenges exceeding the limits and may negatively impact numerous individuals (Ferraro et al., 2015; George & et al., 2016).

Studies declared that absence of appropriate responses at present to tackle these lofty challenges, including inequality, poverty and corruption, all of which are evolving (Griggs et al., 2013; Whiteman et al., 2013). Waddock (2008) stated that the European Union, the UN, international agencies and individual countries are searching for solutions to tackle these lofty challenges. Analyses presented that these solutions target businesses as operating participants and urge their cooperation with the civil society and public sector participants to promote sustainable development (Rasche et al., 2013; Voegtlin & Pless, 2014). Nevertheless, researchers argued that the aspect of business cooperation remains uncertain (Scherer et al., 2009), despite the frequent appeal for corporate inputs into sustainable development (Marcus & Fremeth, 2009) and approval of significant CSRs (Matten & Crane, 2005; Scherer & Palazzo, 2007).

Scholars argued that companies contribute to sustainable development by supplying sustainable services and products, engaging in sustainable initiatives or CSR activities and creating public goods (Kaul et al., 2003; Matten & Crane, 2005). Laufer (2003) and Sethi and Schepers (2013) claimed that their inputs are often unsubstantial rather than symbolic. A similar view was expressed in different studies that companies are central actors in creating environmental catastrophes and social issues (Banerjee, 2007; Fleming & Jones, 2013; Rhodes, 2016; Schembera & Scherer, 2017).

Advocates warned that this concept indicates that the internal incentive structures and decision-making of businesses are operating ineffectively, affecting their corporate governance structures negatively, particularly on how they govern these structures to tackle lofty social challenges (Greve et al., 2010; Scherer et al., 2013). Therefore, these lofty challenges are complicated and have no applicable solutions. The challenges become an issue of consideration for not only different countries (Grand Challenges Canada, 2011) and international government participants, such as the European Commission (Georghiou & Harper, 2008; Cagnin et al., 2012), the OECD (2011, 2012) and the UN (2015), but also for civil society participants, such as NGOs, and private participants, such as industry associations and private companies (Ferraro et al., 2015; George & et al., 2016; Nilsson, 2017).

An investigation of sustainable development in Mongolia has revealed that SMEs form a significant part of Mongolian economy, accounting for 98% of all enterprises, of which 75% are microenterprises (Asian Development Bank, 2018). However, they face numerous challenges to unlock their full potentials. As reported by the Asian Development Bank (2018), the most common constraint is limited access to funds; only 10% of all 37,000

enterprises have regular financial access within banks. Therefore, improving and increasing financial access for SMEs is a foremost necessity. This improvement can be done by creating co-financing options with local microfinance institutions and banks, expanding alternative financing instruments unavailable from domestic financial institutions and providing consultancy services for SMEs. Reviewing governance policy, mechanism and structure can improve business associations and strengthen business environments.

The development of SMEs to establish effective corporate governance practices and promote sustainable development remains the centre of policy dispute not only in emerging economies but also in advanced economies. Supporting the development of SMEs have various benefits: (1) entrepreneurship is reinforced; (2) SMEs have a great possibility of using technologies that require labour rigorous to impact directly employability level; (3) SMEs are easily established in addition to immediate operations to accelerate returns; and (4) they can offset power compared with strategically large enterprises. Accordingly, the development of SMEs can accelerate the realisation of significant socio-economic objectives involving poverty mitigation. However, the capability of SMEs to develop highly depends on their ability to invest in qualifications, innovations and restructuring. All these investments require access to capital, threatening national economic growth.

Consequently, a weak governance framework, underdeveloped institutional infrastructure and pervasive corruption in the Mongolian sustainable development not only threaten the development of SMEs but also inhibit entrepreneurship, reduce unemployment, weaken economic growth and allow power concentration on few strategically large enterprises. Here, sustainable development towards broad social collective interests can be ensured by launching broad management for accountability and transparency practices. This management must monitor, scrutinise and reward the state and corporations' influence on society in addition to their environmental and economic performance while ensuring cooperation, controlling power and inclusiveness.

2.7.1. Cooperation

In this study, the term cooperation can be described as a transparent, accountable and interactive practice by which different social participants become jointly responsive to one another together with scrutiny on the ethical acceptability, public desirability and sustainable development (Von Schomberg, 2011). Accordingly, cooperation involves different forms of responsibility (Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017): (1) the responsibility of doing no detriment (Deschamps, 2012; Lee & Petts, 2013), (2) the responsibility of doing good (Stahl et al., 2014) and (3) responsible governance (Jordan, 2008; Scherer et al., 2009). These responsibilities signify the need for developing institutions, procedures and structures at various levels to enable innovations that aid (1) and (2).

Governance engages with various responsibilities and is important to achieve cooperation (Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017). The understanding of cooperation in this study is broader because it considers all forms of civil society participants, including public and private entities, and potential forms of cooperation among them. These two considerations are due to two reasons: (1) studying corporate governance in Mongolia in a wide perception is more effective than focusing on certain a segment because Mongolia is one of the developing countries and (2) Mongolia exhibits high-level corruption. Moreover, cooperation is discrete because it is subject to a premeditated control process. Particularly, cooperative governance demands governance structures across different levels (corporate,

societal and international) that enable an inclusive process of mutual will for the realisation of the objectives, mechanisms and social tolerability of innovations (Stilgoe et al., 2013; Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017).

In contrast, Marti and Scherer (2016) expanded that these governance structures also help society to analyse how the settlements between opposing collective objectives (e.g. potential settlements between stability, justice and public well-being and efficiency) should be governed and define the extent of harm tolerated when modifying financial markets. Accordingly, corporate governance should enable a mechanism that facilitates organisations' cooperation while addressing social fears and needs. Thus, its capacity for doing good is enhanced, whereas its capacity to cause detriment is limited, thereby impacting sustainable development. Consequently, reforming institutions and governance across all structures to sustainable development objectives and solve existing lofty challenges is significant to cooperation (Cagnin et al., 2012; Nilsson, 2017; UN, 2015). Reforming institutions and governance structures through cooperative initiatives aims to achieve cooperation that not only serves business objectives and enable corporate fiscal growth but also tackles lofty challenges, serve the collective interest of the civil society and promote sustainability (Nilsson, 2017).

However, how private businesses should be governed, how disagreements should be determined and what interests should be considered raise disputes. Certain scholars claim that private companies should exclusively focus on shareholders' interests (Jensen, 2002; Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004), whereas others argue that private companies should incorporate the concerns of different stakeholders (Aguilera & Jackson, 2003; Cadbury, 2003; Mitchell et al., 2016) and emphasise that private companies focus openly on public welfare (Ulrich, 2008). From the normative standpoint, corporate governance should impact the corporate cooperation process and vice versa. As a result, acceptance from society is achieved (legitimacy); sustainable development objectives are attainable (effectiveness); and appropriate mechanisms (efficiency) are employed due to the rising cooperation, avoidance of detriment and enhanced the good to society.

The capitalist notion of society in developed countries is characterised by the explicit separation of functions (Friedman, 1970; Jensen, 2002; Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004). Legal and political mechanisms establish and enforce legal frameworks that lay limitations on economic participants. This strategy ensures that the outcomes of their earnings-oriented behaviour can assist the public good. By contrast, Friedman (1970) added that corporations focus on their efficiency without taking any political and social responsibilities. This conception of how capitalist economies operate is widely considered, particularly by several economic participants, as a leading example of earnings-oriented corporations. In contrast, when business activities negatively influence the state and social institutions are unwilling or cannot regulate corporations, the responsibility of corporations is believed to disassociate from the public welfare and becomes indefensible (Palazzo & Scherer, 2006; Scherer & Palazzo, 2007). When these institutional catastrophes are perceived as normal rather than an exemption, corporations become uncertain to serve shareholders' interest, generate profits and achieve efficiency (Benabou & Tirole, 2010). In these state catastrophes, businesses, among other social and private participants, have a crucial role in developing and spreading cooperation that supports sustainable development.

2.7.2. Controlling Power

A publicly traded company is a corporation controlled and owned by the general public; nevertheless, these corporations perform as a defining context for corporate governance. The concentration of ownership on an individual or a few large shareholders is termed blockholding and has been a long-standing challenge to corporate governance study (Holderness, 2003).

The direct engagement of concentrated ownership in the company is the norm in most countries, except for the United Kingdom and the United States (La Porta et al., 2000). Many empirical studies have proven that blockholding involves significant transactional costs in various ways. For example, controlling blockholders may enjoy their private benefits, namely controlling private benefits, which are not shared with various shareholders (Dyck & Zingales, 2004). They achieve these controlling private benefits by pursuing self-governing strategies which may harm not only the company performance and minority shareholders but also other stakeholders, such as creditors and employees.

Nevertheless, blockholders support the enhancement of the patron–client relationship. Brinkerhoff and Goldsmith (2004) stated that patron–client relationships involve a complex network of personal connections between bosses or political patrons and their followers or individual clients. These connections are often developed on joint material benefits: patrons supply limited resources to clients and become partners in turn for their cooperation and support. Patrons hold inconsistent power and consequently benefit from careless permissiveness regarding the distribution of assets in their power. Kettering (1988) argued that most patrons in contemporary polities are not autonomous actors, though they have connections to a big network of contacts and often act as a mediator who organises exchanges between an individual and the state. Patrons neglect long-term state interests and focus on assisting their clients. Migdal (1988) claimed that modern patron–client relationships tend to expand in weak political and institutional environments, which is fundamental to the politics of existence for both parties. Brinkerhoff and Goldsmith (2004) stated that weak and marginalised people of the community are naturally trapped in such problem-solving contacts as a pragmatic refers to solve their frequent concerns because they repeatedly face restricted access to essential sources of support. Various variables are defined as representatives for political connections: personal relationships, family bonds, selection of ex-government authority as a director and geographic closeness. Collins and Rodriguez (2008) stated that the personal relationship of executives with the bureaucrat is obvious predictors of involvement in corruption. They also argued that executives with strong personal relationships are willing to support and participate in corrupt arrangements.

In addition, Agrawal and Knoeber (2001) emphasised that politically attached external executives play a significant role in government trade in terms of exports and imports. Consequently, political officials receive political contributions embedded in tax benefits (Gupta & Swenson, 2003). The cross-country scholars highlighted that government intervention is extensively connected to corruption, whereas the central government controls economic resources (Faccio et al., 2006; Dong-Hua et al., 2007; Parsley, 2009). Shleifer and Vishny (1993) claimed that the limitation of central government control permits various authorities from diverse government organisations to execute independent bribes on private companies, considerably raising the total bribe level.

Considering social and cultural relations, it is critical to equalise power across social groups, the intensity of power-dependence relations and the extent to which weak members of society depend on elites for credit, land and diverse resources. These elements construct a social setting wherein clients are likely to flourish. This social setting can significantly provide the main source of economy and support for the public sector, whereas the private sector is comparatively underprivileged. Regarding the contextual variables relevant to nations' characteristics, economic and governance mechanisms, policymaking, transparent resource distribution and enforcement of existing rules and regulations must be encouraged.

2.7.3. Participation

In this study, the term participation refers to public engagement or inclusiveness. According to Meadowcroft and Steurer (2013), public participation ensures that governance mechanisms consider the perspectives and interests of diverse social participants and utilise different knowledge supports when tackling collective issues. Beck (1992) asserted that participation is crucial to social and economic augmentation when actors of society in constitutional processes of the realisation of mutual will challenge the destructive consequences of existing policies or acquire different public dogmas. Furthermore, Reid et al. (2010) claimed that lofty challenges, such as corruption, poverty and inequality, economic slowdown and sustainability issues, require insight and knowledge of professionals who are skilled at defining the issues, underpinning their causes and developing suitable processes to upgrade them. In contrast, Dryzek and Pickering (2017) argued that participants in society or bureaucrats in the political and administrative mechanism may consider their capabilities without considering professional knowledge, downplaying the importance of scientific suggestion and putting great importance on their experience. This phenomenon tends to prevail in developing countries, such as Mongolia.

This study considers that effective corporate governance must continuously acknowledge diverse perspectives and insights and must be capable to challenge the status quo, such as examining dominant values, structures, behaviours and practices concerning their efficiency, effectiveness and legitimacy. Moreover, governance mechanisms should be in a state of ever-evolving reflection. Vob et al. (2006) expressed a similar view that public mutual response demands that verdicts be made and that decisions should yield to action. Regarding various types of participation in governance mechanisms, Irvin and Stansbury (2004) stated that the actual participants depend on the problem that requires solution and the associated restraints to resources and time and organisational and individual capacities to reflect on the associated participants. Another interesting question raised here is how such different types of participants correspond to each other and reach a consensus.

Fung (2006) categorised six dominant methods of engagement, from the lowest to the highest engagement. In the lowest engagement methods, participants are barred from decision-making but are involved in communication: (1) they accept information and stay passive; (2) they have the opportunity to express their inclinations; and (3) they can explore, transform or develop their inclinations. In the following two methods of participant engagement, every participant possesses a greater impact on decision-making. (4) Regarding bargaining and aggregation, the careful preferences of the actors are gathered into a mutual choice which is often driven by the participants' control resources. In (5) negotiation and deliberation methods, a mutual decision is made based on an argumentative

interaction. In other words, the participants make their mutual choices and shared preferences on principles, arguments and reasons to which other participants can correspond. The last method is (6) technical proficiency, whereby professionals whose proficient specialisation and training demand them to solve particular issues and determine participants' choices and public policies.

Furthermore, Fung (2006) highlighted the significance of authority and impact on the influence of participants and how the actors' collective decisions are tied to actions. He stated that participants have diverse levels of authority based on certain considerations. This authority defines the level of the participants' impact on a collective decision and public policy by exercising their uninterrupted power. Participants with minimal authority participate in social problems for self-advantage and with no intentions to impact mutual decisions. In the strong method of participatory decision-making, actors exercise uninterrupted authority by determining the impact of the method of participating in co-governing alliances or offering advice where authorities and participants mutually determine the objectives of policies.

Elkington (1998) stated that monitoring and compensating the company's influence on the civil society together with the environmental, social and economic performance aspects can ensure improvement in cooperation between governance participants, decentralisation of controlling power and enhancement in public participation in decision-making towards wider social preferences. This objective can be achieved by introducing various transparency and accountability approaches, including mandatory corporate social and environmental reporting. In developed economies, particularly in Europe, governmental policies increasingly demand mandatory reporting on all three aspects. Reports on environmental, social and economic performance will assist in measuring or presenting the scope to which the organisation contributes to sustainable development. Thus, mandatory reporting will enhance transparency and accountability practices, thereby acknowledging different participant ideas on future instructions of the company and leading to innovation.

2.8. Chapter Summary

The notion of corporate governance is broad, though its perception can be divided into two main groups: the narrow and wide perception. The narrow perception of corporate governance is defined as a set of mechanisms that affect managers' decisions considering the separation of ownership and control. The United Kingdom and the United States represent this corporate governance perception. However, the rest of developing countries employ this corporate governance perception. The narrow perception of corporate governance fails to address systematic issues at the core of corporate governance, for instance, underdeveloped institutional infrastructure, weak judicial institutions and inadequately outlined property rights. Therefore, the wide perception of corporate governance is necessary to consider the institutional infrastructure, particularly governing institutions, the rule of law and political practice. Thus, corporate governance dealings significantly differ between developed and developing countries.

A comparison between developed and developing countries reveals that the formation of corporations is relatively new in developing countries. Moreover, economic reform efforts in these countries were performed in a non-transparent and unaccountable manner, resulting in increased government interventions rather than otherwise. In

the case of Mongolia, the notion of corporate governance was constituted in the 1990s. During this period, the country was required to undergo economic reform to establish new institutions and abolish the old ones. Privatisation played a strategic significant role by shifting state-owned productive assets to few agile and corrupt individuals who were close to asymmetric information. As a result, the privatisation, liberalisation and deregulation processes increased the government intervention rather than phasing out government intervention in corporate activities. Additionally, power concentration on few individuals has intensified, and pervasive corruption has spread to high levels of the state, the public and private sectors, the judiciary system and media.

This situation has raised a question on whether organisation- or national-level governance is more effective. Studies suggest that organisation-level governance mechanisms are more suitable for developed countries, whereas national-level governance is more effective in developing countries. However, balancing both is ideal, which requires reinforcing great transparency and accountability practices. Transparency and accountability are essential not only to the market-based analysis of corporate behaviour, helping shareholders to apply their rights properly, but also to influencing organisational behaviour and fighting against corruption. These benefits can be achieved by maintaining and boosting the dynamic relationship between various participants.

In contrast, when transparency and accountability practices are threatened to a certain extent, an equivalent level of corruption exists. Thus, a great corruption level possesses the same level of obstacles to transparency and accountability practices. The reason is that asymmetric information creates insiders' rent-seeking opportunities and provides great opportunities for corruption. When corrupt individuals have misallocated resources or acquired assets, they start seeking ways to gain self-protection from any punishment from the state. Thus, corruption negatively impacts a state's government, judicial, economic and societal conditions. These aspects are the four main pillars to the functions of effective corporate governance. Furthermore, empirical evidence has also proven that corruption indicates tax fraud and the shadow economy, deficient social interconnection, lack of capability for state reform, socio-economic instability, economic maladministration and statistical control. These warnings have also been proven in the case of Mongolia. Corruption has spread pervasively throughout the country and has deteriorated the civil society's trust despite Mongolia being a member of the World Bank for nearly three decades, participating in several international initiatives and conventions and making various institutional arrangements. As a result, people's doubt has increased, structural cooperation is developed and economic growth has ceased due to the absence of accountability and insufficient transparency.

These problems have restrained sustainable development by slowing down environmental cooperation and integration, creating collective assets and economic growth. Thus far, no suitable actions are taken in response to the lofty challenges, such as corruption, poverty and inequality. These challenges are not only an issue for developing countries but also an issue of international concern. The emergence of issues on effective corporate governance, corruption and sustainable development has raised the need to reinforce great practices of transparency and accountability. Consequently, these practices can help improve structural cooperation and integration, decentralise controlling power in hands of a few individuals and support the participation of different stakeholders. Accordingly, civil society must be empowered through education, knowledge and guidance on great

transparency and accountability practices. This approach can help to combat the endemic corruption, establish effective corporate governance practices and promote sustainable development.

Thus, the research gap addressed in this study is the absence of transparency and accountability practices. This research gap along with the conceptual framework of this research will be discussed and defined further in the succeeding sections.

2.9. Conceptual Framework

Beside different social participants including private and transactional companies, corporations have a vital role in establishment of effective corporate governance and sustainable development in events of government failures. It has been revealed that broader transparency and accountability practices combine to sustain and enhance dynamic relationship between different social participants. On the other hand, wider transparency and accountability practices will pressure institutions to address resulting problems in association with three premises of corporate governance: structural cooperation, controlling power and participation or inclusiveness of various stakeholders. Accordingly, augmentation of transparency and accountability practices in relation to three central premises of corporate governance is seen as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in developing countries, particularly in the case of Mongolia. Correspondingly, Figure 3 below illustrates the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 3: Conceptual Framework

On the one side, this study investigates potential transparency and accountability approaches to enhance cooperation between various social participants, decentralising the controlling power of blockholders and promoting public participation or inclusiveness to augment overall transparency and accountability practices at the national level. As a result, improved transparency and accountability practices will enhance cooperation between different social participants, confronting the controlling power of a few individuals while encouraging public inclusiveness. These two-way processes are illustrated in Figure 3 with two-way arrows.

On the other side, improved transparency and accountability practices will support establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development through public scrutiny. Contrary, effective corporate governance practice, anti-corruption activities and sustainable development will

strengthen overall transparency and accountability practices. These two-way processes are also demonstrated Figure 3 with two-way arrows.

2.10. Research Gap

Investigation of existing governance and institutional setting in Mongolia has revealed that existence of concentrated controlling power in hands of blockholders alongside pervasive corruption deteriorates cooperation between different social participants, leads to more concentration of controlling power, and enlarges exclusiveness (poverty and inequality), while weakening capacity of judiciary systems and civil society. These political, institutional and socioeconomic complexities in developing countries constrain an application of appropriate governance theories and models. Nevertheless, the literature has emphasised that the underlying problem is an absence of broader transparency and accountability practices.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Purpose of the Chapter

This chapter discusses the philosophical underpinning, research design, deductive and inductive reasoning, research methods, sampling techniques, the mixed-and multimethod approach, data analysis methods, ethical principles of conduct and research validity and reliability. The fitness of data collection methods to this research is also explained.

Every research is unique in its context and employment of methods for interpreting certain phenomena as knowledge. This study aims to establish effective corporate governance practices, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in developing countries: a case of Mongolia. Accordingly, ontological and epistemological underpinning, field research design, inductive reasoning, qualitative field research, qualitative archival study, non-probability purposive sampling, qualitative multimethod approach, qualitative content analysis and qualitative grounded theory analysis have been employed in this study and provided with justifications. Furthermore, ethical principles of conduct, namely autonomy, beneficence, justice and inclusiveness, followed by research validity and reliability, have been discussed relative to the data collection process and findings. According to Opie (2004), justifying the selected methodology can increase the research reliability. Moreover, understanding the philosophical background can strengthen the nature of the study (Ritchie et al., 2003). All this information will be covered in the next section.

3.2. Research Ontological Stance and Rationality

The investigation of the existing governance and institutional setting in Mongolia emphasised power concentration, deteriorated public participation, cooperation constraints underpinned by pervasive corruption in different sectors, the absence of transparency and insufficient accountability. For nearly three decades, Mongolia has been working with the World Bank, which is one of the leading supporters of good governance, to address issues of corruption, poverty and inequality and strengthen transparency and accountability. However, corruption has continued to widely spread across different structures and sectors in the country, including top-level leaders, the public and private sectors, the judiciary system and the media. The legal environment and civil society of Mongolia cannot fight against corruption, thus deteriorating public trust and increasing doubt which affects structural cooperation. Therefore, various transparency and accountability approaches must be explored as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. This study is exploratory in nature. Thus, archival research and observation will be applied to explore alternative ways to improve and strengthen transparency and accountability, which propose a qualitative multimethod approach.

In addition, transparency and accountability in civil society are perceived as a body of knowledge in social science, determined as constructive reality and proved by many nations with appropriate actions. These actions comprise a set of prioritised approaches to achieving the central objectives of transparency and accountability. The researcher

examines transparency and accountability practices, not as an independent, external reality transformed into knowledge but as a construction of methods through which participants involved in phenomena understand the meaning, make sense and form an individual belief. From this perspective, transparency and accountability practices constitute a human construction developed by an understanding of phenomena. Individual participation is required to tackle challenges and find solutions (Szydlik et al., 2003). This objective can be achieved through a proactive process or capacity augmentation that requires action for an establishment to rationalise, understand, explore, communicate, apply, test and practically reflect.

Therefore, based on this ontological stance, this research focuses not only on the field of corporate governance, corruption and sustainable development, but also on transparency and accountability practices. Thus, the study engages transparency and accountability practices, corporate governance, anti-corruption and sustainable development agenda. This study will employ a qualitative approach to explore ways to improve and strengthen transparency and accountability practice in stages of institutional structure to combat corruption and establish effective governance and sustainable development in Mongolia.

3.3. Research Epistemological Stance and Rationality

The philosophy of epistemology concerns the learning process and 'the roots in which individuals believe something to be real (Oliver, 2010), that is, what is the existing educational knowledge and how is it known (Sharp, 2009). Consequently, the researcher's epistemological viewpoint is fundamental to the selection of methodology relative to the research aim and questions (Ritchie et al., 2003) as the research focuses on obtaining new knowledge. The examination of new knowledge is based on the methodology and the rationale of its selection. Thus, the methodology is directly connected to the strength of the new knowledge claimed.

The researcher's ontological and epistemological viewpoints are connected. The philosophy of ontology underpins the reality of beings, whereas the philosophy of epistemology underpins the knowledge of those beings. Thus, an ontological perspective perceives knowledge as existence that remains autonomous from the researcher's interpretation in determining epistemologically, new knowledge can be seized from objective reflection. In contrast, the ontological stance of knowledge is subject to the interpretation that new epistemological knowledge is learnt through understanding and making sense. Transparency and accountability practices influence establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. It is a constructed body of practices to be learnt through the communication of existence, justification and exercise of practical methods contributing to evoked and unconscious capacity augmentation of knowledge.

From the researcher's ontological viewpoint of transparency and accountability practice, effective corporate governance practice, anti-corruption and sustainable development is a social construction interconnectedly developed through cooperation among different social participants. This cooperation also upholds an epistemological viewpoint of learning through understanding and sense-making. Thus, this perspective influences the researcher's selected data collection methods and observational data used for analysis. The selection is based

on establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development through transparency and accountability practice and on how the new knowledge from the study is constructed.

This study employs the archival observation method in which the researcher's positionality would not be communicated at the risk of bias. Additionally, the research methodology enables the participants to express their individual views without directing questions to the researcher and expressing judgement. Similarly, all observational data will be presented without a predetermined concept from the researcher and reference to reality. Accordingly, data collection and analysis methods are necessary, through which participants can freely suggest and share their viewpoints with confidentiality and observed data can be interpreted, respectively. Thus, transparency and accountability practices can be improved and strengthened to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development validly and reliably.

Consequently, the ontological stance connects with the epistemological perspective of knowledge regarding the positionality of the researcher's viewpoint on establishment of effective governance practice, anti-corruption mechanisms and sustainable development. These philosophical underpinnings form the basis of the selection processes for data collection methods and analysis. An extensive review of research methodologies and analysis techniques will be discussed below. Then, the selected methods for this study will be justified.

3.4. Field Research Design

Research design is the framework of strategy selected by the researcher to incorporate different sections of the study logically and coherently and thus address the research problem effectively through data collection, study measurements and data analysis (Vaus, 2001). This study aims to address the research problem of exploring ways to improve and strengthen overall transparency and accountability practices to improve cooperation between different social participants, decentralise controlling power, and enhance inclusiveness of different stakeholders as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia where corruption is pervasive among state entities and main institutional organisations. Many scholars asserted that the application of governance theories and models in developing countries is challenging due to the complicated characters of political, institutional and socioeconomic settings.

This study employed the field research design because it explores ways to improve and strengthen transparency and accountability practice. This research design is also referred to as participant observation in the field, which involves various interpretative processes developed through the employment of multiple qualitative data collection methods (Bailey, 2017). Field observation data are documented in field notes, which are recorded at the field site. Field research design enables the researcher to address the research problem effectively in numerous ways as follows:

1. To fill the research gaps by understanding the research problem specific to local conditions and civil society, which cannot be established from previously provided data
2. To facilitate modes to scrutinise the origin, scale and scope of a problem and explore ways to resolve the problem in their inhabited environment

3. To validate the data by collecting additional data that contradict or support the findings stated of previous studies in the field of governance
4. To conduct interviews and observations that reflect the particular cultural setting of the situation being examined
5. To provide an opportunity to obtain new insights into examining contemporary theories and long-standing assumptions addressed in the literature

Findings from field research design provide an interpretation of the study findings that reveal underpinning concepts, ideas and themes.

3.5. Introduction of the Study Field Site

The National Council of Corporate Governance (NCCG) is located at the centre of Mongolia, behind the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and approximately 10 minutes away from the Mongolian Stock Exchange. It is a small office with five permanent employees and develops a contractual relationship with professionals and organisations depending on the project.

The NCCG members include president of Department of Trade and Development; director of Jargalkhaan Khaikhan consulting company; former executive director of Mongolian Stock Exchange; executive director of Mongolian Freight Exchange; head of financial markets and insurance division of financial policy department of ministry of finance; Financial Regulatory Commission; deputy chairman and head of policy development and management division of state property policy and regulatory agency; executive director of Mongolian institute of certified public accountants; secretary of Mongolian securities dealers association; president of Mongolian insurers association; member of board of Mongolian association of non-bank financial institution; and head of supervision department of the Mongolian Stock Exchange (NCCG, 2021).

The NCCG focuses not only on enhancing corporate governance awareness and shareholder rights but also on the cooperation between international and government organisations to promote good governance practice and provide consultancy. Within the framework of good governance development, the NCCG focuses on the following:

- Amending the security market and company laws and state and local property laws to enforce the implementation and practice of corporate governance code and business ethics
- Implementing good governance practices in major projects and program agreements with foreign investors
- Determining the level of governance practice of state-owned entities and disclosing to the public
- Improving accountability and responsibility of the BOD and bringing the accountability to international standards
- Evaluating governance practice and establishing a public information platform
- Organising training and seminars for the members of the BOD, executive management and their representative organisation
- Encouraging public–private sector cooperation at all levels in the development of good governance

Within this governance development framework, all the NCCG members fully support the project and provide resources. The organisation aims to develop convenient economic conditions derived from the principles of governance and the implementation of internationally recognised governance codes and ethics. All NCCG members are supportive and united, particularly the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and Mongolian Stock Exchange. They have a governance and enforcement team comprising their employees. For instance, the NCCG director introduced the researcher to the governance teams of the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and Mongolian Stock Exchange and appointed representatives to cooperate. The NCCG also organises seminars for members of the BOD and executive management. Certification is mutually required by the NCCG, Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and Mongolian Stock Exchange. The NCCG was established by the 187th Act of Financial Regulatory Commission on 16 November 2011 to implement the 'Corporate Governance National Development Program'. This program was adopted by the 69th Act of the Mongolian Government on 9 March 2011. Although the duration of the program had ended, the NCCG has decided to continue as a professional institute, collaborating between state and private companies as an independent and self-funded organisation by the 444th Act of Financial Regulatory Commission on 17 December 2015 and Article 2.1 of Note 24 of the Government on 25 April 2016 (NCCG, 2019).

While working on the field site with field experts, the researcher evaluated the compliance with the governance regulatory environment of the top 20 listed companies on the Mongolian Stock Exchange. Thus, volunteering in a professional organisation in the field has opened further opportunities to conduct archival research from the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and Mongolian Stock Exchange.

3.6. Data Collection Process: Gaining Access to the Study Field

To collect the desired data for this research, the researcher travelled to Mongolia and stayed for more than seven weeks from 18 January 2019 to 13 March 2019. On 21 January, the researcher visited the NCCG, which has been discovered from the review of the literature investigating the existing governance and institutional setting in Mongolia. Although the director was out for a meeting on that day, the researcher communicated with a manager to convey the purpose of the visit. The manager has contacted the director and requested the researcher to leave her contact details for the director. At around 5 P.M., the NCCG contacted the researcher and expressed that the director would like to meet the next day.

The meeting allowed the researcher to introduce herself to the director, including her purpose in Mongolia and duration of stay, discuss the research. The director welcomed the researcher and offered her to work as a temporary consultant and independent researcher in the office from 9 A.M. to 5 P.M. The director's business card and statement are presented in the appendices as evidence. Thus, the researcher worked on the site between 22 January 2019 and 11 March 2019.

The opportunity was suitable for an observational study to acquire an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon and cultural practices by observing various aspects in the field site. Fieldnotes are an effective approach to facilitating this process. Emerson et al. (2011) defined field notes as a description of experiences and observations

that the researcher has gained while engaging in an intense and complicated approach. It is a valuable method for qualitative scholars whose central objective is to understand the actual perceptions of the study being conducted. However, the main shortcoming of the use of field notes is that it is documented by the researcher and thus subject to memory. Therefore, a potential mindful or unmindful bias of the researcher may arise. Considering this drawback, the researcher will demonstrate her observation and understanding of reality true to the fact by constant comparison or providing evidence wherever possible.

3.7. Choice of Inductive Reasoning

Knowledge can be acquired using two key approaches to reasoning: inductive and deductive reasoning. Deductive reasoning is the process of testing an established theory to determine its applicability to a particular phenomenon (Hyde, 2006). In contrast, inductive reasoning is the process of developing a theory based on the observation of a particular phenomenon to create generalisations about the instance under research (Hyde, 2006). The choice of the reasoning approach depends on the disposition of the research questions, ontological underpinnings and epistemological nature.

In this research, inductive reasoning is given the exploratory nature of the study, exploring ways to improve and strengthen transparency and accountability practices as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in a country where corruption is widespread across structures and sectors. As mentioned previously, the inductive approach starts with observations and draws generalisations at the end. These generalisations must be tested to determine whether the results should be rejected or verified. Correspondingly, all ideologies derived from the inductive approach are theoretically formulated. However, in the inductive approach, the researcher should honestly record his/her actual observations, without any biases and prejudgements and with an open mind. Then, the record of these observations forms the foundation on which generalisation and theories are constructed to establish scientific knowledge. Bernard (2006) stated that inductive reasoning involves searching for a pattern of the observations and establishing a theory for those identified patterns through hypotheses.

One of the main features of inductive reasoning is that the researcher has complete freedom in determining the progress of the research. The inductive approach does not require an assumption at the start of the research, and the nature and type of findings are uncertain until the end of the research. This feature makes the inductive reasoning approach exceptionally appropriate for this specific study. The previous chapter has discussed that this study will be based on the wide perception of corporate governance practice due to the complexity of issues in developing countries, such as Mongolia. The researcher can understand and make sense of reality and construct theories. Additionally, the inductive reasoning approach is suitable for this study due to the absence of applicable corporate governance theories in developing countries as presented in the literature review. The available theories cannot address systematic corporate governance challenges. As stated by Lodico et al. (2010), in inductive reasoning, the researcher needs to apply the observations in describing the conditions being investigated or in establishing an abstract. Nevertheless, the nature of inductive reasoning illustrates that the approach is associated

with the qualitative methodology of observational data gathering and analysis, whereas deductive reasoning is associated with the quantitative methodology (Neuman, 2014).

However, scholars have been criticising certain characteristics of inductive reasoning concerning science. The dominant challenge of the inductive approach is that the collected data of the study and the investigator's partial knowledge of connections may manipulate his/her. Considering this concern, it can be argued that, firstly, the researcher is a Mongolian and, throughout her teenage years, has witnessed a growing number of social wrongdoings including widespread corrupt activities; the rich getting richer, poor getting poorer and decreasing number of the middle class; discrimination between being poor and rich; the government becoming the place who takes what; deteriorating legitimacy in society as everyone has respective views leading to increasing conflict; and arrogant public officers among others. Therefore, a longitudinal observation led the researcher to conduct this research on establishing effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in the context of developing country of Mongolia.

Secondly, the researcher had insufficient corporate governance knowledge when starting this study. When searching for articles in the field of corporate governance, the relationship between agents (managers) and principals (shareholders) at an organisation level is often discussed. The discussion resulted in a challenging and lengthy Literature Review chapter. The researcher's corporate governance perception was bigger than the principal-agent relationship to tackle systematic challenges and complexity of corporate governance in Mongolia. Thus, the researcher had to gather many forms of information from various fields of disciplines, such as corporate governance, public policy, corruption, patron-client relationship, corruption and sustainable development, for the literature review. The review discusses systematic challenges and complexities of corporate governance practice. Thus, the literature review chapter of this study has expanded the researcher's knowledge through various information sources, such as journal articles, books and reports.

Thirdly, in this research, the inductive reasoning process starts with the observation of annual reports, financial reports, shareholders' meeting reports and announcements made on responsible organisations. The reports of the top 20 listed companies with high market capitalisation on the Mongolian Stock Exchange are examined, discovering their common characteristics. In certain instances, new considerations can be formed, whereas the observations can induce specific principles when recurring relationships exist. Furthermore, the observations can induce additional innovative considerations when they are not manipulated by actions and current philosophies. Thus, inductive reasoning has been considered as the most appropriate approach for this study.

3.8. Choice of Primary Data Collection Method

Collecting study-specific data is the most essential part of conducting research. Although the researcher may have the ideal research proposal, his/her capacity to finish the research will be limited when the required data cannot be collected. The data collection process is a challenging task that requires exceptional planning, determination, understanding and meticulous work to finish the study effectively. The process of data collection starts with

identifying the type of data required, accompanied by sampling from the target population. Subsequently, the researcher has to apply specific methods to collect the data from the selected sample.

Data sources include primary and secondary data collection. Primary data collection aims to obtain new data for specific research problems using appropriate methods (Saunders et al., 2016). These new data are added to existing knowledge, making it available for use in future research. Then, they are transformed into secondary data. Primary data can be reused in (1) the portrayal of modern and historic attributes, (2) reproduction of the original research or comparative study, (3) re-analysis of new data obtained through new questions not addressed previously, (4) research methodology development and (5) learning. Alternatively, any form of primary data can be used as secondary data for further study in a similar field. An advantage of primary data collection is that they are exceptionally tailored to the research analysis. However, primary data have the disadvantage of being expensive to collect. Primary data are also termed raw data collected from the source in an uncontrolled or a controlled situation. Uncontrolled situations include a review of questionnaires or observations in a specific setting, whereas controlled situations can be experimental studies, in which the researcher can control certain variables. Thus, data cannot be collected from individuals to whom sampling plays a significant role.

The previous section has clarified that this study will employ the inductive reasoning approach. The inductive reasoning approach primarily enables the development of study results from significant, dominant and frequent themes hidden in raw information, without restrictions inflicted by structured research methodologies. Inductive reasoning provides an efficient and convenient approach to probing qualitative data for various research drives. Qualitative data are commonly gathered from observations and prolonged interactions with participants and phenomena under investigation. A combination of inductive reasoning and qualitative data collection is the most suitable approach for this study. Justification for the choice of inductive reasoning approach states that this study focuses on wide perception of corporate governance practice because Mongolia is a developing country with major systematic challenges at the centre of corporate governance mechanisms, implications to pervasive corruption and sustainable development.

The research gap for this study is the absence of transparency and insufficient accountability practices across all institutional sectors. Thus, to tackle the complexities of corporate governance issues, the inductive reasoning approach to qualitative data collection is selected because it enables the researcher to observe situations through practical experience in the field and determine misconduct that restrains transparency and accountability practices within the governance framework. Accordingly, qualitative data collection methods specifically selected for this study will be considered in the following.

3.9. Archival Research Selection

Qualitative research constitutes a holistic approach to exploration. It is also defined as a transformational construct that develops in a natural surrounding which allows the researcher to acquire detailed information through high engagement in real experiences (Creswell, 2003). Qualitative research employs intentional use for explaining, describing and interpreting gathered information. Leedy and Ormrod (2001) claimed that qualitative research tends

to build and formulate new theories, therefore providing a minimal structure in detail. Qualitative research has five forms: action research, grounded theory, case study, archival research and ethnographic study. The choice of archival research will be considered subsequently.

Archival research uses primary data archived in different repositories. These organisations are established to obtain, archive and distribute information for specific reasons, such as research. Different archival data require varying conditions to disseminate the data to the researcher. Data use is often limited to the researcher who requested the use of such data. According to Trace (2002), primary data include records, objects, documents, manuscripts, audio, visual and sound materials among other sources. Archives are stored to perform further activities rather than putting end zones. Therefore, archives intrinsically reveal the authenticity of those activities. Official archival data provide real-life information, which can be re-analysed, revised and compared with other primary or contemporary data. A close overlap has been observed between archival research data and secondary data collection. Qualitative data collection through archival research is the primary data collection process. Under this method, official administrative documents are held to purposefully establish particular institutions, whereas secondary data are primary data collection used for further studies.

The researcher was volunteered on the site of the NCCG and gained an opportunity to conduct archival research based on the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and the Mongolian Stock Exchange. Accordingly, the researcher has retrieved the documents of the top 20 listed companies. These documents include a record of the board meeting and annual reports from the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and financial statements and shareholders' meeting announcement from the Mongolian Stock Exchange and its website. These data help to assess the degree of compliance to the governance regulatory environment. The 20 listed companies were not selected by the researcher but were identified annually through their market capitalisation or high indexes recorded on the Mongolian Stock Exchange.

Archival research focuses on evaluating the degree of compliance to governance relevant laws and regulations. The purpose is to scrutinise governance and regulatory environment and its enforcement in the institutional setting through real-life experience. The researcher has reviewed company and security market laws and corporate governance codes. The researcher faced a challenge to capture adequate information in a simplified, organised and efficient manner. Hence, a weighted scoring model is employed to address this challenge. The weighted scoring model encompasses pre-established criteria drawn from company and security market laws and corporate governance codes and is divided into three main themes: transparency, shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, and board of directors (BOD). These theme headings have been given based on similar content stated in company and security market laws and corporate governance codes. Thus, volunteering enabled the researcher to conduct not only archival research but also observational study in the field through immersion in real-life experience.

3.10. Archival Research: Purposive Sampling

Sampling methods are predominantly categorised into probability and non-probability sampling (Dawson & Trapp, 2004). Probability sampling ensures the generalisability of research findings to the target population. The virtue of probability sampling assures every individual in the population an equal opportunity to be selected in the research. Probability sampling is further classified into simple random, cluster, stratified random, systematic random, multistage and multiphase sampling. All these probability sampling techniques use random selection. Probability sampling is widely used in the deductive reasoning approach and quantitative data collection. Alternatively, non-probability sampling is selected in purpose as it prevents difficulty in sampling with a particular approach in consideration. Non-probability sampling techniques include snowball sampling, quota sampling and purposive or convenience sampling. From here, archival research will be discussed further in detail followed by justifying how this method is applied in data collection.

The purposive sampling method is broadly applied in qualitative studies to recognise and select cases that obtain rich information to utilise scarce resources efficiently (Patton, 2002). This method involves recognising and selecting participants or groups of participants who are exceptionally experienced with or knowledgeable about an event of interest (Cresswell & Clark, 2011). Furthermore, Bernard (2002) and Spradley (1979) highlighted the importance of accessibility, the ability to interact and the eagerness to participate in experiences and behave in an expressive, communicative and reflective manner. On the contrary, random sampling is applied to confirm the generalisability of results by eliminating potential selection bias and controlling the potential impacts of identified and unidentified confounders.

The archival research study has selected and reviewed the archived documents of 20 companies from the Mongolian Stock Exchange and Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission. These selected companies are the top 20 listed companies with high indexes or big market capitalisation on the Mongolian Stock Exchange (2019). The list of the top 20 companies is released every year by the Mongolian Stock Exchange. Therefore, identifying and selecting the samples have no bias from the researcher. The research has believed that the selected top 20 listed companies with high indexes on the Mongolian Stock Exchange show a high degree of compliance with the governance regulatory environment based on two grounds. Firstly, as reported by CFA Institute Research Foundation (2021), 200 companies are registered on the Mongolian Stock Exchange in 2019, which is the latest update. Thus, the top 20 listed companies represent 10% of the total listed companies on the Mongolian Stock Exchange, which is a sufficient representation of the market.

Secondly, stock market indexes are generated by choosing a set of companies who are registered and issued shares on a public stock market. Therefore, the top 20 companies are formed by the 20 leading companies registered on the Mongolian Stock Exchange as evaluated by market capitalisation. The degree of an index is measured by demonstrating the cumulative price fluctuations in numerous points and is also presented as a percentage. Companies enlist and eject from an index due to their market capitalisation upsurges and plummets. The compositions of the index of corporations are reviewed regularly to ensure that corporations qualify to be listed

under an index. The Mongolian Stock Exchange reviews the constituents of the top 20 listed companies every year. The stock market index for the top 20 listed companies is a measure of many market assessments including business assurance, stock market assurance and the conditions of the economy and investments among others. Similarly, the widely accepted indexes that are commonly used are the FTSE 100, Dow Jones Industrial Average, DAX, S&P 500, CAC and Hang Seng.

In addition to the top 20 selected companies, the narrow perception of corporate governance practice deals with relationships between principals (shareholders) and agents (managers) of publicly listed companies, where ownership and control are separated. By analysing the behaviour of the selected top 20 listed companies, the researcher has encountered common practical issues that further raised questions regarding the wide perception of corporate governance practice and institutional infrastructure.

3.11. Archival Research: Potential Bias

Scientific research needs to be planned, conducted and disclosed transparently, without diverging from validity and truthfulness. Research that is not characterised by these fundamental principles is misleading. Research has many sources of bias; thus, avoiding or managing potential bias is essential. Here, the term bias refers to any divergence from truthful data collection, analysis, interpretation and reporting, which can result in a misleading conclusion. Bias arises either unintentionally or intentionally (Gardenier & Resnik, 2010).

Researchers in qualitative studies may face confrontations with language differences. This issue arises when study participants and the researcher speak the same local language, and the local language data are translated into English language publications. Language differences can potentially lead to negative consequences due to misconceptions between languages. Such condition is particularly associated with qualitative studies, which are based on words. In contrast, language is the core in all stages of research, from data collection and analysis to reporting in publications. Squires (2008) argued that the impacts of shifting between languages on validity have attracted considerable attention in cross-country studies. Nevertheless, Polkinghorne (2005) claimed that qualitative research is valid when the gap between the understanding of the participants and as decoded in the outcomes is minimal.

In this study, the pre-established criteria used in the weighted scoring model are imported from company and securities market laws and corporate governance codes in Mongolia. The researcher's native language is Mongolian. Thus, these pre-established criteria were initially formulated in the language of Mongolia and subsequently translated into English by the researcher. This process could potentially bias the translation. However, in this study, doing so does not impact the research because these pre-established criteria are legal propositions stated in most unpretentious words, without different meanings. Therefore, bias in the translation is highly unlikely and unnecessary. Moreover, utilising a professional translation service was expensive, considering that the researcher has travelled to Mongolia with a limited budget. Consequently, the researcher's translation of the legal propositions stated in Mongolia's company and securities market laws and corporate governance codes does not impact the data collection, analysis and interpretations and findings.

3.12. Archival Research: Content Analysis

LeCompte and Schensul (1999) defined data analysis as the procedure of condensing a bulky amount of gathered data to interpret the results. Data can be analysed using various strategies in quantitative and qualitative data analyses. Quantitative data analysis comprises descriptive statistics, regressions, correlations and cross-tabulation. By contrast, the qualitative methodology is characterised by belief in much diverse existence, commitment to determining an approach to a detailed understanding of reality, commitment to participants' perspectives, investigations with least distraction to the natural setting of the phenomenon and records of outcomes in a literary format containing participants' experiences (Streubert & Carpenter, 2011). Qualitative methods commonly aim to expand the understanding of a certain phenomenon from the viewpoint of those who are experiencing it. Qualitative data analysis includes grounded theory, discourse, framework, narrative, content and thematic analyses.

Data gathered in the weighted scoring model from the top 20 listed companies' archived documents have been analysed through qualitative content analysis due to its unique feature that facilitates the researcher to apply various analysis methods for a large amount of documented information (Powers & Knapp, 2006). These selected companies are the top 20 listed companies with a high index on the Mongolian Stock Exchange. Furthermore, a detailed discussion of purposive sampling above explains other reasons for selecting the top 20 companies and the selection method.

In 2013, the NGCC and International Finance Corporation, Japanese organisation, conducted a similar study based on 2011 data (NCCG, 2013). The study assessed the overall corporate governance practice in Mongolia using five categories: shareholders' rights; equal treatment to shareholders; the role of corporate governance participants; transparency; and responsibility of the BOD. This assessment of the Mongolian corporate governance practice was based on the OECD's principles and evaluation methods, Mongolian corporate governance legal framework and administration structure and the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission's corporate governance codes. The assessment of corporate governance practice was conducted for the top 20 listed companies on Mongolian Stock Exchange. The top 20 selected companies had a total market capitalisation of over 89.5% in 2011, whereas 336 companies were registered, 215 of which were active.

The assessment has been conducted using 123 questions within the above-mentioned five categories. The assessment focused on collecting various data available for public. Accordingly, the investigation involved reviewing company annual report; financial report; guidance from Mongolian Stock Exchange; guidance from Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission; protocols of meetings particularly, shareholders' meetings; company policy; company websites; and other sources. The assessment had been conducted based on a scoring method between 2 and 0: where 2 marks company complies with good practice; 1 marks company insufficiently complies with good practice; and 0 marks the company does not comply with good practice.

Subsequently, the companies were divided into four percentage bands based on their total score: (1) 5% and above indicates very good, (2) 65%–74% indicates good, (3) 50%–64% indicates moderate, and (4) 50% and below

indicates insufficient. Overall, the assessment of corporate governance practice revealed that all 20 companies have scored below 50%, signifying insufficient corporate governance practice (NCCG, 2013).

The NCCG (2015) replicated the assessment of corporate governance practice in 2015 to compare and determine whether corporate governance practice shows an improvement. The findings demonstrated an exponential improvement in practice.

Table 4: Compliance Performance of Listed Companies between 2013 and 2015

Governance of Listed Companies							
Categories	2013			2015			2013 versus 2015
	Number of questions	Percentage (%) of total rating score	Total score in percentage (%)	Number of questions	Percentage (%) of total rating score	Total score in percentage (%)	
Shareholders' rights	22	15	50.7	20	20	58.4	Improved
Equal treatment to shareholders	19	15	29.7	11	10	50.0	Improved
Role of participants	14	10	16.1	12	10	44.7	Improved
Transparency	32	30	18.0	20	30	50.0	Improved
Responsibility of the BOD	36	30	9.6	30	30	57.0	Improved
Total	123	100	27.5 (Average)	93	100	53.4 (Average)	Improved

Source: NCCG (2013; 2015)

Table 4 above demonstrates five categories used to conduct the assessment of corporate governance practice. Each category involves different number of questions and percentage of total rating score. The assessment methodology-scoring system had been conducted as subsequently: (1) selected questions were scored and calculated the total score for each category; (2) each category's total score were then divided by maximum total score of all five categories, which resulted the percentage of the section within entire questions set; (3) multiply the percentage of the category by total coefficient in each category, which generated total percentage per section; and (4) calculate total coefficient in percentage for all five sections.

For example, the category of shareholders' rights comprises 22 questions; total allocated scores had been calculated for category shareholders' rights, which then divided by total maximum score of 246 (highest score is two multiplied by total number of questions:123) and resulted 15%; followed by total coefficient multiplier in each section, which resulted 50.7% for the category of shareholders' right.

In comparison between 2013 and 2015, the total number of questions have been reduced by 30 questions, and the percentage is consistent. Therefore, the reduction of questions with stable percentage could potentially result in improvement in performance.

In this study, the assessment of compliance had been conducted with application of alternative approach of weight scoring model. The archival research has discussed previously that the weighted scoring model contains pre-established criteria derived from company law, law of security market, and corporate governance codes. These criteria were categorised into three themes: transparency, shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, and BOD which were conveyed from company law, law of security market, and corporate governance codes. The archival research had intended to assess companies' compliance to corporate governance regulatory environment. Theme of transparency involves 16 criteria, theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting contains 15 criteria, and theme of BOD includes 18 criteria respectively. After listing all legal provisions, the researcher and a representative from Mongolian Stock Exchange had reviewed them multiple times.

Overall, 49 criteria are pre-listed. As the name suggests, the weighted scoring model involves calculation. For instance, if all 49 criteria are 100%, the weight of theme: transparency with 16 criteria is calculated as $16/49*100\% = 32.65\%$, the weight of theme: shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting with 15 criteria is equivalent to $15/49*100\% = 30.61\%$, and the weight of theme: BOD with 18 criteria is calculated as $18/49*100\% = 36.73\%$ correspondingly. As mentioned previously, these pre-established criteria are legal provisions. Therefore, each criterion has equal importance in the weighted scoring model. The weight of each criterion in the theme of transparency is $32.65\%/16 = 2.04\%$, which is rounded off to 2.0% to visually simplify the table. A similar calculation has been performed on the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting and the theme of BOD. The weight of each criterion is defined as $30.61\%/15 = 2.04$ and $36.73\%/18 = 2.04\%$ respectively and both are rounded off to 2.0%. The degree of impact of each criterion on the overall result depends on the number attempting to communicate multiplied by the unique criterion weight. This steady calculation of criteria depends on the criterion weight and the score is the fundamental feature of the weighted scoring model. Accordingly, each criterion has been scored between 4 and 0: where 4 indicates company exceptionally complies with governance laws and regulations; 3 indicates the company respectably complies with governance laws and regulations; 2 marks the company moderately complies with governance laws and regulations; 1 signifies the company poorly complies with governance laws and regulations; and 0 implies company does not comply with governance laws and regulations.

Appropriate scores were assigned to each company based on their archived materials. A score of 2 is assigned if the company mentioned the criterion on the report, alternatively, the company moderately complies with governance laws and regulations. Therefore, the score of 2 is the threshold in this weighted scoring model. Depending on the degree of details provided in archived documents, a score of 3 or 4 was assigned to that company. In contrast, if legal provision or criterion is considered on company's reports briefly or not considered or skipped, a score of 1 or 0 are assigned respectively. For instance, in the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, criterion B3 states: Does the company promptly provide information to shareholders relevant to an annual report, financial situation, risks and company operations? A review of archived documents has revealed that certain companies had provided their reports on time, a few companies had provided late, and risk-relevant information has been missing for all top 20 companies. In this case, the scores ranging between 3 and 4 were allocated because the question has asked: Does the company provide information on time? -the answer was 'yes' for majority of the

companies. In contrast, if the question had asked: Does the company provide risk assessment report or risk-relevant information? - the answer could have been 'no'. Therefore, the allocated score could be '0'. The scoring was based on archived documents, therefore, an appropriate score had to be provided based on information rather than observation. From here, it can be claimed that the researcher should have separated the questions, yet, it had mentioned prior that the pre-established criteria were not developed by the researcher, instead, they had been translated from the Mongolian legal provisions.

Although this weighted scoring model is commonly used in quantitative or deductive studies, it has also been applied in qualitative studies to quantify results. Thus, its adaptable feature has enabled the researcher not only to organise gathered data in a consistent, determined manner, but also to work efficiently in terms of time and amount of data collected. Comparable data had allowed the researcher to evaluate companies' compliance to governance regulatory environment. If the weighted scoring model results in numeric values though the data collection possesses is qualitative in nature, it could potentially raise confusion that quantitative data analysis method should be applied rather than qualitative content analysis. Nevertheless, qualitative content analysis has another key characteristic that enables the researcher to conduct data analysis qualitatively, despite the quantitative results (Gbrich, 2007). Consequently, the employment of the weighted scoring model in archival research has allowed effective data analysis through content analysis.

Comparing the content analysis and previous assessments, it can be observed that studies have been developed based on Mongolian governance regulatory framework. However, previous assessments have employed more criteria to evaluate corporate governance practice, as presented in Table 5 below. The assessment criteria have also been derived from the OECD's principles and evaluation methods, the Mongolian corporate governance legal framework and administration structure and Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission's corporate governance codes. The content analysis in this study has focused on corporate governance regulatory framework, particularly company law, law of security market, and corporate governance codes. Similarly, the number of criteria in this content analysis is less than that used in previous assessments. Also, the scores range between 4 and 0 in the weighted scoring model, which is wider than the previous assessments, ranging between 2 and 0. These differences may be the reason the compliance rate is higher compared with the previous assessments (Table 5). All studies have been conducted on the top 20 listed companies with large market capitalisation, though is reviewed annually.

Table 5: Compliance Performance of Listed Companies between 2013, 2015 and 2020

Governance of Listed Companies											
Categories	2013			2015			2013 versus 2015	2020			2015 versus 2020
	Number of questions	Weight	Result	Number of questions	Weight	Result	Up/down +/-	Number of questions	Weight	Result	Up/down +/-
Shareholders' rights	22	15	50.7	20	20	58.4	+	15	30.6	86	+
Equal treatment to shareholders	19	15	29.7	11	10	50.0	+				
Role of participants	14	10	16.1	12	10	44.7	+	x			
Transparency	32	30	18.0	20	30	50.0	+	16	32.7	91	+
Responsibility of the BOD	36	30	9.6	30	30	57.0	+	18	36.7	93	+
Total	123	100	27.5	93	100	53.4	+	49	100	90	+

Source: NCCG (2013; 2015)

Regarding the stages of content analysis, the previous assessments used a two-stage process: calculating the total score and separating the total score into pre-determined percentage bands. In contrast, this study has applied the weighted scoring model which has facilitated the researcher to combine this two-stage process and qualitatively interpret the data.

3.13. Observational Study Selection

An observational study is a non-experimental and qualitative study that intends to observe, document and analyse a specific culture, society, attitudes and behaviours (Ciesielska et al., 2018). Observational studies are categorised as non-experimental because observations do not control any variables. Observations are typically divided into non-participant or naturalistic observation, participant observation and controlled observation based on the structural level of the social setting. Naturalistic observation is conducted in an environment where the study matter is observed unassumingly as it is performed by an outside observer (Ciesielska et al., 2018). Naturalistic observation is often used by sociologists to investigate belief systems, cultural practices, proscribes of social groups and cultural practices.

Participant observation is part of naturalistic observation because it is applied in a social setting. It demands researchers to covertly participate or overtly engage in the study setting. Covert participant observation entails that an investigator becomes a part of a particular group and observes without the participants' knowledge, whereas participant observation infers that the participants are informed that they are the subjects of the study. Controlled observation is performed in an environment that is limited to a structure. This type of observation is commonly applied in marketing and psychology studies. Control observation operates as an exclusion to the non-

experimental characteristic of observational study as it is studied in a controlled setting. In contrast, uncontrolled observation involves naturalistic observation applied in an unstructured environment. In addition to the types of observations, a study environment is also classified into structured and unstructured observations. Structured observation uses a particular structure for observing, classifying and documenting behaviour, whereas unstructured observation employs an open-minded approach to a study matter in which the investigator documents everything that has been observed and then examines the collected data.

An observational study has many advantages, such as flexibility, inexpensiveness, open-mindedness, allows to record any changes, great environmental validity, enables a researcher to understand a phenomenon or society, provides an option to the researcher to participate either overtly or covertly and leads to more in-depth observation. However, observational studies have certain disadvantages: they are conducted at a small scale, less consistent, difficult to apply in constructing cause–effect relationships, time-consuming, challenging in obtaining access, impossible to be analysed statistically and involved with various ethical issues or potential biases brought by the researcher.

3.14. Observational Study: Gathering Information Process

This study conducted an observational study while undertaking archival research. The weighted scoring model has been employed to capture extensive data in an organised manner. The model consists of three themes: transparency, shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, and BOD. Thus, the observational data relative to archival research dealt with how transparency and accountability is practiced, how shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting are exercised and conducted and how the BOD operates. In addition, the researcher conducted an observational study on the overall content in reports and compared them between the 20 listed companies. For example, one company's annual report contains its background information more than halfway with limited information on performance or other relevant information, whereas another company's annual report presents information about its brief background, performance, CSR, risk management and other relevant information. Thus, the content of annual reports was inconsistent across the top 20 companies. This condition has been observed when the researcher scored the companies based on the information they provided to the market and the public.

These study observations performed on the purposefully selected 20 companies have been gathered during the review of archived documents for the top 20 companies to assign scores to the pre-established criteria in the weighted scoring model. In the theme of transparency, this study employed the online platform of the Mongolian Stock Exchange, where listed companies submit required documents regularly and investors and the public primarily obtain necessary market and company information. Therefore, the platform must be highly transparent, accountable, rich in information, current and fast. Annual financial reports and shareholders' meeting announcements have been reviewed to score the compliance to transparency practice based on a pre-established criterion. The process was complex as the associated observations comprising contents in annual reports were various, unclear and time-consuming. Moreover, audit reports were absent; the main institutions have insufficient reinforcement; and the shareholders' meeting announcements of selected companies were close to the date or

published after the date. For instance, if the shareholders' meeting was on 23 July, then the announcement was published on 18 July. The researcher believed that this short notice is unreasonable.

In the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, as well as the theme of BOD, the researcher had examined the shareholders' meeting reports for the selected 20 companies from the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission. The latest documents were dated 2019 and reviewed under the company's supervision in a room with two to four people. Certain documents were not allowed for the researcher. The examination of the shareholders' meeting report revealed several issues: most of the content in the shareholders' meeting reports were replicated legal provisions from company law, law of security market, and corporate governance codes; audit and risk management information were insufficient; other stakeholders exhibit negligence as none of the documents mentioned about other stakeholders but rather focus on the main shareholders, BOD, mission, vision, main operations in a particular sector, profit/loss and statement of objectives for upcoming years; corporate governance codes are only formulated without implementation and practice; and market dominance with any competitors hardly exists.

3.15. Observational Study: Additional Information

The researcher has volunteered in the NCCG was introduced to a governance team in the Mongolian Stock Exchange. The researcher has the absence of audit and risk management and, in response, has contacted a representative to clarify the observation. Accordingly, the researcher has confirmed that although listed companies were required to provide audit reports since 2019, the reports are voluntary, not compulsory. Regarding data validity concerns in the observational study, the researcher has further clarified the observations. Individuals who provided additional information remained anonymous due to ethical concerns in research. This further clarification for the observational study has validated the researcher's observations during the archival examination. The clarified information has been analysed through grounded theory, and findings have supported the content analysis with an in-depth explanation.

In addition, the researcher has attended a training course organised by the NCCG. The training course aims to educate the public about good corporate governance practices. The information provided through the course focused on shareholders and their rights. The researcher has observed that the information is inappropriate in the case of Mongolia because corporate governance mechanism issues are bigger than different types of shareholders and their rights. Furthermore, the central argument of this study states that if the national corporate governance mechanisms do not function effectively and cause pervasive corruption, then exploring organisation-level corporate governance practice in developing countries with high corruption is worthless. Therefore, training courses should focus more on the wide perception of corporate governance practice than on the narrow perception. This additional observed information has supported the observational study and was analysed through grounded theory analysis. Finally, the findings of the grounded theory analysis supported the findings of content analysis with great detail.

3.16. Observational Study: Grounded Theory Analysis

The gathered information through the observational study were analysed using the qualitative grounded theory. Grounded theory analysis aims to develop a theory or theoretical framework based on observed data (Knigge & Cope, 2006). The analysis method was selected to analyse the observed information in this study. The method is also appropriate for unstructured qualitative data analysis, including observations, interviews, texts and focus groups as it provides flexibility with direction. The key principle of grounded theory analysis is to describe considerable details of different sources, starting with open coding (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). In the open coding process, the observed information was explained in detail and tabulated for a visual demonstration. Open coding has defined six categories. Then, these categories have been compared with each other by answering questions of what, where, when, why and how, together with the consequences in conditional interrelationship guide. Thus, the researcher was able to define interrelationships and patterns among the identified categories, which have been sorted through open coding.

Consequently, the conditional interrelationship guide transmits structure to process. Subsequently, the researcher has applied an introspective coding matrix to create a storyline of the various patterns discovered in the conditional interrelationship guide. The introspective coding matrix was employed mainly to contextualise the underlying category, namely the integral phenomenon that connects to the other significant and insignificant categories. Lastly, the final phase of grounded theory is the selective coding or interpretive process which focuses on incorporating all the interpretive effort of the analysis. Thus, relevant phenomena were incorporated in the underlying category through the storyline. Accordingly, the underlying category was determined as promoting transparency and accountability initiatives.

The grounded theory analysis has assisted the researcher in conceptualising information that has been observed during the archival research and expanding the understanding of the phenomenon. The findings of grounded theory analysis have supported the content analysis by enabling the researcher to provide comprehensive interpretation. For instance, the content analysis has shown a high compliance rate for transparency practice. However, the observational study has shown that the absence of audit and risk management information in addition to the replication of legal provisions has further challenged the compliance rate of transparency. Comparing the findings between the content analysis and grounded theory analysis enabled the researcher to interpret the collected data in detail. Finally, a detailed analysis of the observational study associated with the present study will be discussed in the following chapter.

3.17. Choice of Multimethod Approach

Depending on the complexity of a study, the researcher can apply either mono, mixed or multimethod approach. The mono-method research design is often used in quantitative research, where topics are widely known but still require clarifications, whereas the mixed-method approach allows the researcher to combine methods of information gathering and analysis from qualitative and quantitative research methodologies (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998; Creswell, 2003; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Alternatively, the researcher can obtain and analyse

not only numeric information collected through quantitative research but also narrative information obtained through qualitative research to answer research sub-question(s) stated in a specific study.

In contrast, the multimethod approach is often applied to a research scheme with various interlinked projects within a single broad research subject and designed to answer the main research question (Morse, 2003). This method requires more than a single source of information, whereas the mono-method approach (quantitative or qualitative) employs only one research method or information source (Bryman, 2006).

Scholars from various fields of studies suggest the application of the multimethod approach to investigating complicated social circumstances (Brewer & Hunter, 1989; Creswell, 2003; Newman & Benz, 1998). The multimethod approach helps to acquire complete answers and enhance the potency of our knowledge (Mingers, 2001). Employing the multimethod approach improves the understandings of the dynamic aspects of an event through the study. Thus, the researcher gains a detailed explanation. Mingers (2001) claimed that applying more than one research technique in a single study focuses on various aspects of existence, thus generating an improved understanding of a research topic. Certain studies, such as in geography, are fundamentally interconnected and have employed the multimethod approach and incorporated results for several years. The application of the multimethod approach in this study is necessary based on three reasons. Firstly, this study deals with the wide perception of corporate governance practice in the developing country of Mongolia, where institutional infrastructure is underdeveloped and corporate governance mechanisms are complex. Therefore, the multimethod approach is the most appropriate choice for investigating such complicated social phenomena as it enables the researcher to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the different aspects of an event.

Secondly, the research gap has been identified as the underlying cause for ineffective corporate governance practice, pervasive corruption and stagnant sustainable development is the absence of transparency and accountability practices on a large scale. Therefore, the multimethod approach was necessary to address various transparency and accountability practices, which are required to be incorporated in existing corporate governance mechanisms but not exercised properly in practice. Thirdly, this study has adopted inductive observations in addition to the qualitative archival research which forms the multimethod approach. Employing more than one research instrument focusing on different sides of reality has allowed the researcher to recognise significant issues in transparency and accountability practices. Moreover, a reinforcement of these defined transparency and accountability practices will improve the corporate governance framework to combat corruption and generate implications for sustainable development. Hence, the multimethod approach was the most suitable choice for this study.

3.18. Cross-sectional Study Selection

Studies are conducted in a certain period and classified into either longitudinal or cross-sectional. Longitudinal study consistently applies repetitive or continuous measurements to specific individuals for a long period, in months or years (Caruana et al., 2015). Research is often associated with many threats to the study because of its virtue of a prolonged period. The potential challenges include interrupted or incomplete follow-up of certain individuals, substantial funding needs, failed conclusion and complications in the separation of the corresponding

impression of exposure and effect. In contrast, a cross-sectional study is conducted for a short period or at one timepoint. Therefore, it only provides an overview of a result, and the characteristics associated with this study demonstrate a specific time. A cross-sectional study is often conducted to measure the prevalence of an effect of interest for a target population (Levin, 2006). The characteristic of a snapshot of time could have certain drawbacks: a snapshot could produce different results at different times, and drawing causal assumptions is difficult (Mann, 2003). Cross-sectional studies are also considered observational because all necessary data are gathered to study a phenomenon at a single time point.

Qualitative archival research and observations were conducted using the multimethod approach for approximately seven weeks, from Monday to Friday between 9 A.M. and 5 P.M. In the observational study, the researcher has recorded observed information about a phenomenon without influencing natural existence. In contrast, in the archival research, the researcher had managed to obtain access to the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and Mongolian Stock Exchange to review existing records of the top 20 listed companies without communicating with a single participant. This cross-sectional study has facilitated the researcher to examine various variables within limited time. The researcher had managed to investigate cooperation, controlling power and inclusiveness in regards to broader transparency and accountability practice as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development at a minimal cost. The choice of whether cross-sectional study or longitudinal study depends on the research questions. Accordingly, adopting a cross-sectional study in this research was the right decision.

3.19. Ethical Principles of Conduct

Ethical challenges are inevitable in any type of research. The study process develops pressure between the study objectives and participants' privacy rights. Research ethics aims at preventing harm and doing good for others. Potential harm during the research process can be mitigated or avoided through the appropriate application of ethical principles. Thus, safeguarding participants in any type of research is critical. This section discusses potential ethical challenges and ethical behaviour of the researcher to be applied and maintained in this multimethod study. Such ethical challenges and principles are classified into autonomy, beneficence and justice and inclusiveness, each of which will be explained below.

3.19.1. Autonomy

Many authors have asserted that respect for human rights is an obligation in any type of research (Munhall, 1988; Raudonis, 1992; Kvale, 1996; Dresser, 1998). Capron (1989) supported this consideration and claimed that all types of research should be conducted according to the principles of protection of autonomy, justice, beneficence and confidentiality. He speculated that respect for autonomy is the appreciation of human rights, involving the right to know about the research, the right to decide independently whether to contribute to the research and the full right to terminate at any time without consequences.

Throughout the qualitative data collection process, the autonomy ethical principle has been applied when gaining access to the field site of the NCCG and obtaining permission to retrieve archival administrative documents from

the Mongolian Stock Exchange and Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission. The researcher introduced herself and the research area and purpose to the director of the NCCG and the department head. In addition, the director and department head had the full right whether to participate in the research.

3.19.2. Beneficence

Another important ethical consideration that needs to be reviewed in any type of research is beneficence, that is, the right attitude to protect vulnerable individuals and cause no harm to others (Orb et al., 2000). In particular situations, beneficence could become a central principle than others and exercise the paternalism approach, which involves the refusal of autonomy.

Data gathering methodologies and participant selection methods also comprise ethical consequences. Raudonis (1992) claimed that the inclusion of participants should involve great consideration during the selection process. In addition to maintaining the ethical consideration of beneficence, managing the potential outcomes of publishing the identification of participants is a moral duty. Thus, the participants will be informed about how data will be stored and used in the research. Furthermore, the participants' approval will be requested regarding the publication of other information, such as quotations, as such publication could potentially reveal the participants' identity, though anonymous. Despite the necessity of protecting confidentiality, the data collection process requires confirmability, keeping all documents involved in this research. As recommended by Streubert and Carpenter (2011), this confirmability assists other researchers in overseeing. The researcher was allowed to review certain documents under supervision while retrieving administrative documents from the Mongolian Stock Exchange and Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission. Therefore, the researcher considered the publication of information with confidentiality, without revealing any identity.

3.19.3. Justice and Inclusiveness

The third ethical principle associated with this research is justice, fairness and equal treatment. This principle is mainly characterised by the prevention of abuse and exploitation of participants. Identifying participants' vulnerability and impact on the research demonstrates the researcher's degree of consideration and application of justice in this multimethod study. Another way to exercise ethical justice is by protecting the autonomy of the most vulnerable participants, such as those with cognitive impairment, mentally ill, emotionally unstable, children and elderly people, and by listening to the calls of disadvantaged and minority groups. As stated by Capron (1989), such practical challenges emerge when researchers exercise the principle of ethical justice.

Following the scope and objectives of this research, the participants have not been discriminated against religion, race, language, gender, age, ethnicity, disability and sex to contribute to this research.

3.20. Research Validity

Validity is focused on the accountability of research instruments and indicates the extent of their measurement. Although complete definiteness validity does not exist, researchers should strongly support the validity of their measurements (Bollen, 1989). Four categories of validity should be considered within the research: statistical conclusion, internal, construct and external validity. Statistical conclusion of validity measures the relationship

between two variables. A definition provided by Cook and Campbell (1979), statistical conclusion validity deals with interpretations of whether presumed covariations resulted in an identified alpha level and the acquired variances. A statistical conclusion has several constraints, such as the bias of assumptions, unsatisfied statistical data, reliability of measurement and reliability of conduct. Internal validity tests the validity of the study. For instance, a class teacher measures the students' teaching satisfaction. Only half of the class participated in the survey, though all students appreciate their teacher. Here, the raising question on internal validity is: Does the teacher hold a representable sample of students or a discriminated sample? Many factors can threaten internal validity, including demoralisation, sample selection, dissemination of treatment, instrumentation and testing.

Construct validity stresses how adequately data analysis is transformed or translated into an idea, concept or behaviour, developing a construct into an operating and functioning concept, referred to as operationalisation (Mann, 2003). External research validity implies drawing generalisation on other individuals, times and settings. Generalising into a well-defined population should be separated from generalising into entire populations. Each concept is related to external validity: the first concept is important in verifying whether any study objectives have been met within the target population, whereas the second concept is significant to detecting other populations involved in the research process to evaluate the scope of generalisation (Cook & Campbell, 1979).

In this study of an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia, internal, construct and external validity can be discussed. Here, the internal validity of research instruments was strengthened by justifying the selected methods for this study. Regarding the selection of sample for archival research, the list of the 20 listed companies with indexes is announced by the Mongolian Stock Exchange every financial year. Hence, the sample selection for archival research does not contain discrimination. Contrarily, the study construct validity can be observed in Chapter 4 Data Collection and Analysis to determine how the analysed data transformed into an idea or concept into a functioning matter. Lastly, the external validity can be seen in Chapter 6 Conclusion, where the researcher summarises the entire research and verifies whether the research questions have been answered with logical reasoning.

3.21. Research Reliability

Reliability focuses on a subjective test employed to measure certain attributes or aspects (Rosenthal & Rosnow, 1991). It relies on the consistency and stability of measurements under different situations and events and with other substitute instruments, which test the same object.

Errors can arise due to various causes, including the variations in different types of measurement, such as the conditional aspects that impact the attitude of the topics under investigation, and the different approaches employed by different researchers. Therefore, the researcher is constrained by the reliability of the test methods and the individual who employs them. Reliability measurement does not always result as valid. According to Bollen (1989), a reliability measurement involves a free range of errors and does not require that measuring instruments must be valid. Hence, highly reliable instruments may not be valid. In other words, although reliability is a crucial measurement, it does not provide a sufficient position for validity (Nunnally, 1978).

Numerous factors impede tests from being explicitly replicable. Such factors are subject to the nature of the measurement and the manner it is conducted (Nunnally, 1978). The errors of test that trigger changes in the reliability of the measurement and the errors of the instrument arising from a change in reliability on alternative types of a test must be categorised. Reliability errors are fundamentally caused by sampling. Every individual has an equal chance to be selected for the measurement; thus, the greater the number of participants, the greater is the magnitude of the eliminated error and the more reliability improve. Alternatively, reliability can be strengthened by a statement of test and simple design. A highly reliable test is primarily designed with long measurements. In contrast, it can be argued that long measurements can cause fatigue and boredom during the answering process, reducing the continuity of meticulous response (Rosenthal & Rosnow, 1991).

If this research will be replicated in the future using the same research instruments, the reliability of measurement is likely to be consistent. The reason is that this study has employed archival research and observation, which focus on social practices formed by an institutional environment for nearly three decades. However, the research reliability would have minor errors, which may occur in archival research.

1. For archival research, the weighted scoring model has been used to assess the degree of compliance to governance regulatory environments and has allocated scores ranging between 0 and 4. In this research, a score of 4 is assigned to companies that met the relevant criteria and 0 otherwise. This allocation of score range could vary between individuals.
2. The archival research is conducted on the top 20 selected listed companies with a high market capitalisation as identified by the Mongolian Stock Exchange, and the list is reviewed every financial year. Therefore, changes in the sample can potentially affect the reliability of measurement.
3. Time can also affect the reliability of measurement. Following this present study, certain measurements may be improved or worsened in future studies. All these changes occurring over time can cause consistency errors in measurement.

Otherwise, the reliability of measurements is expected to be consistent as the data are collected based on social practices and systems shaped over time. In addition, all the detailed measurements have been categorised into transparency and accountability, cooperation, controlling power and inclusiveness. These can be implemented in practice through social capacity augmentation. The grounded theory analysis provides a long list of detailed measurements that can potentially support the reliability of this research.

3.22. Chapter Summary

The chapter has discussed the research methodology, philosophical underpinnings, research design, methods, sampling, data collection and analysis methods, the mixed-method versus multimethod approach, the longitudinal versus cross-section study, ethical principles, validity and reliability.

The application of the selected research methods in this study has been justified. Table 6 below summarises these methods. The data collected through these methods will be discussed in Chapter 4 Data Collection and Analysis.

Table 6: Summary of Research Methodologies

Research Methodology	Suitability
Ontological underpinning	The researcher's ontological viewpoint of transparency, accountability, good governance, anti-corruption and sustainable development is a social construction interconnectedly developed through cooperation rooted in such factors.
Epistemological underpinning	The ontological viewpoint upholds an epistemological viewpoint of learning through understanding and sense-making.
Field research design	This study employed the field research design because it explores methods for improving and strengthening the transparency and accountability practice. This research design is also referred to as participant observation in the field, involving various interpretative processes developed upon employment of multiple qualitative data collection methods.
Inductive approach	Inductive reasoning is used as this research explores methods for improving and strengthening transparency and accountability practices to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in a country where corruption is widespread across various structures and sectors.
Archival research and observation	The study applies archival research alongside observation to explore methods for improving and strengthening transparency and accountability practices by addressing practical issues. Both qualitative methods are used to gather primary data.
Sampling	Purposefully selected top 20 listed companies with high indexes on the Mongolian Stock Exchange have been employed in this study. These top companies are identified by the Mongolian Stock Exchange every financial year.
Multimethod	This method combines archival and observational study, proposing a qualitative multimethod approach.
Data collection process	The data collection process is used to obtain access to the field site and applied to introduce the field site.
Data analysis methods	For archival research, qualitative content analysis is used to help the researcher apply various analysis methods for substantial documented information (Powers and Knapp, 2006). Accordingly, the weighted scoring model is used to capture considerable qualitative data. Another key characteristic of qualitative content analysis is that data can be analysed qualitatively despite its quantitative result (Gbrich, 2007). Accordingly, data observed in the weighted scoring model will be qualitatively analysed by theme. In contrast, the observational data have been analysed using grounded theory analysis.
Conduct of ethical principles	This study discusses four types of ethical principles: autonomy, beneficence, justice and inclusiveness.
Research validity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The internal validity of the research instruments was strengthened by justifying their use. • Construct validity can be observed in Chapter 4, illustrating how the analysed data transformed into an idea or concept and then into a functioning matter. • External validity is illustrated in the Conclusion chapter, where the researcher summarises the research and verifies whether the research objectives have been met within the target population.
Research reliability	This study has employed archival research and observation, which focuses on social practices formed by domestic institutions for nearly three decades. Thus, minor errors can potentially occur when replicating this study in the future. These errors have been discussed in detail above.

CHAPTER 4: DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Purpose of the Chapter

This chapter extensively focuses on demonstrating the data collected through the selected research methodologies. The chapter also reports these observed data by employing explicitly selected analysis techniques, which have been discussed in the Research Methodology chapter. The researcher has conducted the study based on the NCCG, the only professional organisation in the field of governance in Mongolia.

This study conducted archival research on the top 20 selected listed companies with high indexes on the Mongolian Stock Exchange. The required data for archival research were collected from the Mongolian Stock Exchange and Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission. These data have been analysed using a weighted scoring model. On the contrary, the qualitative grounded theory analysis method has been applied to observational data gathered through an observational study. Subsequently, the findings of the weighted scoring model have been cross-analysed with the findings from grounded theory analysis. Tables and graphs were used to organise, demonstrate and report the gathered data. The researcher will also provide all available evidence for the data collection process in the appendices.

4.2. Overview of the Weighted Scoring Model

The designed weighted scoring model comprises three main themes: transparency, shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, and BOD. They are broadly emphasised in company and security markets laws and corporate governance code as the main indicators of economic condition and directly influenced by domestic governance mechanisms. Corruption is pervasive across various structures and sectors. Thus, the themes of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, and BOD must be considered to examine the situation of the business environment for investors.

According to the observational data, the theme of transparency resulted in total average scores of 54.9 out of 64; the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting have produced total average score of 54.7 out of 60; whereas the theme of BOD have generated total average score of 65.6 out of 72-indicating 86%, 91% and 93% compliance rates respectively. Although these high compliance rates are in line with each other, these results seem to contradict the existing practice in Mongolia. A detailed primary analysis will be discussed below.

4.3. Primary Analysis of the Weighted Scoring Model: Theme of Transparency

The transparency section of the weighted scoring model demonstrates a total number of 16 listed criteria, with a criterion weight of 2% each. A score ranging between 4 and 0 has been distributed to the top 20 listed companies. The data used in this section were mainly collected from the website of the Mongolian Stock Exchange. Any further enquiries have been discussed with a representative from the governance team of the Mongolian Stock Exchange. Assured information was also obtained from the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission.

Table 7: Weighted Scoring Model: Transparency

No	Criteria	Category	Tavan Tolgoi	Gobi	APU	Talkh Chihar	Darhan Nohii	Suu	LendMn	Mongol Shuudaa	Mongol Baralt	Arif Insurance	Mandal Insurance	Gutal	Bi Di Sek	Max Impex	Arif Sanhuugiin Negdel	Ittools	Hi Bi Oil	Mik Holding	Huvsgul Altan Duulga	Jenko Tur Berent	Average Score	Weight	Weighted Score	Total Score
			60	55	51	57	56	55	58	51	51	64	59	57	55	45	51	55	47	58	58	54	54.9	32.7%	0.86	1.31
A1	Do you follow principle of transparency and open tendering when choosing company's board of directors and executive management?	The right to vote and to be elected	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	3	4	3	4	3	3.5	2%	0.07	
A2	Does board of directors set procedures to fully provide company information to shareholders and other interested regulatory authorities in timely manner?	Information disclosure	3	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	2	4	3	4	3.5	2%	0.07	
A3	Does company provide not only fulfil legal requirements but also business definition in accordance with international best practice, analysis of financial situation, performance results, change in asset, cash flow as well as risk and risk factor information disclosed in annual report?	Information disclosure	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	4	2	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3.4	2%	0.07	
A4	Does the company disclose information about events and mid-term results through its own website and through the related organization's website?	Information disclosure	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	2	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	3.7	2%	0.07	
A5	Does the company disclose information in a timely, accurate, unambiguous and complete manner as stated in company law and law of security market?	Information disclosure	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	3	3.7	2%	0.07	
A6	Does the company broadly disclose information about its management to the public?	Information disclosure	4	3	3	4	3	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3.3	2%	0.07	
A7	Does the financial statement include information about large-scale and conflict-of-interest?	Information disclosure	4	2	2	3	4	3	4	2	2	4	3	4	4	3	2	3	3	4	4	4	3.2	2%	0.07	
A8	Does the company broadly disclose information about shareholders to public?	Information disclosure	3	2	3	3	3	4	3	3	1	4	4	4	3	3	3	2	3	4	3	4	3.1	2%	0.06	
A9	Does the company disclose information about dividend policy to public?	Information disclosure	4	2	3	3	3	2	4	2	4	4	4	4	3	3	2	3	4	3	4	3	3.2	2%	0.07	
A10	Does the company provide information about amount of dividend paid to shareholders, its form, time and cause when it does not distribute the dividends to public?	Information disclosure	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	2	4	4	4	4	3	3	2	4	3	4	4	3	3.4	2%	0.07	
A11	Does the company provide information about termination of contract with suppliers and buyers which affects 20% or more sales revenue to public?	Information disclosure	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	3	3	4	3	2	4	2	3	4	2	4	4	2	3.3	2%	0.07	
A12	Are public provided with information about the property worth more than 10% or more of the value of a company being sold, pledged or transferred in any form and preserved?	Information disclosure	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	2	4	3	3	3	2	4	3	1	3	3	3	3.2	2%	0.06	
A13	Are public provided with information about decision to issue additional shares or securities?	Information disclosure	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	2	4	4	3	4	4	3	3.6	2%	0.07	
A14	Does the company provide information about any decisions that affect issued securities released by organisation's board of directors to public?	Information disclosure	3	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	2	4	4	3	3	3	4	3.5	2%	0.07	
A15	Is the announcement of regular shareholders' meeting submitted to the Financial Regulatory Commission, Mongolian Stock Exchange and shareholders on time?	Information disclosure	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.0	2%	0.08	
A16	Does relevant policy involve disclosure of information to public when external auditors are involved?	Information disclosure	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	2	4	3	4	3.6	2%	0.07	

Table 7 demonstrates that A15 (announcement of regular shareholder meeting submitted to the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission, Mongolian Stock Exchange and shareholders) indicates the highest score of 4 in a majority of the companies, and produced the highest average score of 4. Multiplied by the criterion weight of 2%, A15 generates the highest criterion weighted score of 0.08. Thus, this criterion is exceptionally complied with by most companies. Similar calculations have been applied across all criteria. Criteria A4 and A5 result in the second-highest average score of 3.7, followed by criteria A13 and A16 indicating the third-highest average score of 3.6, whereas criteria A1, A2 and A14 present the fourth-highest average score of 3.5 with a weighted score of 0.07.

Criteria A8 (The company should broadly disclose information about shareholders to the public) has scored the lowest average score of 3.1 with a weighted score of 0.06, followed by criteria A7, A9 and A12 with the second-lowest average score of 3.2 and a weighted score of 0.07 and 0.06, respectively. Criteria A6 and A11 show the third-lowest average score of 3.3 with a weighted score of 0.07. Criteria A3 and A10 result in the fourth-lowest average score of 3.4 with a weighted score of 0.07. Although these criteria ranked as the lowest in the weighted scoring model, the overall average score illustrates that they comply with the governance regulatory environment.

Overall, the compliance of transparency-relevant laws and regulations in the governance regulatory environment has resulted in a total average score of 54.9 out of 64, indicating an 86% compliance rate. Therefore, transparency-relevant laws and regulations in the governance regulatory environment are exceptionally complied with in the Mongolian institutional environment.

4.4. Primary Analysis of the Weighted Scoring Model: Theme of Shareholder Rights and Shareholders' Meeting

The second theme of the weighted scoring model is the shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, with 15 criteria. Table 8 below lists each criterion stating the fundamental rights of shareholders, scored between 4 and 0.

Table 8: Weighted Scoring Model: Shareholder Rights and Shareholders' Meeting

Criteria	Category	Tavan Tolgoi	Gobi	APU	Talkh Chiher	Darhan Nehii	Suu	LendMn	Mongol Shuudan	Mongol Bazalt	Ard Insurance	Mandal Insurance	Gutal	Bi Di Sek	Max Impex	Ard Sanhuugiin Negdel	Itools	Hi Bi Oil	Mik Holding	Huvsgul Altan Duulga	Jenko Tur Bereau	Average Score	Weight	Weighted Score	Total Score	
		53	59	50	52	53	53	59	52	58	60	57	57	55	53	52	56	48	55	55	53	54.7	30.6%	0.91	1.22	
No Shareholder Rights and Shareholders' Meeting	Category	53	59	50	52	53	53	59	52	58	60	57	57	55	53	52	56	48	55	55	53	54.7	30.6%	0.91	1.22	
B1	Are conditions provided to shareholders to participate in important decision making regarding operation of the company?	Right to participate in the shareholders meeting / voting rights	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	3.9	2.0%	0.08		
B2	Does the company provide conditions to its shareholders to exercise their rights to obtain information about company's operation?	Right to obtain information	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	3.8	2.0%	0.08	
B3	Does the company provide information relevant to annual report, financial situation, risks and company's operation to shareholders in a timely manner ?	Right to obtain information	4	4	3	3	3	3	4	3	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	3	0	4	4	3	3.2	2.0%	0.07	
B4	Do existing shareholders have access to financial accounting reports?	Dividend rights	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.7	2.0%	0.08	
B5	Does the company enable its shareholders to exercise their right to monitor company's large-size and conflict-of-interest transactions?	The right to demand investigation of the company's operations	3	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3.5	2.0%	0.07	
B6	Is there a condition for the company to liquidate the share of the remaining assets when the company is closed?	Dividend rights	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	3.8	2.0%	0.08	
B7	Is there a system to communicate information to shareholders in a timely manner regarding details of candidate to board of directors?	The right to vote and to be elected	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4.0	2.0%	0.08	
B8	According to company law, are shareholders entitled to demand to repurchase back their shares if they are disagreeing to decision made or were absent when the decision made at the shareholders' meeting?	Rights to demand redemption of shares	3	4	2	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	3	3.5	2.0%	0.07		
B9	Is the shareholder holding 10% or more of the company's total shares eligible to request auditing through internal and external auditors?	The right to demand investigation of the company's operations	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	1	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	3.7	2.0%	0.07	
B10	Are there conditions provided to deliver shareholders' meeting material in an appropriate manner and which enables to review discussion of meeting prior the meeting?	Shareholder rights at the meeting	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	3	3.7	2.0%	0.08	
B11	Are incentives given to the company's management team been reported to shareholders?	Right to obtain information	3	3	3	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	3.6	2.0%	0.07	
B12	Is there voting for every issue discussed at the shareholders' meeting?	Decision of shareholders' meeting		4	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3.7	2.0%	0.08		
B13	Is recording of shareholders' meeting released within required timeframe stated in law and confirmed with signature and a stamp of chairman of meeting?	Meeting rules of shareholders and notes of meeting	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	3.7	2.0%	0.08	
B14	Is there condition provided to introduce decisions resulted from shareholders' meeting?	Meeting rules of shareholders	4	4	3	3	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	3	3.6	2.0%	0.07	
B15	Does the relevant procedure involve alternative voting option in case the shareholder would not able attend shareholders' meeting?	Meeting rules of shareholders	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	2	4	4	4	4	3	4	2	4	4	3	3	4	3.5	2.0%	0.07	

The collected information shows that the criterion B7 (A system is used to communicate information about candidates to the BOD to shareholders on time) scored the highest average score of 4.0 across the top 20 companies and with the highest weighted score of 0.08; followed by the criterion B1 (Conditions are provided for shareholders to participate in important decision-making regarding company operations) has the second-highest average score of 3.9; accompanied by the criterion B2 and B6 with the third-highest average score of 3.8 respectively. The criteria B4, B9, B10, B12 and B13 have the fourth-highest average score of 3.7 with a weighted score of 0.08.

The criterion B3 (The company provides information relevant to the annual report, financial situation, risks and company operations to shareholders on time) has the lowest average score of 3.2 across the top 20 listed companies with a weighted score of 0.07; pursued by criteria B5, B8 and B15 with the second-lowest average score of 3.5; whereas criteria B11 and B14 have the third-lowest average score of 3.6 with a weighted score of 0.07 correspondingly.

The calculated average score across all criteria for the top 20 listed companies demonstrate that majority of the criteria have resulted in a reasonably higher average score with a considerably consistent weighted score. The total average score is 54.7 out of 60 with a 91% compliance performance rate. Therefore, the top 20 selected listed companies with high indexes respectfully to exceptionally comply with the fundamental rights of shareholders.

4.5. Primary Analysis of the Weighted Scoring Model: Theme of Board of Directors

The third theme of BOD in the weighted scoring model 18 criteria with a criterion weight of 2%. Each criterion has scored between 4 and 0 across the top 20 listed companies with high indexes in the Mongolian Stock Exchange (2019). Table 9 below presents the observational data of the top 20 listed companies.

Table 9: Weighted Scoring Model: Board of Directors

Criteria		Tavan Tolgoi	Gobi	APU	Talkh Chiher	Darhan Nehii	Suu	LendMn	Mongol Shuudaa	Mongol Bazalt	Ard Insurance	Mandal Insurance	Gutal	Bi Di Sek	Max Impex	Negdel	Itools	Hi Bi Oil	Mik Holding	Huygul Altan Duulga	Jenko Tur Bereau	Average Score	Weight	Weighted Score	Total Score	
No	Board of Directors (BOD)	66	67	54	69	66	65	70	70	68	68	58	69	62	68	70	63	59	67	69	63	65.6	36.7%	0.93	1.47	
C1	Are there any regulations governing the Board operation?	Operational rules of the BOD	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4.0	2%	0.08	
C2	Is there regulation governing election of chairman not from members of executive management?	Chairman election	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	0	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.7	2%	0.07	
C3	Is there a sufficient number of independent members of the board?	Members of the board of directors	4	4	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	2	4	4	3	3	3.6	2%	0.07		
C4	Does the company policy state that the board of directors have the responsibility to personally participate in the shareholders' meeting and answer the questions of shareholders?	Role of board of directors	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	1	4	3	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	3.5	2%	0.07		
C5	Is there a professional compensation and nomination committee at the board of directors?	Board committee	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	3.9	2%	0.08		
C6	Is there an internal audit committee to increase the efficiency of corporate governance?	Board committee	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	3.8	2%	0.08		
C7	Does the company have a risk management committee?	Board committee	4	2	2	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	2	4	4	3	3	4	3	3	3.4	2%	0.07		
C8	Whether the audit, the compensation and the nomination committee are independent members	Board committee	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.9	2%	0.08		
C9	Does the compensation committee have incentive policy for board members and executive management and authorized officials?	Board committee	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3.9	2%	0.08		
C10	Can the fair amount of incentive be set for performance of each members of board of directors after the completion of the reporting year?	Board committee	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	3	4	3	3	4	4	3	3.6	2%	0.07		
C11	Is the salary and incentive system for the executive management conform to the interests of the shareholders?	Board committee	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	2	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	3	3.6	2%	0.07		
C12	Is the activity of nominating and selecting candidate to board of directors according to the rules to be transparent in a way of open announcement?	Board committee	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	3.7	2%	0.07		
C13	Is there a policy to regulate the selection of an independent auditor?	External auditor	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	3.7	2%	0.08		
C14	Does the selection of the independent auditor have been disclosed to the shareholders' meeting to confirm its independence?	External auditor	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	3	4	4	3.6	2%	0.07		
C15	Does the board of directors conduct integrated activities to provide risk management to all internal and external operational risk, finance and law enforcement, and other potential risks?	Risk management	3	2	3	3	3	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3.6	2%	0.07		
C16	Does the board ensure that the company will be responsible for identifying, evaluating, and determining the risks involved, and are responsible for mitigating and responding to these risks?	Risk management	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	4	2	4	4	3	3	4	4	3	4	2	3.5	2%	0.07		
C17	Does the board committee produce reports?	Board committee	4	4	2	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	1	2	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	3.5	2%	0.07		
C18	Does the Board comply with code of ethics?	Ethics of board of directors	3	4	2	4	4	3	2	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	3.5	2%	0.07		

Table 9 above shows that the criterion C1 (regulations governing the BOD's operation) marks the highest average score of 4.0 among the top 20 companies with the highest weighted score of 0.08. Criteria C5, C8 and C9 have the second-highest average score of 3.9 with a weighted score of 0.08; accompanied by criteria C2, C12 and C13 with the third-highest average score of 3.7 and a weighted score of 0.07, 0.07 and 0.08 respectively.

In contrast, the criterion C7 (the company should have a risk management committee) shows the lowest average score of 3.4 across the 20 companies with a weighted score of 0.07, pursued by criteria C4, C16, C17 and C17 with the second-lowest average score of 3.5 and a weighted score of 0.07. Subsequently, criteria C3, C10, C11, C14 and C15 have the third-lowest average score of 3.6 with a weighted score of 0.07. Consequently, the theme of BOD has resulted in a total average score of 65.6 out of 72, indicating a 93% compliance rate. It can be interpreted that the regulations governing BOD exceptionally complied with the governance regulatory environment, similar to the previous theme of transparency, as well as, shareholder rights shareholders' meeting.

4.6. Secondary Analysis between the Themes

The first theme of transparency has resulted in an overall average score of 54.9 out of 64, indicating a high compliance rate of 86%. The second theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting has presented a total average score of 54.7 out of 60, indicating a compliance rate of 91%. Great respect for shareholder rights is ensured through adequate transparency and accountability practice. Accordingly, this high compliance rate resulted from shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, which is in line with the high compliance rate of the theme transparency. However, capital markets, stock markets, insurance and derivative financing could have been developed, if respect to shareholder rights is greatly acknowledged. The development of markets could be driven by greater investment amounts than large personal savings in commercial banks that loan the money to businesses at high interest rates.

Lastly, the theme of BOD has resulted in a total average score of 65.6 out of 72, indicating a 93% compliance rate with governance-relevant laws and regulations concerning the BOD structure. This high compliance rate is consistent with the high rates of the theme: transparency, as well as, the theme: shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting.

4.7. Grounded Theory Analysis

The field observation in this study was explained and coded into six initial categories. These defined categories are then engaged in steady comparison during habitually so-called axial (Strauss & Corbin, 1998) or reflective (McCaslin & Scott, 2003) coding and selective coding. Steadily comparing the defined categories assists the researcher in understanding the formation of interrelationships. A conditional interrelationship guide is a method for discovering patterns and interrelationships between the defined categories that contextualise a core phenomenon. Subsequently, an introspective coding matrix can be constructed from the established guide. This matrix will help the researcher in developing a theory following the explicit illustration in the conditional matrix.

4.7.1. Open Coding

Open coding is the initial step of grounded theory analysis. At this stage, the researcher breaks observational data into distinct categories and generate “codes” to identify them. As its term would entail, open coding is intended to relief the researcher to original theoretical opportunities, as the researcher initially engage with collected observational data. The goal of categorising observational data and identifying them with codes is to allow the researcher to constantly compare and contrast related occurrences in the gathered observational data. In order to do this, the researcher describes all fragments of data or observational data and label them with specific code. For instance, Table 10 illustrates three columns: description, possessions and category. The description section shows detailed observational data; the possessions section presents list of relevant concepts; and the category section displays the label. Accordingly, in relation to first description of observational data, the relevant concepts in the possessions section are defined as unstandardized format of information, missing audit and risk-relevant information, lack of reinforcement mechanism, and untimely manner. All these concepts are coded or labelled as ineffective communication. By doing so, the process enforces the researcher out of predetermined beliefs and biases in association with her own research study. Open coding is the fundamental stage of coding and is accompanied by axial or reflective coding.

Table 10: Open Coding

Description	Possessions	Category
<p>Field observation 1: When gathering the required data for the listed criteria under the theme of transparency, reading and finding the necessary information from annual company performance reports and shareholders’ meeting notice was time-consuming, unstandardized and sometimes does not generate any data. The reports had various content, some of which were irrelevant, and certain necessary information was missing for the majority of the companies such as audit reports and risk management reports. As reported by a representative from the Mongolian Stock Exchange, listed companies are encouraged to provide audit reports since 2019. However, these reports were only voluntary, not compulsory. Moreover, the main institutions lack reinforcement towards companies’ governance on how the reports should be produced and what information should be included. The announcement of shareholders’ meetings was also unreasonably close to the meeting date or published after the date.</p>	<p>Unstandardized format of information Missing audit and risk-relevant information Lack of reinforcement mechanism Untimely manner</p>	<p>Ineffective communication</p>
<p>Field observation 2: A review was conducted on the top 20 companies’ annual performance reports and shareholders’ meeting notes from the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission to obtain the required data for the listed criteria under the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders’ meeting and BOD. However, governance-relevant laws and regulations were only formulated rather than demonstrated and implemented in business activities. Also, audit and risk management exhibited insufficient information.</p>	<p>Compliance only Insufficient information about audit and risk management</p>	<p>Failure of the rule of law</p>
<p>Field observation 3: The criteria of the weighted scoring model were listed based on the review of company and security market laws and corporate governance code. Accordingly, scarce legal provisions for other stakeholders, particularly customers, suppliers and employees, were identified. None of the archived official documents has mentioned these stakeholders. Rather, they focus on the establishment of the company, main shareholders, the BOD, mission, vision, main operation, profit/loss and statement of objectives for the upcoming year. These stakeholders are overlooked in the governance regulatory environment.</p>	<p>Weak judiciary system Exclusiveness of stakeholders</p>	<p>Abandoned stakeholders</p>
<p>Field observation 4: The companies do not practice good governance codes. Although the corporate governance code was launched in 2007 (Yener, 2008), the institutional environment still exhibits significant challenges. For instance, the code requires comply or explain system because certain codes are mandatory policies, whereas others are voluntary. However, the mandatory regulations and policies are only formulated without implementation and practice.</p>	<p>Absence of implementation and practice</p>	<p>Defenceless governance regime</p>
<p>Field observation 5: The researcher attended a training course organised by the NCCG to enhance public knowledge of good governance. Since the emergence of good governance issues, an effective decision-making process, controlling power, the participation of the public, cooperation, doing good for society, compliance with the rule of law and investment in a market economy among others were expected. However, the training gives additional information about a different class of shares, shareholder rights in decision-making based on the number of shares held in the company and regulatory environment.</p>	<p>Inadequate information and knowledge</p>	<p>Lack of knowledge and awareness of reality</p>

Description	Possessions	Category
<p>Field observation 6: The market is dominated by a few giants depending on the sector. For instance, the mining, cashmere, beverage and meat production industries have a few domestic competitors. However, the fashion, retail, hospitality, travel and other industries have hardly any competitors both locally and internationally.</p>	<p>Crowding in profitable industries</p> <p>Underdevelopment of various sectors</p> <p>Absence of competitors</p>	<p>Concentration of controlling power</p>

4.7.2. Conditional Interrelationship Guide

The conditional interrelationship guide presented in Table 11 below presents a comparison of the above-defined categories during open coding by reflectively answering questions of what, where, when, why and how alongside the consequences (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). By doing so enables to define patterns or interrelationships between various concepts and categories previously examined in the open coding. For instance, starting with the category of ineffective communication: What is ineffective communication? Ineffective communication is defined as the indirect format of information and avoidance of necessary information. This definition is based on collective field observation of practices.

The second relational question states: When does ineffective communication arise? Ineffective communication arises during an observer's pursuits. The third comparative question states: Where does ineffective communication arise? Ineffective communication arises in practices in institutional environment and the stages of pursuit. The subsequent question probed states: Why does ineffective communication arise? Certain behaviours delayed or prevented the attainment of accessible though possibly unrecognised information. Thus, answering when, where and why questions emphasise the conditions and structures. The fifth designed asking question states how to initiate interactions and actions between the categories or make sense of the dynamic practices over a long period. Moreover, the question enables deeper investigation to understand potential consequences. Ineffective communication arises due to unstandardized information format; absence of audit- and risk-relevant information; risk of data control and mismanagement; absence of surveillance; and risk of manipulating balance sheet. The final question on the conditional interrelationship guide states: With what hypothetical consequence is communication ineffective, or with what hypothetical consequence does ineffective communication arise? The conceivable consequence in this study was public experience of practice and implementation level. Hence, individuals' experience, in this situation, are occurred purposefully through their actions. The consequence of exercising ineffective communication is a constrain to cooperation. This defined category under the 'consequences' column becomes the key category to examine further connections and relationships with other identified categories.

Following this process, the designed conditional interrelationship guide transmits structure to process. The consequences resulting from the guide will further outline the central phenomenon in the introspective coding matrix presented in Table 12. In addition to the consequences, the remaining categories on the guide tend to be measurements on the introspective coding matrix. Thus, the ground theory-building process involves verification (Denzin & Lincoln, 2017) of the resulting relationships within observational data in different forms.

Table 11: Conditional Interrelationship Guide

Category	What	When	Where	Why	How	Consequences
Ineffective communication	Indirect style of information and avoidance of necessary information	During pursuit	In the stages of the pursuit	Because certain behaviours delayed or prevented the attainment of accessible though possibly unrecognised information	Supplying unstandardized information format Avoiding provision of audit- and risk-relevant information Risk of data control and mismanagement Absence of surveillance and risk of manipulating balance sheet	Cooperation
Failure of the rule of law	Economic hardship caused by disintegration of expectations and destabilised enterprises	Throughout democracy During pursuit	In lifestyle In practice and implementation In cooperation	Because principles of clarity, stability, generality, publicity and prosperity of the institutional norms that administer a society are inexistent	Corruption level Unemployment level Inequality and poverty Standard of Living Abuse of human rights	Inclusiveness
Abandoned stakeholders	Instability of democracy driven by internal (civil society's discouragement of solidarity, public liveliness, trust and cooperation) and external factors (disassociated interests misrepresent government transparency and accountability practices to its residents)	Throughout democracy During pursuit	In the civil society In an institutional environment In practice and implementation In cooperation	Because of the presence of corruption, exclusiveness, inequality, deteriorated legitimacy and distrust, disrespect to human rights due to non-transparent negotiation and insufficient accountability	Inconsideration and exclusiveness Unemployment level Minimal state support or nothing Alcohol addiction Crime level	Inclusiveness

Defenceless governance regime	Structural form only without significance, rules only without practice and compliance only without implementation	During pursuit	In the stages of the pursuit	Because of the concentration of internal controlling power which circumvents audit and risk management, recruits own people who are inappropriately qualified to be a committee member of and assembling misrepresentation; negligence from governors, regulators, analysts and auditors	Lack of reinforcement Absence of implementation and practice Confusion Corruption level Lack of transparency and accountability	Cooperation
Lack of knowledge and awareness of reality	Confusion underpinned by non-transparency and insufficient accountability	Throughout democracy During pursuit	In civil society In an institutional environment	Because non-transparency and insufficient accountability leads to public distrust, disunity and disengagement to the government decision-making process of development	Lack of transparency and insufficient accountability Distrust and disengagement	Controlling power
Concentration of controlling power	Excessive controlling power on the government rather than on national and regional governance	Throughout the market economy During pursuit	In public officials In an institutional environment In government agencies In administrative service providers In wealthy individuals	Because non-transparency and insufficient accountability promotes patron–client relationships while not only weakening the judiciary system but also destroying public trust, solidarity and participation	Corruption level Business owners’ avoidance of their statutory duties Growing social issues caused by corrupt officials Individuals’ impact on court decisions for personal benefits Business owners’ enhancement of their relationship to gain market dominance	Controlling power

Table 12: Introspective Coding Matrix

Underlying Category	Promoting Transparency and Accountability Initiatives				
Possessions	Process	Position	Procedure	Product	Purpose
Practices	Cooperation	Controlling power	Inclusiveness	Accomplishment	Sustainable development
Measurements	Standardised information format Provide audit- and risk-relevant information Information autonomy Performance indicators Implementation and practice Reinforcement Transparency and accountability Understandability and certainty	Transparency and accountability Enforcing business owners to exercise their statutory duties Anti-corruption Independent judiciary system Proposing an appropriate policy Rule of law	Transparency and accountability Unemployment level Inequality and poverty Public services Standard of living Public backing Human rights State support Crime level Social care	Awareness and understanding of reality Transparency and accountability Learning from sources Encouraging public participation Where to start to combat How to start to combat Strategies Setting measures Consistent oversight Reinforcing implementation and practice	Transparency and accountability Consistent encouragement of initiatives Positive influence Minor shareholder's protection Judiciary system Sense of 'me' matters Communicating standpoint Compelling desires Convenient economic condition
Contexts	Challenges	Judgement	Values	Vision	Meaning in vision
Means for tolerating the consequences	Momentum in governance	Public participation	Good governance	Progressive recognition of vision	Establishing good governance practices, impacts on corruption and sustainable development.

4.7.3. Introspective Coding Matrix

The conditional interrelationship guide not only recognises the interactions and relationships between the categories, but also explains how the consequences of every category. This step will be the main focus of this stage of data analysis. The rise of these means and possessions of comprehending the consequences is a pointer to achieve hypothetical saturation (Glaser, 1978). The introspective coding matrix in Table 12 above is the approach to create the storyline of the various patterns revealed in the conditional interrelationship guide.

A central objective of creating an introspective coding matrix is to contextualise the underlying category, namely the integral phenomenon that relates to the remaining significant and insignificant categories. When an underlying category is defined, the remaining categories are converted to sub-categories. These sub-categories in the introspective coding matrix become the category headings: possessions, practices, measurements, contexts and means for tolerating the consequences. The approach to recognising the headings in the introspective coding matrix depends on the interactions and relationships revealed in the conditional interrelationship guide.

Firstly, the conditional interrelationship guide recognised the consequences as the main categories in which the remaining categories are directed. Therefore, all remaining categories not presented in the category of consequences or showed only once are held aside temporarily to perform the consequences. In this study of an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in the case of Mongolia, the categories of consequences are cooperation, controlling power, inclusiveness, accomplishment, development, promotion, transparency and accountability initiatives and vision. These classifications became the descriptors in the introspective coding matrix.

The matrix is created to construct an underlying category to determine and characterise it and thus sufficiently account for the entire collected data. The main objective is to address the primary phenomenon of the study. In the developed introspective coding matrix, the descriptors that outline and contextualise the underlying categories are possessions, practices, measurements, contexts and means for tolerating consequences. The approach is stepping back to shape a general constructivist view.

At this stage, certain relationships are likely to be recognised for the introspective coding matrix and can be relocated in the suitable descriptor types, which is more reasonable. The set on the side sub-categories is likely to become the dimensions in an appropriate column. Then, blocks for alternative descriptors on the introspective coding matrix are created; potential practices will be determined surrounding the general (consequences) categories. In this study of an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in the case of Mongolia, eight categories were determined as potential practices: cooperation, controlling power, inclusiveness, promotion, transparency and accountability initiatives, execution and accomplishment, progressive understanding of meaningful vision and good governance. In the introspective coding matrix, five practices were determined: cooperation, controlling power, inclusiveness, accomplishment and development. After determining the practices, the main temporary categories were identified across the same key categories under the contexts. If the main temporary categories were not determined, then any of the

consequences categories under the contexts could have been questioned. Therefore, the main temporary categories must be determined when the groupings have been finalised.

Subsequently, determining which of the main categories are the means for tolerating the consequences of the underlying category was essential. Then, the possessions were identified as they serve as links and are more speculative than being categories. Reviewing and reflecting on the entire study through the question (What could be potential possessions?) may generate execution and accomplishment, process cooperation and other practices, enable controlling power, give rise to a lack of transparency and insufficient accountability and corruption and result in inclusiveness, inequality and poverty, public services and abuse of human rights were speculated.

At this phase of analysis, the underlying category can be predicted. In this study, promoting transparency and accountability initiatives were proposed and revisited to available data to probe: What do we know about transparency and accountability initiatives in this study? Firstly, the core criteria of establishing effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development have to be met by promoting transparency and accountability initiatives. If core the criteria are met, then insistence is not a problem because integration is a pull, not a push. Promotion raises the level of participation, initiatives, contributions and meaning in goal, upholding public participation the transparent and accountable system may uphold. The public can enforce greater transparency and sufficient accountability to meet sufficient core criteria to cause integration and inclusiveness at the recognition level and value in the institutional environment. Recognition is central to promoting transparency and accountability initiatives. Accordingly, promoting transparency and accountability initiatives is a satisfactory underlying category in this study and located in the suitable block in the introspective coding matrix.

After identifying the underlying category, other potential categories are placed in an appropriate block to provide a strong ground for its reliability and verify that each block sufficiently approves the underlying category and that it fits within the observed data. This repetitive process constantly incorporates open coding and the available data and literature to categorise and validate relevance and adequacy.

Based on Table 12, the underlying category of this study is ultimately becoming more sophisticated as promoting transparency and accountability initiatives. Momentum in governance, which describes how the public tolerates consequences of cooperation, was challenging to establish. This analytical sharpness has supported the researcher to move to the following and final stage of selective coding of the interpretive process of grounded theory. The selective coding process focuses on integrating, explaining and refining the emerging theoretical framework (Strauss & Corbin, 1998; McCaslin & Scott, 2003). Accordingly, creating a storyline and explaining the development of the theoretical framework is necessary.

4.7.4. Explanation and Theory

Selective coding is the final phase of the interpretive process of grounded theory, which focuses on integrating all the explanatory effort of the analysis. This selective coding is analogous to reflective coding, though it is handled at a greater level of conceptualisation (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Selective coding aims to interpret the storyline. In the case of this study, selective coding intends to produce a storyline that determines the underlying phenomena of promoting transparency and accountability initiatives. The initial research question of this study states: What are

the ways to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia? One of the developing economies with a weak institutional environment, poor judiciary system and pervasive corruption. This question has been developed to: What are the potential approaches for promoting transparency and accountability initiatives in Mongolia? Furthermore, the question of: How does such initiative proceed, among what adaptabilities and what are the impacts on the macro and the micro-environment from the principle and system perspectives? Requires writing a storyline or a comprehensive descriptive outline. Subsequently, this outline must be verified with the findings from content analysis through cross-analysis, and discussion of the findings relevant to the literature review. The storyline is discussed below based on the introspective coding matrix in Table 12, from left to right direction.

4.7.5. Formation of Storyline

The final process of selective coding requires integrating relevant phenomena to the underlying category. The possessions and measurements of the underlying category are solidly developed at this stage of analysis. Patterns of possessions and measurements of related concepts, categories and phenomena are interrelated in the introspective coding matrix. The storyline of this study of an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in the case of Mongolia has emphasised five necessary processes: cooperation, controlling power, inclusiveness, accomplishment and development. Development is expected to happen through these processes in pursuit of promoting transparency and accountability initiatives.

Starting with the process of cooperation on the far-left, the contexts have been determined challenges in which the development can happen. The means for tolerating consequences have been identified as momentum in governance. The measurements have also been determined as setting the standardised information format; requesting to provide audit- and risk-relevant information; requesting information autonomy without manipulating financial statement and audit reports; demanding performance indicators, such as year-over-year company performance; focusing on the implementation and practice of legal provisions; reinforcing the practice of good; understanding the situation; creating certainty; and practicing the principle of transparency and accountability. These measurements have been demonstrated in the introspective coding matrix in Table 12 above. Within a storyline, people need to cooperate to start a challenging activity. Each measurement illustrates that difficulties are part of the development. Businesses are requested to adopt the prerequisites of each challenge, focus on its importance and appreciate the momentum in governance. The process of tackling these challenges in cooperation has a corresponding influence on decentralising the controlling power. Enforcing transparency and accountability enables business owners to exercise their statutory duties, combat corruption, fight for an independent judiciary system, propose an appropriate policy regardless of self-interest and enforce the rule of law.

Practicing transparency and accountability opens truth to the civil society, makes their judgement and provides normative layouts of isomorphic institutional pressure to institutional entities to do their job right. This controlling power is foundational to promoting principle initiatives. Public inclusiveness systems are essential to values and held open to likelihood. The standard of living, human rights, state support and social care are the motives in an

effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. However, unemployment, inequality and poverty, poor public services and crimes are the causes for urgency. Good governance in connection with values stimulates to consider existing phenomena. The accomplishment of a set of goals is a progressive recognition of a meaningful vision. People will make sense of the matters by understanding reality, promoting transparency and accountability, learning from sources, maintaining consistent oversight, reinforcing implementation and practice and positively influencing the establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development through their initiatives and participation, though only secondary in their mind. It cannot occur without transparency and accountability as it enables people to make appropriate judgement. Establishing good governance significantly impacts sustainable development through transparency and accountability, consistent encouragement of initiatives, positive influence, an independent judiciary system, communicating standpoint, compelling desires and creation of a convenient economic condition.

A new theoretical framework is developed using this storyline as navigation, going backwards to weave a story at a greater version of abstraction and incorporating structure and practice in a specific statement. The study of an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia has developed a theoretical framework of integrity restoration (Figure 4) as a long-term solution by considering relevance and values in promoting transparency and accountability initiatives.

Thus, the process enables specificity in the emerging theoretical framework. Here, the study specificity yielded particular conditions in which the establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development will occur under how it evolved throughout the logical process demonstration of grounded theory. Considering data reliability, transmission and perseverance, the emerging theoretical framework will be cross-analysed with content analysis below. Results will be discussed in the following chapter. Consequently, the dependability of the storyline and the development of the theoretical framework are reliable.

Figure 4: Integrity Restoration Framework

4.8. Cross-Analysis between Content Analysis and Grounded Theory Analysis

The content analysis examined the theme of transparency, shareholder rights and shareholders’ meeting, and BOD to determine the degree to which companies practice governance-relevant laws and regulations. The three themes have a total average score of 54.9 out of 64, 54.7 out of 60 and 65.6 out of 72, indicating compliance rates 86%, 91% and 93% respectively. All results show that companies exceptionally comply with the governance of relevant laws and regulations.

However, although the theme of transparency resulted in a high compliance rate, certain criteria in the theme are overrated, such as criterion A1: Does the company follow the principle of transparency and open tendering when choosing the company’s BOD and executive management? On the archived administrative documents, if a company has pointed out that the company follows the principle of transparency and open tendering when choosing the BOD and executive management, in this case, the criterion is scored 2, which is a moderate score. The range of scores slightly varies depending on the depth of practical information. However, in practice, the company’s BOD and executive management consist of siblings, relatives or close friends. Criterion A2 states: Does the BOD set procedures to completely provide company information to shareholders and other interested regulatory

authorities promptly? Criterion A5 states: Does the company disclose information in a timely, accurate, unambiguous and complete manner as stated in the company and security market laws? As mentioned previously, the majority of information on the theme of transparency is gathered from the Mongolian Stock Exchange website. An examination of information had revealed that the shareholders' meetings were announced 2 or 3 days before the meeting date or after the meeting date.

Criterion A3 states: Does the company fulfil not only the legal requirements, but also the definition of business according to international best practices, financial situation analysis, performance results, changes in assets, cash flow, and risk and risk factor information disclosed in an annual report? When reviewing an annual report from the Mongolian Stock Exchange website, the analysis of the financial situation, and risk and risk factor information was insufficiently disclosed for all the top 20 listed companies. Criterion A6 states: Does the company broadly disclose information about management to the public? The provided information was brief instead of broadly disclosed information. Furthermore, the literature has emphasised that transparency and accountability are the key to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development to maintain and boost the dynamic relationship between various participants with distinctive backgrounds (Husted & Folger, 2004). In contrast, when transparency is absent and accountability is insufficient, corruption spreads, income distribution worsens, inclusiveness narrows, participation deteriorates, controlling power is concentrated, public trust lowers and doubts upsurge among others.

In the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, criterion B3 states: Does the company promptly provide shareholders with information relevant to an annual report, financial situation, risks, and company operation? A review of the archived documents has revealed that certain companies had provided their reports on time, though few of them had provided the reports late, and that risk-relevant information was missing for all the top 20 companies. Therefore, criterion B3 is overrated practically and contradicts the overall result despite the fact that it has been mentioned in the archived documents. An appropriate score is required based on information rather than observation because the scoring is based on archived documents. Furthermore, great respect for shareholder rights is ensured through the adequate practice of transparency. However, the theme of transparency has previously revealed that specific criteria were not exercised, and the resulted high compliance rate contradicts reality. This finding could possibly influence the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting.

Similarly, certain criteria in the theme of BOD are not exercised. For instance, the third-highest scored criterion C6 (There should be an internal audit committee to increase corporate governance efficiency) is overrated as it contradicts the existing situation. As an assumption, if the company has an internal audit committee to improve the governance efficiency, then it would have solid audit reporting, great transparency, strong accountability and improved governance practice. Publicly listed companies on the Mongolian Stock Exchange do not provide audit reports along with other annual financial reports. Audit reports are only suggested to listed companies since 2019 but are not a mandatory requirement neither by the Mongolian Stock Exchange nor the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Environment. As reported by Criado-jime et al. (2008), voluntary reporting requirements do not meet

the needs of stakeholders. Therefore, compulsory audit reporting at the end of a financial year is an effective approach to strengthening accountability alongside transparency.

The following criteria are also believed to be overrated, though they indicate the lowest average scores: C7 (The company should have a risk management committee); C15 (The BOD should conduct integrated activities to provide risk management to all internal and external operational risks, finance, law enforcement and other potential risks); and C16 (The BOD should ensure that the company will take responsibility in identifying, evaluating and determining the risks involved and in mitigating and responding to these risks). As revealed previously in the theme of shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, the criteria or policies and regulations have been replicated only, but not applied in practice. These criteria raise the questions of: who are the members in the risk management committee? and How does the committee operate within the company? On the contrary, if the company has a risk management committee, it would have a risk assessment to a certain extent. However, a review of the documents of the 20 companies revealed that not more than 2 or 3 companies have mentioned risks in their annual performance reports, indicating the absence of risk assessment in all the companies. Risk assessment is necessary for the discussion of situations and issues affecting an organisation's operations, prospects, financial situation and performance. Thus, the high compliance rate contradicts the existing corporate governance practice.

In sum, governance-relevant rules and regulations are only structural forms without significance, only rules without practice and only compliance without implementation. Institutional entities have not established enforcement mechanisms to exercise these legal provisions in practice. Businesses also lack sufficient guidelines on how to exercise these rules and regulations. Moreover, penalties were not imposed on those who do not exercise the governance-relevant rules and regulations.

The practice of transparency is the key to ensure respect for shareholder rights and effectively form a BOD. With the pursuit of transparency practices, civil society can enforce and monitor implementations and practices of laws and regulations. As a result, normative layouts of isomorphic institutional pressure are created for companies to effectively form a BOD that meets different stakeholder needs. Thus, transparency practice is defined as an underlying challenge for this study to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia. Nevertheless, the grounded theory analysis has proposed the integrity restoration framework to promote transparency and accountability initiatives among the five processes of cooperation, controlling power, inclusiveness, accomplishment and development, through which sustainable development can potentially happen. The introspective coding matrix in Table 12 demonstrates the contexts and means for tolerating the consequences for each determined process. Consequently, the findings of the content analysis are consistent with those of the grounded theory analysis as both have addressed that transparency and accountability practices are the underlying phenomena for all other phenomena.

4.9. Chapter Summary

This chapter mainly identifies ways to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia by analysing observed data in depth. Data were collected from two sources: archival research from the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and Mongolian Stock Exchange and field observation at the NCCG. Each source of data has been analysed separately using different analysis techniques. A weighted scoring model approach under the content analysis technique has been applied to the data collected from archival research. The designed model had three sub-sections: transparency, shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting and BOD. Each section consists of a list of criteria with a unique weight. The weighted scoring model aimed to examine the degree of compliance with governance-relevant laws and regulations. The observational data showed that Mongolian companies respectfully to exceptionally comply with governance-relevant laws and regulations. However, certain criteria were not implemented in practice. Thus, the high compliance rate contradicts the reality.

Furthermore, qualitative grounded theory analysis has been to analyse information obtained from the observational study in the field site. The grounded theory analytical process involved three essential phases of data analysis: open, reflective and selective coding. Six initial categories have been identified in open coding, which have been further abstracted to a high level of connection during axial coding to contextualise the underlying category or central phenomenon. Accordingly, a conditional interrelationship guide, in addition to the introspective coding matrix, has been employed to transform the analysis into explanations and develop a theoretical framework. At the final stage of grounded theory analysis or selective coding, the storyline has been constructed together with a new emergent theoretical framework of integrity restoration. The theory yielded detailed conditions through which establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development will occur, similar to how it has been transformed.

Lastly, a cross-analysis has been performed on the content analysis and grounded theory analysis. The results revealed that findings from both analyses are consistent with each other as they address transparency and accountability practices. Therefore, the proposed theoretical framework of integrity restoration will be further discussed relative to the literature in the chapter of Discussion of Findings. Table 13 below summarises the data collection and analysis.

Table 13: Chapter Summary: Data Collection and Analysis

Analysis Method	Themes/Sub-categories	Findings	Emerged Framework	Theoretical	For Further Discussion
Content analysis	Transparency	Transparency	N/A		Integrity restoration theoretical framework
	Shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting				
	Board of directors				
Grounded theory analysis	Cooperation	Promoting transparency and accountability Initiatives	Integrity restoration		
	Controlling power				
	Inclusiveness				
	Accomplishment				
	Sustainable development				

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

5.1. Purpose of the Chapter

This chapter is comprised of four main sections: interpretation of study findings, discussion of implications, acknowledgement of study limitations and recommendations.

The interpretation section begins with a statement of key findings in which the gap in the research field and the primary study result of the integrity restoration framework will be reiterated. This serves not only to close the research gap but also to address specific research questions. The framework involves five fundamental processes: the practice of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power, enhancing inclusiveness, accomplishment and sustainable development. Each of the processes includes several practical approaches that address the research questions.

The section on implications focuses on how the integrity restoration framework fits with previous studies, what are the new contributions and how the findings are different from other studies. These are followed by a statement of study limitations and recommendations.

5.2. Key Findings

We addressed an absence of transparency and insufficient accountability practice at the larger scale. A multi-methods approach has been applied to collect data for this study. The findings from weighted score modelling, which has been applied under content analysis, revealed that even though all three themes have a high compliance rate in comparison to observed information, some of the criteria have not been complied practically. Therefore, we conclude that Mongolian corporate governance rules and regulations are just rules without practice and compliance without implementation. The weighted score modelling has also disclosed that the practice of transparency and accountability is the bottleneck to greater respect of shareholder rights and the effective formation of a board of directors. The pursuit of greater transparency and accountability enables civil society to criticise practices, implementations, and the meaningfulness of laws and regulations. This is expected to establish normative layouts of isomorphic institutional pressure to government, public services and corporations, in order to effectively form a board of directors to meet different needs.

This study often contains information about practices and attitudes which were not on documents. Observed information provided an explanation as to why the high compliance rates contradicted reality. The data has been analysed through grounded theory analysis, which enabled us to develop the integrity restoration framework (demonstrated below in Figure 5), in pursuit of the promotion of transparency and accountability initiatives. This occurs through five processes, which are cooperation, controlling power, inclusiveness, accomplishment and development, which permit sustainable development. Furthermore, each process involves various transparency and accountability approaches, which are expected to enhance cooperation between different social participants, to decentralise controlling power from the hands of a few corrupt individuals, and to promote public participation

at different levels of the decision-making process. These have been considered an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in developing country of Mongolia.

Figure 5: Integrity Restoration Framework

5.3. Addressing Research Question 1: What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be used to enhance structural cooperation among different social participants, as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption, and to support sustainable development?

Cooperation was emphasised as one of the main premises in establishing effective corporate governance practices. It was a starting point for the introduction of the study’s integrity restoration framework. According to Graham et al. (Graham et al., 2003) effective corporate governance can be perceived as cooperation or interaction between processes, structures and institutions. It can be claimed that the practice of transparency and accountability processes enables systems and institutions to be cooperative, and plays a crucial role at all levels, including the business environment. Sir Adrian Cadbury—corporate governance committee director in the United Kingdom (Cadbury, 1992) highlighted that businesses hold interim responsibility towards the society, market, institutional environment and the economy. From this, it can be reasoned that putting pressure on companies and institutions to act transparent, accountable and responsible is believed to make a difference towards the establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Even a small improvement in transparency and accountability practices is expected to support cooperation between processes, structures and institutions, primarily in a developing country where grand corruption and optimum corruption are widespread in-state entities.

Correspondingly, the study findings have outlined the following approaches to enhance structural cooperation between different social participants, and contribute toward overall transparency and accountability practices at a larger scale.

Figure 6: *Defined Transparency and Accountability Approaches to Enhance Cooperation among Different Social Participants*

The standardised format of information: While we gathered data to establish the weighted score model, we found the companies' annual performance reports to be vague, lengthy and variable between companies. It seems companies provide their reports just to comply with existing rules and regulations of submitting it before the deadline set by the Mongolian Stock Exchange, rather than giving it practical importance. It plays a significant role in society, market, institutional environment and economy, by providing a complete statement measuring the outcome of activities throughout the financial year. Therefore, setting a standardised format for the annual report is necessary because it will challenge businesses to be responsible for their operations. A clear set of standardised formats will gradually develop along with good governance practice. Potential advantages of the standardised format report can be:

- *Improves reliability* - A standardised format will remove extra information or any guesswork.
- *Productivity* - The pre-established format will require specific information. So, there is no need to look for documents to prepare or ask for help.
- *Individual morale* - A standardised format will enforce individual transparency, accountability, responsibility and fairness. On the other hand, avoiding the disclosure of unnecessary information, manipulation of financial statements, or influence information autonomy.
- *Efficiency* - The format is in a pre-defined and optimised structure, which means some sections have required information, whilst providing flexibility for extra information.
- *Communication* - The standardised format also enforces consistency on reporting among different businesses, which will aid comprehension.
- *Limiting ambiguity* - Setting clear instructions will bring about reliable information on how the company performed during the financial year and it may direct businesses to focus on key performance indicators (KPI).

This improved disclosure of information is expected to provide simple access, so that it can be compared and contrasted for scrutiny by different social participants. As stated in the literature, cooperation is a transparent, accountable and interactive practice by which different social participants become jointly responsive to one another, together with scrutiny on the ethical acceptability, public desirability and sustainable development (Von Schomberg, 2011). Based on the definition of cooperation, requiring mandatory information along with voluntary information in an organised and standardised format is one of many ways of practicing transparency, accountability and interactive communication, whilst guiding companies' attention to mandated information areas. Thus, the standardised format for information is thought to enhance cooperation among various social stakeholders.

A requirement for audit and risk-relevant information: The audit report has just started to be requested from listed companies as of 2019 and is not mandatory. This should be required and enforced for listed companies rather than leave it to their discretion, especially in developing countries where corruption is widespread. This report plays a significant role in information autonomy, implementation and practice by providing reasonable assurance for the financial statements, confirming that they are autonomous from any fraud or material errors. Therefore, a requirement for audit of risk-relevant information has been considered as one of the approaches of transparency

and accountability that enhances cooperation among various social participants. Furthermore, the audit report enables:

- *A complete overview* – businesses, shareholders and other stakeholders are able to ascertain how the company is doing. Even though a firm ensures no errors from their side, small errors can happen and that needs to be prevented.
- *Provide additional viewpoints* – an audit report also contains explicit observations on whether a company is revealing exceptional compliance, as well as if the company has any serious flaws.
- *Advance credit rating* – providing regular audit reports will be good for strengthening the company's relationship with investors because they are always keen to know whether the business is successful and the company trustworthy.
- *Demonstrating reliability* – a routine audit report provides reliability for the company's statements and feeds reasonable assurance that the business is operating as planned. This will further impact investment inflows to the market and contribute towards economic growth.

Similarly, disclosing risk assessments is also crucial, as it reports a company's situation and possible risks likely to affect business operations, prospects, finance and performance. The importance of risk reporting is as follows:

- *Improvement in market efficiency* – a disclosure of risk improves transparency and decreases market uncertainty.
- *Requires continuous advancement* – risk reporting strengthens transparency by revealing significant areas which demand continuous advancement.
- *Provides reasonable assurance* – the risk report offers reasonable assurance for the management, the board and regulators that the company is progressively improving, ensuring high risk areas are solved, and investigating underlying factors to the problem being faced.

A requirement for audit and risk-relevant information not only strengthens transparency and accountability practices, but also permits companies to engage with various forms of responsibilities (Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017). It puts pressure on companies to provide assurance that businesses hold responsibility of doing no harm for society (Deschamps, 2012; Lee & Petts, 2013), and that they hold responsibility of doing good (Stahl et al., 2014), which demonstrates that they are conducting responsible governance (Jordan, 2008; Scherer et al., 2009). Such various responsibilities are important not only to achieve cooperation among various social participants, but they are also essential to establish effective corporate governance practices in developing countries, where corruption is widespread. In spite of the fact that an audit report is legally required for companies, particularly from non-banking financial associations, insurance companies, banks, and public entities, this is not practically implemented. It can be argued that this is a way for businesses to deliberately avoid being transparent and accountable for their actions.

Demonstration of performance indicators: Reporting of performance indicators were unclear, in that information about how well the business performed over the current financial year was only available from financial statements. In some cases, the businesses presented performance indicators without comparing them to the previous years.

The transparency and accountability approach require detailed explanation of how the business performed the current year, and allows public scrutiny. By enhancing cooperation among various social participants, it builds a solid communication network in a way the companies can gather and distribute market and business information, report business improvement, project future development, and declare a status to different stakeholders with more competence. It will further assist investors and shareholders to make evidence-centred decisions. This performance reporting should be submitted along with other necessary reports such as the annual report, accounts and financial statements. This should be embedded as mandatory information in the above-mentioned standardised format. Although it is simple practice, the absence of performance indicators can be interpreted as businesses intentionally avoiding to present them in order to hide their wrongdoings, by preventing transparency and accountability.

Maintenance of information autonomy: Since the annual reports were vague, lengthy, and variable, the necessary information could easily be manipulated. Thus, information autonomy presents a positive correlation with the previously discussed standardised format for information, audit report and risk-relevant information, and report of performance indicators. In regards to the standardised format for information, making certain information mandatory prevents the avoidance to disclose essential information. On the other hand, it has been mentioned that an audit report provides reasonable assurance for financial statements, proving that they are free from any fraud or material errors. Concomitantly, risk-relevant information declares potential risks which can affect the business operation and profit. In other words, when the audit report and risk-relevant information are absent, there is a high risk of manipulating balance sheets or lack of information autonomy. This leads to public distrust and increases doubt in processes and structures, negatively affecting cooperation. However, disclosure of the audit report and risk-relevant information improves information autonomy, gains public trust for processes and structures, and advances efficiency and effectiveness of cooperation between processes and structures.

Moreover, demanding performance indicators is another way of ensuring reliable and autonomous information. This transparent, accountable and interactive practice, by which various social participants become jointly responsive to one another together with scrutiny on the ethical acceptability, public desirability and sustainable development, forms cooperation.

Enforcement of implementations and practices: Insufficient implementation and practices of legal provisions have occurred in several areas, such as transparency, shareholder rights and shareholders' meeting, and BOD. It has been observed that companies have just replicated the legal provisions instead of implementing them in reality. Although the corporate governance code was launched 13 years ago in 2007 (USAID, 2008) and the regulation requires a comply and explain regime, the scope of challenges is still significant at an institutional environment. Thus, governance mechanisms are defenceless, they are just compliance without implementation due to the lack of transparency and reinforcement mechanisms, insufficient accountability, absence of implementation and practice, corruption, and misunderstanding of legal provisions derived from insufficient guidance.

Widespread corruption and opportunistic behaviour from governors, regulators, analysts and auditors leads to a concentration of internal controlling power which circumvents audit and risk management. In this case, own people

are recruited even though they are inappropriately qualified to be a member of the committee, thus assembling misrepresentation and fuelling further distrust and doubt in processes and structures, making investors unwilling and ultimately slowing down cooperation between processes and systems.

It has been discussed in the literature that there is no enforcement mechanism in contemporary regulatory framework. This is one of factors that causes failure in tackling corruption, even when Mongolia has been attempting to eliminate corruption for over thirty years. Therefore, the approaches proposed by this study are the way to recruit civil society to scrutinise ethical acceptability, social desirability, combat corruption and contribute toward sustainable development, potentiating success in a country where corruption is endemic.

Establishment of a reinforcement mechanism: Either reinforcement mechanisms are absent at all levels, or there is a lack of capacity for institutions to enforce the tenets previously described. Rules, regulations and codes exist, but they are not exercised practically by legal entities. Failure of the rule of law is one of the main issues in establishing effective corporate governance, combat corruption and contribute toward sustainable development. Because it has already been revealed that the Mongolian institutional environment and regulatory framework are weak, it is essential to seek alternative ways to establish enforcement mechanisms. Therefore, enforcement is the way to support cooperation between processes and structures, by eliminating doubt and gaining back public trust. Trying new ways to support cooperation can be unsuccessful since it can lead to more confusion, and misunderstanding. This approach recruits civil society at a larger scale to do this.

Improvement in transparency and accountability: Insufficient transparency and absence of accountability have been highlighted as the bottleneck in this research. Absence of or insufficient practices of the measures expanded before can be perceived as deteriorating the market, society, institutional environment, as well as economic growth. Any improvements proposed by this study are expected to advance cooperation between processes and structures to be effective at a greater scale.

Creating awareness and certainty: All the previously mentioned cooperation practices create not only better awareness, but also certainty in the market, society and institutional environment. This enables processes and structures to be efficient, progressively improve cooperation among different social participants, and expand transparency and accountability practices in the medium to long term. This progressive improvement can happen through reflective, coercive or normative layouts of institutional isomorphic force (Dimaggio & Powell, 1983) driven by a change in individuals' and groups' perceptions, views, goals, actions and beliefs. Therefore, the practices proposed herein had been contextualised as challenges in cooperation in the introspective coding matrix, and means for tolerating the consequences were determined as momentum in governance practice.

5.4. Correlation between Study Findings and Existing Study

The above discussed transparency and accountability practices have also been considered an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption and to support sustainable development. This study's proposed practices have been gathered through an observational study at the study field site.

Providing vague and lengthy annual reports, absence of audit reports, insufficient risk-relevant information, alongside lack of performance indicators, is the type of behaviour companies adhere to largely caused by pervasive corruption. Therefore, dealings in corporate governance framework involve broader determinants, as wider perception of corporate governance suggests (Ahunwan, 2002; Tsamenyi & Uddin, 2008; Wanyama et al., 2013). These proposed approaches further engage with the stakeholder model to corporate governance, which rejects the narrow perception of the shareholder model (Larcker et al., 2005), acknowledging instead various stakeholders who are influenced by or can influence the decision-making process of the company (Freeman, 1984). According to stakeholder theory, this study proposed transparency and accountability practices which enable the management to balance the interests of different stakeholders inside and outside the company, leading to decision-making which serves the interests of various stakeholders (Blair & Stout, 2001; Cadbury, 2003).

This has been absent at the larger scale. The constitution of corporate governance in Mongolia happened at the start of 1990s, and this economic reform was conducted in the interests of the collision of power constituted at the time, not the interests of the majority of Mongolians. Over the past three decades, Mongolia has been confronted with a growing number of socio-economic issues. The country has been demanding to review, improve, and reinforce country's rules, regulations, laws, norms and culture at the national level (Adegbite, 2015). Thus, in the case of Mongolia, national-level governance is more effective, and organisational-level governance is expected to be contingent. Enhanced transparency and accountability practice can be applied as an approach to influence the behaviour of organisations, and to provide assurance for shareholders, as well as prospective investors (Guttentag, 2004; Dembo & Rasaratnam, 2014).

In contrast, Alt and Lassen (2006) escalated that, when public officials and civil servants have a lack of accountability and limited transparency over the public services, corruption can potentially happen. Supporting this view, cross-country scholars emphasised that the government intervention is extremely connected to corruption when the central government controls the economic resources (Faccio et al., 2006; Dong-Hua et al., 2007; Parsley, 2009). This was the case in Mongolia, where the reform process has only served the interests of the few who were close to asymmetric information, when the country was shifting from a communist economy to market-controlled economy. Furthermore, there is limited government transparency inhibited by state secret law. USAID (2005) reported that the publication of state budget data reveals a bundle of figures, yet asset disclosure rules are not enforced on public officials. As a result, Brinkerhoff and Goldsmith (2004) described Mongolian politics as the structure that defines who takes what within society. In 2004, over a decade after its economic reform to a market economy, income per capita stood at just above \$460, ranking the nation with the poorest economies in the world. This is in stark contrast to the country being one of 29 rich developing countries in resources, recognised by the International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2012), hosting 10% of the world's coal reserves [equivalent to 162 billion tonnes, estimated in 2011, with 17 operating coal mines (Sawe, 2019), whilst the population is just over 3.3 million as of March 2021, according to the latest data from the United Nations (Worldometer, 2021). Thus, with an effective corporate governance mechanism, these resources could be distributed fairly.

Yet, recognised levels of corruption in the public sector according to businesspeople and experts, called the corruption perception index (CPI) 2020, produced by Transparency International (2021), reported that New Zealand and Denmark ranked first and second, the United Kingdom shared the 11th place with Canada, Australia and Hong Kong, the United States of America ranked 25th, whereas Mongolia ranked 111th. Ufere et al., (2010) debated that corruption has its causes in the institutional and economic condition of a state, and mirrors the political, cultural, economic and legal institutions of the nation. Moreover, Vargas and Sommer (Vargas & Sommer, 2014) asserted that corruption is a warning of tax fraud, shadow economy, socio-economic instability, a lack of social interconnection, insufficient capability for a state to reform, economic maladministration and statistical control.

In developed countries, broader transparency and accountability practices are exercised through mandatory reporting on environmental and social performance. Whilst voluntary corporate social responsibility (CSR) reporting is widely used, at least within international corporations, governmental conventions in Europe progressively demand it be mandatory. Although, there is no specifications to measure environmental and social impacts, providing necessary reports ensures transparency and accountability practices, but also the extent to which the business contributes towards sustainable developments. In developing countries, several studies revealed that the practice of accountability and transparency in corporate governance is poorly practiced (Akhtaruddin, 2005; Barako, 2007; Samaha & Dahawy, 2011; Agyei-Mensah, 2015). Thus, since the practice of transparency and accountability is the underlying cause for all the socio-economic issues, the proposed transparency and accountability approaches enhance cooperation among different social participants and make a significant contribution towards sustainable development.

5.5. Addressing Research Question 2: What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be applied to decentralise controlling power of block-holders, as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption, and to support sustainable development?

Controlling power has been defined as one of the three main grounds in the establishment of effective corporate governance practice, and appointed as a subsequent process of cooperation in the integrity restoration theoretical framework. Jreisat (2004) asserted that excessive concentration of controlling power in the hands of few individuals, along with government influence over national and regional governance, had been criticised for causing corruption, economic slowdown, immense poverty, political instability, chaos, muddled priorities and abuse of human rights of the residents and non-residents equally. Therefore, it is essential to decentralise concentrated controlling power as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, combat corruption and support sustainable development in Mongolia. When there is an absence of or insufficient practice of transparency and accountability, the condition becomes convenient to concentrate controlling power in the hands of a few corrupt individuals. In other words, transparency and accountability practices have a negative correlation with the concentration of controlling power. The study has proposed several transparency and accountability approaches, which are expected to enhance cooperation among different social participants and contribute toward the decentralisation of controlling power as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Defined Transparency and Accountability Approaches in Decentralisation of Controlling Power of Block-holders

Greater transparency and accountability: As previously noted, greater transparency and accountability practices will contribute toward the decentralisation of controlling power in the hands of a few individuals. Several approaches have been defined to enhance cooperation between various social participants, which, alongside transparency and accountability practices, is projected to decentralise controlling power since these proposed practices are designed for displaying business activities to the scrutiny of civil society.

Enforcing business owners to exercise their duty to the state: Enhancement in cooperation, as well as transparency and accountability practices, are expected to create normative layouts of corresponding institutional pressure towards business owners to exercise their duty to the by being responsible, compliant, and respect the rule of law. This isomorphic institutional pressure can only form through a change in individuals' and groups' perceptions, views, goals, actions and beliefs. Accordingly, transparency and accountability practices bridge to educate civil society regarding good governance and its benefits.

Anti-corruption measures: Greater transparency and accountability practices will permit public scrutiny, reveal corrupt activities and support the development of a culture of liberty. Hence, morally unacceptable behaviours must be scrutinised constantly and criticised publicly, pressure must be applied to these morally unacceptable activities and cheer responsible institutional behaviours, and anti-corruption measures must be reinforced. Mongolia has been working closely with the World Bank to reduce corruption, improve transparency and accountability practices, lower inequality and poverty, establish a foundation of good governance practice and sustainable development. In the meantime, the government has launched comprehensive policies for improving the reporting of budget spending, reinforcing e-acquisition, and establishing a domestic anti-corruption agenda, but these have not yet been enforced to combat corruption (BTI Transformation Index, 2018). Efforts have been unsuccessful for nearly three decades, with wide-spread corruption across different institutional structures. With the support of the integrity restoration framework, reinforcing anti-corruption measures can be possible,

underpinned by enhanced transparency and accountability practices, enhanced cooperation among different social participants, growing trust in the state, respect to the rule of law enforced by resident engagement, participation and multi-stakeholder cooperation.

Development of an independent judiciary system: The judiciary is one of the cornerstones in the establishment of effective corporate governance practices, to combat corruption and to support sustainable development. It must be independent of external influence, in particular of economic and political entities, such as industry associations and government agencies. However, BTI transformation index (2018) stated that, although independent judges are appointed by the judicial general council (JGC), over 34% cuts to their salaries during the economic recession, alongside insufficient resources, limits their financial independence, especially when it concerns a large amount of capital (U.S. Department of State, 2017). In this situation, the practice of greater external transparency and accountability can reveal judiciary intimidation or risk of harassment by mistreated actors, and also enable fair actions to be in place to confront corrupt activities.

Proposing appropriate policy: Through dynamic citizen engagement and participation, empowered by greater transparency and accountability, appropriate policy can be proposed. There are still extensive loopholes resulting in unintentional consequences, although the regulatory framework has evolved since the economic reform in the 1990s. In addition, over 70% of participants said that contemporary transparency policy associated with the business environment is ineffective, and the efforts of government towards anti-corruption are insufficient (Asia Foundation, 2018). On the other hand, Oman et al. (2003) highlighted that corporate governance associates with the state's public and private institutions, recognised and unrecognised, which collectively shape the relationship between managers and investors. Ahunwan (2002) and Okike (2007) reported that these institutions enforce the state's laws, rules, regulations, policies, practices, and set appropriate corporate norms. The definition of corporate governance therefore reveals wide influences in emerging economies. Similarly, greater engagement and participation of dynamic social participants, supported by a wider practice of transparency and accountability, will enable policymakers to propose appropriate policy for public and private sectors.

The rule of law to function: Cooperation and decentralisation of controlling power contribute towards the rule of law to function. We believe that improvement in cooperation, transparency and accountability practices will change individuals' perception, view, knowledge, belief and values. This will create further normative layouts of isomorphic institutional pressure in the market, society and in an institutional environment, to respect the rule of law.

Several reasons seem to cause failure of the rule of law. Firstly, although Mongolia has undertaken both legal and economic reforms based predominantly in their constitution and declared in 1992 (World Bank, 2016), a broad legal gap was left in the regulatory framework (USAID, 2005). Secondly, the regulatory system itself (prosecutors, judges, police) is severely corrupted in Mongolia (USAID, 2005; Asia Foundation, 2007). Although summary of law and regulations are publicly accessible, there is a lack of transparency which weakens the capability of specialists to access and scrutinise the laws, affecting the efficiency of institutions and professionals. In addition, clerks in public institutions, doctors, and teachers are the public officials whom ordinary citizens more often privately bribe to seek

service that Mongolians are usually entitled to (Asia Foundation, 2007). For this to change, there is a real necessity to recognise how to exercise the rule of law as it is intended.

Accordingly, improvement in the practice of cooperation, transparency and accountability is believed to contribute towards decentralisation of controlling power. In doing so, greater transparency and accountability practices, enforcing business owners to exercise their duty to the state, anti-corruption measures, development of an independent judiciary system, proposal of suitable policies and obedience to the rule of law are expected to shape the market, society and institutional environment. It has been asserted by Werlin (2003) that governance is an interconnected system of soft and hard practices of administrative control and decentralisation of controlling power by different approaches that affect the behaviour at the larger-scale of subordinates, participants and citizens. Consequently, the above-mentioned transparency and accountability approaches suggested by integrity restoration framework had been contextualised as a judgement in the introspective coding matrix, because better transparency and accountability will welcome more judgements or critics from enhanced public engagement and means for tolerating consequences had been specified as public participation.

5.6. Correlation between Study Findings and Existing Study

The transparency and accountability approaches proposed to enhance cooperation among various social participants are also expected to decentralise controlling power. The economic reform process that took place in the 1990s was not in the interests of the mass plurality of Mongolians, but in the interest of the power of coalitions constituted at the time (Nixson et al., 2000). As a result, nationalised productive-assets have been denationalised to a few agile and corrupt individuals under non-transparent negotiation. This concentration of ownership in the hands of an individual or a few bulky shareholders, termed as block-holding, has been a long-lasting challenge in corporate governance (Holderness, 2003).

Asymmetric information facilitates rent-seeking opportunities and allows plenty of room for corruption. Reinsberg et al. (2019) stated that outsiders can access limited information compared to insiders, including public officials and managers who have the opportunity to take advantage of this information to augment themselves in the process. In contrast, Rose-Ackerman (2002) argued that buyers offer surpass payments to decision-makers, in order to enhance their likelihood of attaining or preserving dominant rents in previous nationalised enterprises. Martimort and Straub (2009) claimed that once these individuals have owned assets during the privatization, they search ways to protect their newly owned assets without any punishment from the state, since rent-takers potentially bribe a bureaucrat in exchange for complimentary treatment. Reinsberg et al., (2019) reasoned that, in the short term, privatization can lessen control for corruption, as individuals who have personal interests will likely have a lower possibility of being detected and prevented from punishment, given the vulnerability of institutions in developing countries.

Over the years, consequences of these practices have been raising concern in the market, society, institutional environment and hindering sustainable development in many ways. The economy is characterised by an extensive concentration on a limited range of products such as gold, cashmere and copper, whilst leaving other sectors

abandoned. Moreover, during the parliamentary election in 2004, nearly 70 per cent of total MPs accounted for business interests. The extensive patron-client relationship involves a complex network of personal connections between bosses or political patrons and their followers or individual clients Brinkerhoff and Goldsmith (2004). These connections are often developed on joint material benefits: the patrons supply limited resources to clients and in turn become partners for their cooperation and support. The patron holds inconsistent power and consequently enjoys sloppy permissiveness when it comes to the distribution of assets.

Kettering (1988) argued that, in contemporary policies, almost all patrons are not autonomous actors, but form connections within a big network of contacts, often acting as middlemen who organise exchange between the individual and the state. Patrons neglect the long-term state interest, whilst focusing on assisting their clients. Migdal (1988) claimed that, in recent days, patron-client relationships tend to expand in weak political and institutional environments. Brinkerhoff and Goldsmith (2004) stated that weak and marginalised people in a community are trapped into such problem-solving contacts as a pragmatic reference to look for solutions to their frequent concerns, since they repeatedly face restricted access to essential sources of support. Various variables are defined as representative of political connections: personal relationships, family bonds, selection of ex-government authority as a director, and geographic closeness.

It is essential to enhance transparency and accountability practices. Smulovitz and Peruzzotti (2000) declared that the primary role of accountability and transparency is to prevent corruption and form social recruitment against this behaviour. Accordingly, this study has proposed several transparency and accountability approaches to enhance cooperation among different social participants, and further decentralise controlling power. One of the proposed approaches was a requirement for audit and risk-relevant information. Hopper et al., (2009) asserted that the auditing approach plays a significant role in revealing corrupt activities, permitting public assessment and developing a culture of liberty.

Consequently, these proposed transparency and accountability approaches are not only intended to enhance cooperation among different stakeholders, but they are also designed to decentralise controlling power.

5.7. Answering Research question 3: What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be used to promote public participation, as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption, and to support sustainable development?

Inclusiveness was determined as another of the three main premises in good governance theory, and outlined as the third process in the integrity restoration framework. Inclusiveness or public participation can be limited by corruption, whilst making life harder for the majority. Specific approaches to increase cooperation are the at the heart of enhancing inclusiveness, as presented in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8: Defined Transparency and Accountability Approaches in Enhancing Inclusiveness

Reduction in inequality and poverty: Improved transparency and accountability can eliminate poverty and inequality by applying the approaches proposed herein, which settle the asymmetry of information between citizens (principal) and public officials (agent), potentially reinforcing challenges that citizens can levy on public officials (Shleifer & Vishny, 1993).

Extensive transparency and accountability practice will not only enhance cooperation between different social participants and decentralise controlling power, but also enable the public to carry out effective monitoring over corrupt activities, decision-making and actions. It is expected that this will support the allocation of resources to people in need, especially those who are vulnerable.

Improved public services: Greater transparency and accountability, enhanced cooperation and decentralisation of controlling power will create a condition where corrupt activities are more apparent, permitting public assessment and developing a culture of liberty. Eabrasu (2012) stated that by doing so, morally unacceptable behaviours must be scrutinized constantly and criticised publicly, and pressures need to be applied to these morally unacceptable activities to cheer responsible institutional behaviours. In Mongolia, the survey reports on knowledge and perception of corruption also presented that the participants' family had given bribes in the last 3 months. Furthermore, 40% of survey participants in the education sector stressed that they had provided services without pay, gifts or cash to teachers or employees in the school and claimed that they pay bribes to get simple services (Asia Foundation, 2017). With support from the approaches proposed herein, this situation would be confronted, with the public receiving the services they are entitled to without a bribe.

Advanced standard of living: This can be attained as soon as civil society has effective monitoring mechanisms, facilitated by the successful application of the study proposals. Scholars declared that cooperation enables an inclusive process of mutual realisation of objectives and leads to the social tolerability of innovations (Stilgoe et al., 2013; Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017). Marti & Scherer (2016) escalated that this also facilitates the society to contemplate how the settlements between opposing collective objectives (e.g., potential settlements between stability, justice or public well-being and efficiency) should be governed, and to define what extent of harm or risk should be tolerated when modifying financial markets. In this matter, corporate governance would be enabled a mechanism to facilitate the organisation to cooperate, whilst taking social fears and needs into consideration. This

would enhance its capacity for doing good and limit its capacity for causing detriment, thereby combating corruption and enabling sustainable development.

Respect for human rights: The integrity restoration framework has the goal to combat pervasive corruption and contribute towards sustainable development. The consequences of corruption are perilous beyond its definition of exploitation of public power for self-interest, and involve crumbling of the rule of law, development, and effective governance. Corruption also hinders the equitable satisfaction of every human right, whether political, social, civil or economic, such as health, education, security, privacy, freedom of speech, liberty, life, as well as an equal standard of living. Since residents regularly pay bribes to receive services they are entitled to, it is essential to enhance general transparency and accountability practice, which the integrity restoration framework enables. Another primary role of wider transparency and accountability practice is to establish an effective corporate governance framework to uphold fairness and justice. Crouch (2014) escalated that the principle of fairness is not just about public well-being that can be attempted by political actions, it is also about interest, values, and preconceptions that can be expressed and recognized through time and institutional development.

Hence, the wider practice of transparency and accountability would empower expression and recognition of collective interests, values and preconceptions.

5.8. Correlation between Study Findings and Existing Study

The study introduced numerous transparency and accountability practices that have been leading to enhancing cooperation between different social participants, decentralising controlling power, and enhancing inclusiveness.

According to Meadowcroft and Steurer (2013), public participation ensures that governance mechanisms consider the perspectives and interests of diverse social participants, and utilises different knowledge supports when tackling collective issues. Beck (1992) asserted that it has great importance, especially when actors of society in constitutional processes of mutual interests challenge the destructive consequences and adverse effects of existing policies or acquire different public dogmas. Furthermore, Irvin and Stansbury (2004) asserted that the actual type of participants depend on the problem and the restraints associated with resources and time, as well as organisational and individual capacity for reflection. In developed countries, the problems confronted in regards to effective corporate governance practice and sustainable development seem to be focused on the narrow perception of corporate governance which concerns principal-agent relationship. However, in developing countries the problems are associated with a wider perception of corporate governance caused by underdeveloped institutional infrastructures.

Greater transparency and accountability as part of an effective corporate governance framework will not only safeguard fairness and justice, but also address inequality and poverty, ensuring unbiased access to opportunities and rights and a fair distribution of economic and social resources (Khoury, 2015). It also makes information equally accessible to various groups of stakeholders, shareholders, and managers (Giannetti & Simonov, 2006; Williams & Ryan, 2007). Bosse et al. (2009) claimed that the concept of fairness involves several justice systems: reflection of procedural-justice (i.e., justice and processes governing the allocation of resources), distributive-justice (i.e., a

distribution of materialistic assets) and interactional-justice (i.e., respectful, equal treatment throughout the interaction and exchange of information). Although various social participants' perception and interest of fairness can differ from each other, it is still necessary to produce actions that satisfy main stakeholders appropriately, to support access to resources required for civil society to maintain sustainable development (Frooman, 1999).

Furthermore, the competency of individuals, private-sector businesses, public-sector institutions, communities and public organisations should be included in activities in a consistent manner, which enables accomplishments of different favourable objectives involving anti-corruption, reduction in poverty, the establishment of good governance, economic gain and efficient public service distribution (Browne, 2002; Hope, 2008). Baser and Morgan (2008) argued that this capacity of increasing the dynamic of social participants is endogenous in sustainable development which focuses on the existing situation, apart from what donors are doing. The accomplishments are directly dependent on momentum and efforts to eliminate fragility (Barakat & Chard, 2002).

Citizens of Mongolia have been experiencing acts of corruption, increasing poverty, inequality, and inflation, and being mistreated by the public sector for over three decades. The survey data collected by the International Republican Institute (2017) reported that bureaucracy and corruption were below 15%, failed state policies were under 25% and income-inequality was over 35%. Overall, economic situations were estimated as very bad or bad by over 80% of participants (International Republican Institute, 2017). Later, the Asian Development Bank (2020) reported that over 28% of Mongolian citizens were still living in poverty by 2018; this national poverty line has been stable, with uneven improvement in poverty reduction among rural and urban areas. Therefore, it is critical to equalize power across social groups. This is significant particularly in areas where the public sector is the main source of economy and support and the private sector comparatively underprivileged. Regarding contextual-variables relevant to the characters of the nations, the economy and its governance mechanisms, it is essential to encourage policymaking, transparency in resource distribution, and enforce existing rules and regulations.

5.9. Accomplishments

The process of accomplishment in the integrity restoration framework is set to demonstrate what are the accomplishments that can be achieved through the practice of cooperation, improved transparency and accountability, decentralisation of controlling power and enhanced inclusiveness.

Figure 9: *Determined Accomplishments*

Greater awareness and understanding of reality: With improved practices in cooperation, transparency and accountability, decentralised controlling power and enhanced inclusiveness, a greater awareness and understanding of reality are expected. Absence of transparency and insufficient accountability lead to corruption, divided interests and distribution of different information, which further disassociates the public, leading to distrust and exclusiveness. The processes in the integrity restoration framework will promote systems and mechanisms designed to settle asymmetric information between citizens and public officials. A wider practice of transparency and accountability is likely to change individuals' and groups' views, beliefs, behaviour, and awareness of reality.

Advanced transparency and accountability: Defined approaches under the practice of cooperation are the fundamental practices in the market, society and institutional environment designed to advance transparency and accountability. They become a foundation for the process of decentralisation of controlling power and enhancing inclusiveness strengthen them. Thus, transparency and accountability practice has been steadily increasing through the practice of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power and enhancing inclusiveness.

Encouragement of public participation: Progressively improved transparency and accountability practice is projected to encourage public participation. Being open, transparent and accountable opens a door for everyone to participate, make public judgements, let public voice to be heard and enable civil society to become active in the development agenda. It also means acting responsibly and fairness for everyone. In parallel, encouraging public participation can be boosted through public education on the establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Furthermore, greater public participation in the development agenda creates normative layouts of isomorphic institutional force on government, government organisations, public entities and institutions to do their job better, in a fair and responsible manner. It will have a positive impact on distribution of administrative and public services to everyone, without bribes and discrimination.

Accordingly, encouraging public participation is undoubtedly one of the accomplishments that can be achieved through application of the integrity restoration framework.

Reinforcing implementation and practice: It is not only one of the approaches under the practice of cooperation, but designed to tackle implementation and practice from different angles. It is an effective approach to enforce the rule of law to function.

Setting strategies-measures-consistent oversight: Initially defined strategic approaches to achieve an advanced practice of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power, and enhanced inclusiveness, are achievements in themselves. In the case of Mongolia, these strategic approaches were absent, when they should be practised naturally in society. Therefore, reflecting a situation, determining strategies, setting measures and constant oversight have been considered as a starting point toward an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. The above defined accomplishments are contextualised as vision, and means for tolerating the consequences are determined as progressive recognition of vision in the introspective coding matrix.

5.10. Sustainable Development

The last stage of the integrity restoration framework is sustainable development. It can be achieved with an improved practice of transparency and accountability, enhanced cooperation among dynamic social participants, decentralised controlling power, and enhanced inclusiveness of social actors. These achievements will progressively contribute toward the parameters of sustainable development presented below in Figure 10. In the introspective coding matrix, it has been contextualised as meaning in vision, and the means for tolerating consequences have been defined as establishing good governance practice develops a positive economic condition and sustainable development.

Figure 10: Fundamental Components of Sustainable Developments

Advanced transparency and accountability: The introduction of the integrity restoration framework had the objective to augment overall transparency and accountability practice, which can then support enhanced cooperation among dynamic social participants, decentralise controlling power, and enrich inclusiveness of social actors. According to Maingot and Zeghal (2008), the objective of corporate governance accountability and disclosure is to disseminate and communicate information pertaining to the company's performance along with governance to external investors. Yet, the information is not only used by shareholders and investors to evaluate the performance of their assets, but it is also received by other stakeholders concerned with environmental and social policies. In other words, they maintain and boost the dynamic relationship between various participants with distinctive background (Husted & Folger, 2004).

In regards to wider perception of corporate governance, advanced transparency and accountability practice will not only allow civil society to access corporate information, but also permit accessing government information. The goal of advanced transparency and accountability practice is to oversee and monitor those delegated public funds must account for how resources have been distributed, consumed and value created. In order to set this monitoring mechanism, the public need to have access to relevant information to evaluate performance and scrutinise. Accordingly, the role of wider transparency and accountability practice is vital in settling asymmetric information between citizens (principal) and public officials (agent), moreover, contribution toward an establishment of effective corporate governance practice, anti-corruption framework and sustainable development. Therefore, augmentation of transparency and accountability practice is the central strategy in effective corporate governance framework, anti-corruption framework and sustainable development.

Advancement of transparency and accountability practice is not only concern in developing countries, but also challenge in developed countries. The literature review chapter has stated that broader transparency and accountability practices are exercised through mandatory reporting on environmental and social performance in developed countries. Voluntary reporting on corporate social responsibility (CSR) is widely used within international corporations and government entities. Reporting of CSR varies from corporation to corporation, at the same time, it is difficult to measure corporate performance on environmental and social matters. Nonetheless, providing necessary reports not only ensures transparency and accountability practice but also demonstrates corporate contribution toward public well-being, as well as, sustainable development. In comparison between developed countries and developing countries, such extent of transparency and accountability practice exercised in developed countries is, in the case of Mongolia, absent in developing countries.

The literature review has extensively emphasised that Mongolian productive national assets had been privatised to those opportunistic individuals who were close to asymmetric information or member of power of coalition constituted during the time of economic and institutional reform. Asymmetric information had been defined as inadequate distribution of information among supply and demand, it feeds on uncertainties and behavioural motives that are dishonest, triggering a moral jeopardy and principal and agent conflict. In other words, individuals who are insiders or close to source of information has a greater opportunity than the outsiders. Furthermore, asymmetric information leads to the development of patron-client relationships in which an

individual who has authority supply resources to another person (client) based on shared material benefits. On the other hand, it becomes the source of various socio-economic issues including inequality in income-distribution, increase in poverty, concentration on a limited range of products, constraining market competition, bribes to receive public services, pervasive corruption, whilst various social actors are basically barred from decision-making, they are involved in communication in a way of simply accepting information and staying passive.

Correspondingly, advanced transparency and accountability practice will encourage the public to stay engaged and scrutinise patron-client relationship broadly. The progressive public engagement and scrutiny underpinned by advanced transparency and accountability will confront settlement of asymmetric information between citizen and public officials.

Independent judiciary mechanism: The development of independent judiciary mechanisms is possible. It is one of the important elements in establishing effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption and support sustainable development. However, the Mongolian judiciary is highly corrupt due to their limited financial independence, even though independent judges had been appointed. Since failure of the judiciary system means failure of the rule of law to operate, such corrupt domestic institutions and an insufficient legal assurance worsen competition among businesses, consequently restraining investment. On the other hand, corruption also shrinks equality in opportunities and can enlarge disparities in household income.

As stated by Deakin et al. (2017), comparing Western Europe with other nations, a rational regulatory framework is a precondition for effective governance practice and the development of capitalism. This view considers the regulatory practices as needed to govern the state development (Deakin et al., 2017). Similarly, North (1990) claimed that wealthy countries are those which have formed strong institutions that create an environment to protect property rights and administration of contracts, in contrast to developing countries which have vulnerable institutions. Developing countries who have given strategic importance to privatisation when conducting economic reform tend to be confronted with many challenges, but one of them is the absence of a regulatory framework to execute privatisation (Oyejide & Soyibo, 2001). In the case of Mongolia, extensive legal gaps still persist in the regulatory framework, although revision of the main law took place in 2002 (USAID, 2005).

Consistent encouragement of initiatives: This study considers that effective corporate governance needs to be eternally open to diverse perspectives and different insights, and must be capable of challenging the status quo, by examining the dominant values, structures, behaviours and practices that concern efficiency, effectiveness and legitimacy. At the same time, governance mechanisms should be in a state of ever evolving reflection. Wider transparency and accountability practices will contribute to sustainable development by consistently encouraging diverse initiatives. Vob et al. (2006) asserted that public mutual response demands verdicts and that decisions should yield to action.

Sense of me matters: Previously discussed conditions of enhancing inclusiveness, encouraging public participation, respect to human rights and consistent encouragement of initiatives also create the condition of sense of me matter empowered by greater transparency and accountability practices. This further supports dynamic citizen engagement and participation. As stated by Fung (2006), in the lowest engagement methods, participants are

basically barred from decision-making but they are involved in communication: (1) simply accept information and stay passive, (2) hold the opportunity to or express their inclinations, (3) explore, transform or develop their inclinations. In the following two methods of participant engagement, every participant possesses a greater impact on decision-making: (4) bargaining and aggregation, the mindful preferences of the actors are gathered into a mutual choice which is often driven from participants' control resources. In methods of (5) negotiation and deliberation, the mutual decision is made based upon quarrelsome interaction. In other words, the participants attempt to make their mutual choices and shared preferences on principles, arguments and reasons on which all participants can correspond. The last method is (6) technical proficiency, whereby professionals whose proficient specialization and training demands them to solve that particular issue will determine participants choices and public policies.

Currently in Mongolia, citizens simply accept information and stay passive. The situation the country is in today could have been different if their interests, values and voices had been considered in decision-making. Progressively evolving transparency and accountability practice is expected to enforce collective interests to be considered in the development agenda.

Minor shareholder protection: It can be achieved with successful establishment of many of the conditions which have been discussed above. Protection of minority shareholders is one of the many issues in developing countries. In developed economies, the main problem in corporate governance can be defined as principal-agency conflict (Gillian, 2006; Brennan & Solomon, 2008). In developing economies, the main challenges in corporate governance can be described as installation of rule-based mechanism of corporate governance, in opposition to the existing relationship-based mechanism of corporate governance, confronting layered interests, promoting the acceptable culture, improving the protection of minority investors and encouraging good practice of corporate governance (Wanyama et al., 2009; Adegbite, 2015). Excepting the United Kingdom and the United States, practically everywhere else in the world the direct engagement of concentrated ownerships in the company stays the norm (La Porta et al., 2000). Many empirical studies have proven that block-holding involves significant transactional costs in various ways. One of the common examples is that controlling block-holders might enjoy private benefits which are not shared with various shareholders—so termed controlling private benefits (Dyck & Zingales, 2004) — by pursuing self-governing strategies, which might harm not just company performance and minority shareholders, but also other stakeholders such as creditors and employees.

This weak protection of minority shareholders is expected to improve under greater transparency and accountability practices, which are an essential element of market-based analysis of corporate behaviour and the primary requirement in facilitating shareholders to apply their rights properly (Brennan & Solomon, 2008).

Convenient economic condition: Enhancing transparency and accountability practice at the larger scale is an important move toward an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption and to contribute toward sustainable development. Previously discussed determinants for the processes of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power, and enhancing inclusiveness alongside determinants of achievements and sustainable development are important elements in creating a convenient economic condition

which protects shareholders, ensures their return on investment (particularly minority shareholders), and enforces agents to exercise their duty to the principal and state.

Moreover, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are the most significant in Mongolian economy, accounting for 98% of all enterprises, with three-quarters of them being microenterprises (Asian Development Bank, 2018). They face numerous complications to unlock their complete potential, with the most common constraint being limited access to funds, since only 10% of all 37000 enterprises have regular access to finance within banks (Asian Development Bank, 2018). This report suggests that the foremost necessity is to improve finance accessibility for Mongolian SMEs by creating co-financing options with local microfinance institutions and banks, expanding alternative financing instruments that are not available from domestic financial institutions, providing advisory or consultancy services for SMEs and noticeably review policy, mechanism and structure of governance, in order to improve business associations and to strengthen the business environment.

Creating convenient economic conditions underpinned by strengthened transparency and accountability practice at the larger scale provides flexible solutions for the financing problems of SMEs, so they can achieve their complete potential. It has been recognised that the advantages associated with SMEs are various, for example, (1) the reinforcement of entrepreneurship; (2) a greater possibility that SMEs will use labour rigorous technologies in a way that they have a direct impact on employability; (3) they are quickly established along immediate operation to accelerate returns; and (4) they can offset power versus the strategic large enterprises. Accordingly, the development of SMEs is seen as fast-tracking the realisation of larger socio-economic objectives involving poverty mitigation.

5.11. Relating Integrity Restoration Framework to Conceptual Framework

The integrity restoration framework, shown in Figure 5, involves five fundamental processes by which an effort to establish of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development are expected to happen in accordance with promoting transparency and accountability initiatives.

In the study conceptual framework, demonstrated in Figure 3, cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power and public inclusiveness have been recognised as three central premises in the establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development, underpinned by transparency and accountability practice. This study demonstrated that absence of transparency and insufficient accountability results in deteriorating cooperation among different social participants, concentrating controlling power in the hands of block-holders and narrowing public inclusiveness, which further impacts the spread of corruption and threatens sustainable development. Since the opposite holds true, the focus of this study was to identify practical transparency and accountability approaches to ultimately enable sustainable development.

In the integrity restoration framework, several transparency and accountability approaches have been introduced for the process of cooperation. The enhancement of cooperation among different social participants empowered by various transparency and accountability approaches permits: firstly, morally unacceptable behaviours to be scrutinized constantly and criticised publicly; secondly, pressures to be applied to these morally unacceptable

activities to cheer responsible institutional behaviours. Thus, greater transparency and accountability practice enables to tackle lofty challenge of pervasive corruption and contribution toward sustainable development.

The process of evolving cooperation influences the decentralisation of controlling power, by enforcing wider transparency and accountability practice. It reveals truth to the civil society, enabling people to make their judgement, and giving normative layouts of isomorphic institutional pressure to institutional entities. These favouring conditions allow public inclusiveness in the decision-making process of the development agenda. Public inclusiveness mechanisms are vital to the expectations of civil society. It can be argued that different social participants have different values and interests, yet, these need to be balanced. It has been recognised that another significant role of transparency and accountability in effective corporate governance practice is safeguarding fairness and justice. Khoury (2015) asserted that it addresses inequality and poverty by ensuring unbiased access to opportunities and rights and a fair distribution of economic and social resources. Accordingly, reduction of inequality and poverty, improved public services, advanced standard of living, and respect to human rights have been determined as essential elements in enhancing inclusiveness, which can be achieved by enhanced cooperation among various social participants, evolved transparency and accountability practice, and decentralised controlling power.

The accomplishment of determinants in each process is expected to support a progressive recognition of reality, encouragement of public engagement, reinforcement of implementation and practice, and further enables to set appropriate strategies, measures and consistent monitoring in place. Ultimately, conditions which have been developed throughout the processes will contribute toward sustainable development. Consequently, the integrity restoration framework is relevant to the study conceptual framework.

5.12. Discussion of Implications

A theoretical implication of this study is that promoting transparency and accountability initiatives is the key to establish effective governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Privatisation had a strategic significance in economic reform, shifting nationalised assets to the private sector. Disappointingly, state productive-assets have been transferred under non-transparent negotiation to a few corrupt individuals who were close to asymmetric information at the time. This process has been determined as the foundation to many problems that Mongolia faces today, such as grand corruption, optimum corruption, widespread corruption in the public sector and the private sector, increasing inequality and poverty, and increase in irresponsible and unfair activities in society. Moreover, the judicial mechanism and media are becoming more dependent on bureaucrats and wealthy individuals. Despite the fact that Mongolia is rich in mineral resources, the economy is concentrated in limited markets where high rent can be obtained, ranking the country with the poorest countries in the world. Thus, corruption has been expanding and manipulating systems and mechanisms under non-transparent and non-accountable negotiation. Subsequently, the research gap has been defined as an absence of transparency and insufficient accountability.

With the application of a multi-methods approach, this study has recognised that transparency and accountability practice is insufficient in governance systems and mechanisms. For instance, (1) businesses tend to report vague,

lengthy and insignificant information; (2) avoidance of audit and risk-relevant information which deteriorates information autonomy; (3) unclear presentation of performance indicators; (4) a lack of implementation and practice; and (5) scarce capacity in reinforcement mechanisms. These have been determined as fundamental approaches to promote transparency and accountability practice in order to restore integrity. Consequently, the study proposed the integrity restoration framework, which consists of the practice of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power, enhancing inclusiveness, acknowledging accomplishments and sustainable development. Thus, the integrity restoration framework aligns with the literature, but is different from other studies, based on the following grounds:

- The integrity restoration framework is focused on creating normative governance systems and mechanisms in developing countries, whilst the majority of governance relevant studies were conducted as corporate governance in developed economies.
- This research study is concerned with Mongolia, one of the developing economies with natural resources. Yet, there is substantial corruption across social structures, high level of poverty and inequality, absence of transparency and insufficient accountability, and failure of the rule of law to function. Thus, the study setting is complex.
- The study proposed the integrity restoration framework, which was developed through a qualitative multi-method approach: archival research and observation. These were believed to be the most appropriate methods for this study, considering the existing complexity and diversity of social problems in Mongolia. Therefore, the study employed a unique research design.

5.13. Study Findings Associated with Existing Theories

The integrity restoration framework has emphasised the significance of improving and strengthening transparency and accountability practice toward an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. With regards to protecting the investment of shareholders who are the real owners of the business (Bebchuk & Weisbach, 2010; Jensen & Mecklings, 1976), and ensuring a return on investment (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997), greater transparency and accountability practice creates favourable conditions which provide assurance and return on investment. This shareholder protection model is the dominant model in the narrow perception of corporate governance practice and not an appropriate theory when sustainable development is concerned, because it does not see sustainable development as being corporate responsibility.

In contrast, the stakeholder theory of corporate governance rejects the narrow perception of the shareholder protection model and supports a wider perception of sustainable development. The stakeholder theory facilitates the management to balance different interests and concerns of various stakeholders, inside and outside the company, defining a choice of action which serves the interests of different stakeholders (Blair & Stout, 2001; Cadbury, 2003). In contrast, Bres et al. (2018) argued that the stakeholder model has yet to offer systems that will enable businesses to cooperate broadly in moral and institutional concerns that safeguard the legitimacy of sustainable development. Therefore, the integrity restoration framework will pursue wider transparency and accountability initiatives to construct a mechanism which allows corporations to cooperate extensively on lofty

challenges toward sustainable development. In this respect, this framework is powerful because it maintains and boosts dynamic relationships between different stakeholders whose interests are in social well-being being incorporated in the business's decision-making.

It shares similar characteristics with the social CSR model to corporate governance, since this considers businesses as social actors who support the production of public well-being where states are unwilling or unable to manage it (Matten & Crane, 2005; Scherer & Palazzo, 2011; Scherer et al., 2016). Marti and Scherer (2016) stated that this model offers a more balanced strategy to liaise environmental objectives, social and economic matters, since it contains various measures for decision-making such as justice, efficiency and stability. Thus, the integrity restoration framework will support a more balanced strategy which considers dynamic environmental and socio-economic issues. Consequently, corporate development should not be primarily affected by capital drives, but should tackle social issues and serve the civil-society. The difference between the stakeholder model and the CSR model is that the CSR model enables a system that is grounded on consideration and recommends practice that assists with prioritizing objectives. Thus, despite the fact that cultural and regional differences require an application of appropriate governance theory considering the state situation and institutional setting (Farazmand, 2013), the integrity restoration framework provides flexibility and adjustment within any condition.

5.14. Study Limitations

Study literature review: The topic of this research study is an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in developing countries: a case of Mongolia. Finding relevant material which to address this viewpoint was the most challenging task throughout the research process, especially when we had no prior background information in the field. Moreover, the concept of corporate governance, corruption and sustainable development are diverse and complex. The majority of governance materials were in corporate governance in an advanced and developed economy, with minimal materials found in normative governance mechanisms. Since materials concerning normative governance mechanisms are scattered across a diverse field of studies, this can potentially affect the coherence of the literature review.

Translation: This research study is conducted in Mongolia. Pre-established criteria in weighted score modelling were based on company law, the law of security market and corporate governance codes in Mongolia. Therefore, original data gathered through archival research is in Standard Khalkha Mongolian and then translated into English. This may affect the adequacy of translation of criteria in weighted score modelling. All the original data collection materials for TOP-20 listed companies are provided in appendices.

Limited evidence for observation: During the content analysis of archival research, and grounded theory analysis of observation, we were limited in the provision of further evidence to support the observed data. For example,

- Governance relevant laws and regulations were just copied, without implementation and practice. This data was observed from administrative documents held in the Financial Regulatory Commission under supervision. Therefore, we would not be able to provide any evidence of this, even considering study ethical conduct.

- An audit report is not required even at the end of the financial year. It was just started to be recommended for companies from the year commencing 2019. Therefore, we would not be able to evidence how actively or inactively the audit was practised.
- Unstandardized format of information. This claim cannot be evidenced as there is no set of standardised formats for essential information such as performance reports other than financial, audit report and risk report. Moreover, companies' reports cannot be compared and contrasted due to their variety.
- There is a scarcity of legal provisions for other stakeholders, particularly customers, suppliers and employees. This claim cannot be evidenced due to insufficient information.

5.15. Recommendations

Working with governance advocates: While volunteering in the NCCG, we discovered that there are many organisations including the NCCG, the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and the Mongolia Stock Exchange who are advocates of sound corporate governance practice. They have a team of individuals that cooperate with the NCCG. It is a requirement for an individual who is on the board of directors in a registered company on the Mongolian Stock Exchange to attend governance training. It is mutually requested by the Mongolian Stock Exchange, the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission, and the NCCG. In addition, the NCCG works with international organisations to promote sound corporate governance practice. So, there are advocates of effective corporate governance practice, anti-corruption activities and sustainable development in Mongolia with whom individuals can work.

Publications: The practical execution of the proposed approaches in the integrity restoration framework in an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development can happen through a change in individuals' and groups' views, perceptions, beliefs and values. However, peoples' perceptions can deteriorate at the larger-scale due to an absence of transparency and insufficient accountability, which has been holding centre for a long period. Additionally, we observed a lack of publications regarding good governance practice, anti-corruption practices, sustainable development, and benefits of greater transparency and accountability practice. Although the NCCG supplies a good corporate governance practice report or magazine, (1) these publications are not distributed to market and society at a larger-scale, and (2) it does not come out on a regular basis, as the organisation is self-funded. Furthermore, developing countries like Mongolia needs to focus more on the wider perception of corporate governance practices or normative governance mechanisms rather than the narrow perception of corporate governance practices or organisational level practices, since organisational behaviour is habitual and reflective of the institutional environment and domestic governance systems and mechanisms. Therefore, it seems necessary to educate civil society about good corporate governance practices, anti-corruption practices, sustainable development, as well as the importance of a broader practice of transparency and accountability at the larger scale, especially in a country where corruption is pervasive with diverse personal interests. Accordingly, various forms of publications regarding the significance of greater transparency and accountability practice should be supplied to civil society.

Training: When existing normative governance systems and mechanisms are ineffective, existing alongside endemic corruption, the training course should focus on the advantages of establishing effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption, and sustainable development. Recognizing what are the governance challenges in Mongolia, how these should be tackled within the existing situation, and the importance of enforcing transparency and accountability practice, the course should focus on enhancing awareness and providing opportunities for individuals who are willing to work together towards positive change.

The social platform is a communication channel: Traditionally, the TV was the primary source of information. As reported by Transparency International (2018), the majority of 400 media firms are linked to politicians and business cartels. It has a massive negative influence on civil society by dividing public views, encouraging different interests and increasing doubts. Nonetheless, in recent years, internet and social media platforms have been dramatically expanding and becoming an information channel with time and cost efficiency. Therefore, social media platforms can be used as a communication channel to promote greater transparency and accountability initiatives, contribute toward an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Not just for promotion, since it should also demonstrate integrity through its activities, objectives and accomplishments. As a result of this continuous activation of initiatives and activities, it is expected that efforts will operate meaningfully by shaping the normative formation of isomorphic institutional force.

5.16. Chapter Summary

The research gap or problem was defined as an absence of transparency and insufficient accountability. The study resulted in the integrity restoration framework, which does not only promote transparency and accountability practice, but also leads to anti-corruption practices and sustainable development through five fundamental processes: the practice of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power, enhancing inclusiveness, acknowledging accomplishments and sustainable development. Each process encloses different practical approaches which progressively strengthen transparency and accountability practices toward anti-corruption practices and sustainable development. How this study's findings contribute toward closing the research gap has been discussed, followed by recommendations for practical implementations.

CHAPTER 6: STUDY CONCLUSION

6.1. Purpose of Chapter

This chapter concludes the entire study, ensuring all research questions are answered, discussing the new knowledge contribution and providing recommendations for further study. Accordingly, this chapter begins with addressing the research questions, summary and reflection on the research, new knowledge contribution, chapter summary and further research.

6.2. Answering the Research Questions

This research has explored alternative ways as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia.

Addressing Research Question 1: What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be used to enhance structural cooperation among different social participants as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption and to support sustainable development?

This study found integrity restoration framework offers several transparency and accountability approaches to enhance cooperation among dynamic social participants. These approaches include setting a standardised format of information, a requirement of audit and risk relevant information, maintenance of information autonomy, demonstration of performance indicators, establishment of reinforcement mechanism, improvement in overall transparency and accountability, and creating awareness and certainty. These approaches have been identified as an alternative transparency and accountability practices because when the researcher was conducting archival research based on the Mongolian Stock Exchange and the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission, it was noticed these practices were insufficiently practiced.

For example, an approach of setting standardised format of information was been identified when the researcher had been gathering data for pre-established criteria in the weighted scoring model from purposefully selected TOP-20 listed companies' annual reports. It was observed that the content of the report varies between companies, with some being vague, lengthy and difficult to compare and contrast. Therefore, setting a standardised format for mandatory information, as well as voluntary information will enforce companies to provide necessary information without avoiding important requirements, but also provides space for additional information in a voluntary section. While reviewing the archived documents, it was also noticed that audit and risk relevant information and performance indicators were hardly available. The audit report has already been recognised in many study disciplines as an important approach to strengthen transparency and accountability because it provides reasonable assurance for financial statements, guaranteeing that they are free from any fraud or material errors. Supply of this information will further support the maintenance of information autonomy by preventing any information manipulation, the establishment of reinforcement mechanism and an improvement in the overall transparency and accountability practice whilst enhancing civil society awareness and creating certainty.

Consequently, this approach enhances cooperation among different social participants, combats corruption and supports sustainable development by enabling civil society to constantly scrutinise morally unacceptable behaviours, apply pressure on unacceptable activities and applaud responsible institutional behaviours.

Addressing Research Question 2: What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be applied to decentralise controlling power of block-holders as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption and to support sustainable development?

Progressively augmenting cooperation and greater transparency and accountability practice will further enforce business owners to exercise their duty to the state, to reinforce anti-corruption arrangements, to develop independent judiciary system, to propose appropriate policy and, eventually, to respect the rule of law to function. Improved transparency and accountability practice, and enhanced cooperation, will enable the public to criticise wrongdoings, corrupt activities, and appreciate right behaviour. Thus, it develops normative layouts of corresponding institutional pressure on business owners to behave compliant, responsible, and respect the rule of law. Changes in groups' and individuals' perception, view, belief, goals and action underpinned by wider transparency and accountability practice can create such isomorphic pressure. Enhanced public engagement associated with improved behaviour of corporations will then allow anti-corruption arrangements to be effectively implemented. The literature has detailed that Mongolia has been working closely with numerous international organisations to combat pervasive corruption, strengthen transparency and accountability practice and eliminate inequality and poverty by contributing toward an establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development.

Additionally, the Mongolian government has introduced comprehensive anti-corruption policies including extensive reporting of budget expenditure, reinforcing e-acquisition, and instituting domestic anti-corruption agenda. However, these efforts have been unsuccessful, and corruption has been occurring across different institutional structures. Correspondingly, wider practice of transparency and accountability coupled with enhanced cooperation will not only encourage civil society to reinforce existing anti-corruption arrangements but also contribute toward the development of an independent judiciary system. Judiciary is one of the essential constituents in an effective corporate governance framework, an anti-corruption framework, as well as in a sustainable development agenda. It must be independent of external influences, particularly of economic and political entities such as industry associations and state agencies. Greater transparency and accountability practice alongside cooperation among different social participants will safeguard judiciary independence and, simultaneously, enable a proposal of appropriate policies by allowing legal professionals to review drafts before approval.

Furthermore, these progressively developing constituents, underpinned by greater transparency and accountability and cooperation will force dynamic social participants to respect for rule of law. Henceforth, gradually evolving transparency and accountability alongside enhancing cooperation, as well as independence of fundamental constituents will confront the concentration of controlling power in the hands of a few wealthy individuals and

contribute to establish effective corporate governance practice, combating corruption and supporting sustainable development.

Addressing Research Question 3: What practical transparency and accountability techniques can be used to promote public participation as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption and to support sustainable development?

Greater transparency and accountability together with cooperation and decentralised controlling power, on the other hand, can enhance public engagement. Public participation in decision-making can be weakened by the extent of corruption. Determined transparency and accountability approaches to enhance cooperation among different social participants and decentralising controlling power are the source for augmenting public engagement. Extensive transparency and accountability, reduction in inequality and poverty, improved public services, advanced standard of living, and respect for human rights have been identified as essential constituents in the process of enhancing inclusiveness.

Prior processes of greater transparency and accountability, enhanced cooperation and decentralised controlling power will assist in the reduction of inequality and poverty by settling asymmetric information between citizens (principals) and public officials (agents). Furthermore, they will allow civil society to engage and monitor decision-making, actions and corrupt activities. By doing so, allocation of national resources will be distributed effectively to those who are in need, specially, those are vulnerable, and public service will be improved by equal distribution of services without discrimination or bribes. This development of public engagement and monitoring mechanism will put pressure on corporations to cooperate whilst taking social fears and needs into consideration, in a way through which overall living standard will be advanced. Another benefit of greater transparency and accountability, enhanced cooperation and decentralised controlling power, is upholding fairness and justice. Notion of fairness is beyond public well-being, which can be attempted by political action; it is also about interests, values and preconception that can be expressed and recognised through time and institutional development.

Consequently, greater transparency and accountability, enhanced cooperation among different social participants, decentralisation of controlling power in the hands of few individuals alongside enhanced inclusiveness succeeds progressively in the wider practice of transparency and accountability, augmented public engagement, reinforcement of implementation and practice mechanisms, greater public awareness and understanding of reality. Moreover, the setting of feasible strategies, measures and consistent oversight in place will also help the achievement of this objective. Furthermore, constituents developed through the process of cooperation, decentralisation of controlling power and public inclusiveness have contributed toward sustainable development including greater transparency and accountability, independent judiciary mechanism, consistent encouragement of initiatives, sense of me matter, and more importantly, minor shareholder protection alongside convenient economic conditions. Thus, the study finding of the integrity restoration framework is designed to promote transparency and accountability initiatives and restore integrity in the society, market and institutional environment of Mongolia as an effort to establish effective corporate governance practice, to combat corruption and to support sustainable development.

6.3. Summary and Reflection on the Research

This study focused on establishing effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development concerns based on the wide perception of corporate governance practice in Mongolia, where corruption is endemic. Increasing poverty, inequality and unfair and irresponsible acts from bureaucrats and wealthy individuals are the motivations to explore alternative ways to establish effective governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development.

The researcher has volunteered in the NCCG, the only recognised professional organisation in the field in Mongolia. It has opened further opportunities to conduct qualitative archival research from the Mongolian Stock Exchange and the Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission for the top 20 companies with high indexes on the stock market. This study focused on the wide perception of corporate governance practice. Thus, it required considerable data to provide a holistic view.

Similarly, the observational study has enabled the researcher to observe practices and behaviours in the social setting. Observational studies are often applied in complex social-life settings as it allows to obtain a holistic understanding in the field of study. In addition, the archival research has allowed the researcher to obtain authentic information from archived materials which can be compared and contrasted against the observational study. Thus, the qualitative multimethod approach was not only an appropriate method for this study, considering the focus on the wide perception of corporate governance practice and fragile state, but also a combination of methods that strengthens research validity.

The observational data based on the NCCG and the archival research from the Mongolian Stock Exchange and Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission resulted that companies' annual reports are unstandardized, lengthy, vague and time-consuming. Audit- and risk-relevant information were missing; demonstration of performance indicators was insufficient; and the implementation and practice of relevant laws and regulations were absent, which limit transparency and accountability practices. These issues have been defined as alternative ways to improve and strengthen transparency and accountability and further contribute to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in Mongolia.

The results of this research are unexpected. Enforcing these approaches through civil society engagement is expected to improve and strengthen transparency and accountability, enhance public inclusiveness and form normative layouts of isomorphic institutional pressure on the government, institutions, government organisations and administrative offices to deliver services to citizens fairly and responsibly. Thus, constantly improving and strengthening transparency and accountability is essential as they recruit civil society against corrupt comportment. Consequently, the study results have met the researcher's expectations.

In the case of Mongolia, developing countries have been recognised to have expansive socio-economic challenges and complexity. Democracy, liberty, public administration service, poverty and inequality, corruption, institutions and development among others are evident in Mongolia. Thus, focusing on the wide perception of corporate governance practice is more appropriate than the narrow perception. Consequently, a constant effort on

transparency and accountability improvement will socially construct effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development in the long term.

6.4. New Knowledge Contributions

6.4.1. Theoretical Contribution

The grounded theory analysis was performed on the observational data and have resulted in the integrity restoration framework. The analytical process involved three stages of data analysis: open, axial and selective coding. In open coding, different sources of observational data have been described in detail and coded into six initial categories.

In axial or reflective coding, the initially identified categories were constantly compared to determine patterns and interrelationships. Accordingly, the conditional interrelationship guide was established by asking exploratory questions of what, when, where, why, how and consequences. Addressing these questions has enabled the researcher to understand emerging patterns and interrelationships. Cooperation, controlling power and inclusiveness has been determined as the existence of patterns and interrelationships between different categories. These patterns have also been addressed in the literature review, where cooperation, controlling power and inclusiveness had been identified as the central challenges to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development.

In the selective coding, the storyline was established. The introspective coding matrix has been employed to capture an advanced level of speculation to progress to the final stage of data analysis, namely selective coding. Then, the formulated framework in the storyline was explained while visually demonstrating the combination of conditional interrelationship matrix and storyline. In this study, the conditional interrelationship guide has presented the dynamic elements of the emerging theoretical view of the integrity restoration framework. A combination of the conditional interrelationship guide and introspective coding matrix enabled the transformation of the analysis into explanations and framework development.

The integrity restoration framework emerged in pursuit of promoting transparency and accountability initiatives. The Discussion of Findings chapter illustrates that great practice of transparency and accountability promoted by the integrity restoration framework maintains and boosts cooperation between different social groups, recruits civil society against corruption and wrongdoings, forms normative layouts of isomorphic institutional pressure in society, and contributes to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Thus, the theoretical contribution of this study is the restoration of integrity by promoting transparency and accountability initiatives to establish effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development, despite social, institutional and regional differences.

6.4.2. Methodological Contribution

This study conducted qualitative archival research in the Mongolian Stock Exchange and Mongolian Financial Regulatory Commission and field observation at the NCCG site. Thus, one of the methodological contributions of this study is the uniqueness of the research design. If this study would be replicated applying a similar research

design in the same organisations, (1) the researcher's perception and arrangements could differ, and (2) the data content of future studies could be different because this study is based on the 2019 data as the latest.

For the archival research, the weighted scoring model has been applied to capture an extensive amount of documented information. The model has been designed based on the Mongolian security market and company laws and corporate governance code. Each criterion in the weighted scoring model has been quantitatively measured and qualitatively interpreted. The model has delivered certain methodological contributions to this study, enabling the researcher to (1) capture the desired data in a pre-established format, (2) maintain organisation and order and (3) be effective and efficient in terms of time and cost. Additionally, the grounded theory analysis has been used in the observational study. The methodological contributions of the grounded theory analysis included (1) theory development from data analysis and (2) logical speculation. Therefore, this research has generated several methodological contributions.

6.4.3. Practical Contribution

The study focused on establishing effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development. Thus, possible practical implications of the integrity restoration framework were discussed.

The study findings regarding sustainable development showed that great transparency and accountability is expected to bring stability and certainty in the market, society and institutional environment and propose policies that support sustainable development. Improved regulatory environment achieved by the successful implementation of the integrity restoration framework is expected to enforce the implementation and practice of rules and regulations, ensure respect for the rule of law, restore integrity, support fair competition and provide equal protection for everyone.

Moreover, the study findings regarding sustainable development showed that a successful implementation of integrity restoration will set anti-corruption mechanisms, create jobs and alternative market developments, increase fair competition in the market and society, reduce poverty and inequality and enhance public awareness of the importance of good governance, development agenda and economic growth among others. Thus, the study proposed that the integrity restoration framework starts with simple, practical approaches and then progressively tackling larger socio-economic challenges from various aspects.

6.5. Chapter Summary

The research questions for this study have all been met. The selected qualitative multimethod approach has enabled the researcher to explain the research questions in detail. The chapter has also discussed the theoretical, methodological and practical contributions of this study to establishment of effective corporate governance practice, impacts on corruption and sustainable development.

6.6. Further Research

Future research is suggested to apply the theoretical framework introduced in this research in the real-life setting and extend this study by associating expansive social influencing factors in developing, aid-receiving countries with study-specific governance systems and processes. Accordingly, future research will apply and explore the depths in the field of governance. Therefore, a qualitative study is the most effective approach. If future research approves the practical application of the theoretical framework developed in this study, the validity of this study will be improved. Moreover, if future research employs the same qualitative ethnographic study at the field site, then the findings of this study will be reproduced, and the reliability will be strengthened.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: *Reference Letter for Field Study*

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 2: Business Card in English

Appendix 3: Business Card in Mongolian

Personal details withheld.